

AN EXAMINATION OF THE RANDOMISED CONTROLLED TRIAL
AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL EVIDENCE FOR THE INTRODUCTION
OF DIETARY FAT RECOMMENDATIONS IN 1977 AND 1983:
A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS

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Declaration

I have not registered for any other award of the University of the West of Scotland, or of any other academic or professional institution during this research programme. The material in this thesis has not been used in any other submission for an academic award.

Zoë Verna Harcombe

Part of the work in this thesis has been previously reported in the following papers and conference presentations:

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Abstract

Introduction: National dietary guidelines were introduced in 1977 and 1983, by the United States (US) and United Kingdom (UK) governments respectively, with the intention of reducing deaths from coronary heart disease (CHD) by reducing or modifying fat intake. The two specific guidelines recommended the consumption of no more than 30% of total calories as dietary fat and no more than 10% of calories as saturated fat. To date, no analysis of the evidence base for these recommendations has been undertaken.

Methods: A systematic review and meta-analysis was undertaken of RCTs, published prior to 1983, which examined the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD and all-causes. A systematic review and meta-analysis was undertaken of RCTs, currently available, which examined the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD and all-causes.

A systematic review was undertaken of epidemiological evidence published prior to 1983, which examined the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD. A systematic review and meta-analysis was undertaken of epidemiological evidence currently available, which examined the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD.

Results: For RCTs available at the time the dietary fat guidelines were introduced, the risk ratio (RR) for dietary fat interventions and all-cause mortality was 0.982 (95% CI, 0.878 to 1.098). The RR for dietary fat interventions and CHD mortality was 0.951 (95% CI, 0.784 to 1.155).

For RCTs currently available, the RR for dietary fat interventions and all-cause mortality was 0.991 (95% CI, 0.935 to 1.051). The RR for dietary fat interventions and CHD mortality was 0.976 (95% CI, 0.878 to 1.084).

The reductions in mean serum cholesterol levels were significantly higher in the intervention groups (effect size > 1.0); this did not result in significant differences in CHD or all-cause mortality.

The epidemiological evidence available at the time the dietary fat guidelines were introduced included one prospective cohort study that found an association between CHD mortality and saturated fat, but not total fat, intake. Five other studies found no association for total or saturated fat.

For epidemiological evidence currently available, the RR for total dietary fat and CHD deaths was 1.06 (95% CI 0.97 to 1.16). The RR for saturated fat and CHD deaths was 1.13 (95% CI 0.93 to 1.37).

There were no statistically significant relationships from any of the meta-analyses undertaken.

Only one RCT currently available examined dietary fat and CHD mortality in men and women without previous heart disease. All other RCTs lacked generalisability. Only one prospective cohort study currently available examined dietary fat and CHD mortality in healthy men and women. All other prospective cohort studies lacked generalisability.

The specific dietary fat recommendations made were untested in any trial prior to being introduced.

Conclusion: Studies examining the relationship between dietary fat and CHD mortality have largely been undertaken on men and often men with pre-existing heart disease. The evidence for males with secondary disease was not conclusive. Dietary guidelines were introduced for whole populations despite this.

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Note

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Note

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List of abbreviations

BD	Professor Bruce Davies
BMI	Body Mass Index
CHD	Coronary Heart Disease
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
DART	Diet And Reinfarction Trial (RCT)
FG	Dr. Fergal Grace
g	Grams
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HDL	High Density Lipoprotein
IHD	Ischemic Heart Disease
LDL	Low Density Lipoprotein
mg	milligrams
mg/dl	milligrams per decilitre
MI	Myocardial Infarction
mmHg	millimeters of mercury
mmol/l	millimoles per litre
MOOSE	Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology methodology
MRFIT	Multiple Risk Factor Intervention Trial
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
RR	Risk Ratio
SD	Standard Deviation
STARS	St Thomas' Atherosclerosis Regression Study (RCT)
UK	United Kingdom
US	United States
WHI	Women's Health Initiative (RCT)

Glossary

Abell-Kendall method: The Abell-Kendall method is a standard reference method for estimation of total serum cholesterol without interference from bilirubin, protein, and haemoglobin.

Anthropometric: Anthropometry is the science that defines physical measurements of a person's size, form, and functional capacities.

Atherosclerosis: Atherosclerosis is a specific form of arteriosclerosis. The term refers to build up of plaques in the arteries.

Arteriosclerosis: Arteriosclerosis refers to a thickening and hardening of arteries.

AutoAnalyzer N-24 method: The AutoAnalyzer N-24 method is a standard reference method for estimation of total serum cholesterol based on the ferric chloride reaction. The Abell-Kendall method was noted as the most used reference method following its introduction in 1952. The AutoAnalyzer N-24 method was found to give comparable results to the Abell-Kendall procedure with the benefit of a degree of automation (National Institutes of Health: National Heart Lung and Blood Institute, 1995).

Bifurcation: Bifurcation is the division of something into two parts. This describes locations where arterial branches occur.

Blood plasma: Blood plasma (sometimes called just plasma) is obtained by taking a sample of blood and removing blood cells. The red blood cells and white blood cells are removed by spinning with a centrifuge. Chemicals are added to prevent the blood's natural tendency to clot.

Blood serum: Blood serum is prepared by obtaining a blood sample, allowing formation of the blood clot, and removing the clot using a centrifuge. Both plasma and serum are light yellow in colour. Blood serum is blood plasma without clotting factors.

Cholestyramine: Cholestyramine is a medication that binds bile in the gastrointestinal tract to prevent its re-absorption. The resulting loss of bile acids is addressed by the liver by converting more serum cholesterol to bile acids to normalise levels, thus lowering serum cholesterol levels.

Cohort study: See observational study: Cohort study.

Digitalis Glycosides: Digitalis Glycosides are medications indicated for the treatment of congestive heart failure. They have a positive inotropic action, which stimulates and increases the strength of heart muscle contraction.

Eucaloric: Eucaloric means in caloric balance: at an intake designed to maintain weight.

Funnel plot: See Statistical terms in meta-analysis.

Haemodynamics: Haemodynamics is the study of blood flow.

Intima: Intima is the innermost coating or membrane of a part or organ, particularly of a vein or artery.

Lecithin: Lecithin is a generic term to designate any group of yellow-brownish fatty substances occurring in animal and plant tissues composed of phosphoric acid, choline, fatty acids, glycerol, glycolipids, triglycerides, and phospholipids.

Linoleic acid: Linoleic acid is a polyunsaturated omega-6 fatty acid.

Linolenic acid: Linolenic acid is a polyunsaturated omega-3 fatty acid

Meta-analysis: Meta-analysis is a statistical technique for pooling data. Meta-analysis is one of the steps undertaken during a systematic review. Best practice methodology for systematic review and meta-analysis was defined in 2009 with the PRISMA statement (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) (Moher et al., 2009). The earliest use of the term meta-analysis is credited to Gene Glass (Glass, 1976). Systematic review of data is always possible; meta-analysis is not always possible – it depends on the data available.

MOOSE: MOOSE is an acronym for “Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology methodology” (Stroup et al., 2000). This is the best practice methodology for systematic review of observational studies.

Nosologist: Nosology is a branch of medicine that deals with classification of diseases. A nosologist is a practitioner of disease classification.

Observational study: An observational study is where no intervention takes place. The researcher *observes* and assesses the strength of the relationship between an exposure and a disease variable. There are three types of observational study (Song and Chung, 2010):

- Cohort study: A cohort study can be prospective (looking forward) or retrospective (looking back). Cohort observational studies are sometimes called longitudinal studies. The word “cohort” in epidemiology means “a group of people with defined characteristics who are followed up to determine incidence of, or mortality from some

specific disease, all cause of death, or some other outcome.” (Morabia A. A History of Epidemiologic Methods and Concepts. Birkhaeuser Verlag; Basel: 2004. pp. 1–405).

- **Case-control study:** A case control study looks at the present and past. The key difference between a case-control study and a cohort study is that the case-control study has a control, or unexposed, group. For example, the Richard Doll smoking study followed a number of people over time and divided them into those who developed cancer and those who didn't. It then evaluated the smoking incidence among those who developed cancer vs. those who didn't.

- **Cross-sectional study (prevalence study):** A cross-sectional study looks at the present. It can be viewed as a 'snap-shot'. It cannot assess cause and effect.

Occidentals: Occidentals are people from the western part of the world – the Occident

PRISMA: PRISMA is an acronym for “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses” (Moher et al., 2009). See Systematic review.

Prospective Cohort study: See Observational study: cohort (prospective).

Randomised Controlled Trial (RCT): A randomised controlled trial is a study in which participants are randomly assigned (i.e., they have an equal probability of being assigned to any group) to a control group or an intervention group. Procedures are controlled to ensure that all participants in all study groups are treated the same except for the factor that is unique to their group. The unique factor is the type of intervention that they receive.

Statistical terms:

- **Effect size:** The effect size is calculated as the mean (intervention) minus the mean (control), divided by the pooled standard deviations (Coe, 2002).
- **Egger's regression intercept:** Egger's regression intercept uses the inverse of the standard error to predict the standardised effect (the effect size divided by the standard error). The more the intercept deviates from zero, the more pronounced the asymmetry. If the *p*-value (1 tailed recommended) of the intercept is 0.1 or smaller, the asymmetry is considered to be statistically significant.
- **Fisher's exact test:** A statistical test of independence of rows and columns in a 2 by 2 contingency table. Its null hypothesis is that intervention does not affect outcome – the two are independent. This is rejected if the *p* value is small/significant.

- **Funnel plot:** The funnel plot measures study size on the vertical axis as a function of effect size on the horizontal axis. Large studies appear toward the top of the graph and tend to cluster near the mean effect size. Smaller studies appear toward the bottom of the graph and are dispersed across a range of values. In the absence of publication bias studies are distributed symmetrically about the combined effect size. In the presence of bias, the bottom of the plot shows asymmetry. This reflects the fact that smaller studies, toward the bottom, are more likely to be published if they have larger than average effects, which makes them more likely to meet the criterion for statistical significance.
- **I²:** is the proportion of the variance that reflects differences in true effects rather than sampling error. If there are no differences in true effects (all differences can be attributed to sampling) then I² is zero. If no differences can be attributed to sampling then I² is 100%.
- **Q:** reflects the distance of each study from the mean effect (weighted, squared and summed over all studies). If all studies share the same effect size, the expected value of Q would equal the degrees of freedom. If Q is greater than df(Q) there is some dispersion of effects. If *p* is concomitantly <0.1 (which is the recommended criterion for this test), the excess dispersion is statistically significant.
- **T²:** is the estimate of between study variance in true effects. If T² is greater than 0 there is a variation in true effect size.

Statistically significant: Some of the literature reported that findings were “significant” or “not significant”, without specifying at what level. Unless specified, it has been assumed that the significance level was $p < 0.05$.

Systematic review: The term systematic review appears as early as 1948 in a literature search (Holland, 1948). It means to review something in a methodological/systematic way. Best practice methodology for randomised controlled trials was defined in 2009 with the PRISMA statement (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) (Moher et al., 2009).

Tallow: Tallow is a rendered form of beef or mutton fat, processed from suet.

Chapter One – Introduction

Background

Until the final quarter of the twentieth century, public health dietary advice in the United States (US) and the United Kingdom (UK) focused on minimum intakes, to ensure that populations consumed adequate nutrients. The US 1950s-1970s “Basic Four Foundation Diet” recommended four or more bread and cereal portions daily, two cups or more of milk and two or more servings of meat (Davis and Saltos., 1999). The UK favoured micronutrient recommendations; until the first macronutrient guideline was introduced in 1950 with British Medical Association advice that dietary fat intake should provide a minimum of 25% of daily calories (Foster and Lunn, 2007) (British Medical Association, 1950).

The first public health dietary guidelines to set maximum intakes were those announced by the US Select Committee on Nutrition and Human needs in 1977 (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977). These were followed by UK public health dietary advice issued by the National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education in 1983 (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983). Dietary recommendations in both cases focused on one macronutrient, fat, and a component part of that macronutrient, saturated fat. The specific targets were to i) reduce overall fat consumption to 30% of total energy intake and ii) reduce saturated fat consumption to 10% of total energy intake.

The dietary recommendations were introduced with the intention of reducing deaths from coronary heart disease (CHD) by reducing fat intake. In 1950, the death rate from all causes for the US was 1.45% (National Center for Health Statistics, 2011). Of these 1,446 deaths per 100,000 people, 589 (41%) were recorded as deaths from heart disease. The death rate from heart disease in America in 1950 was thus 0.59%, approximately 6 people in 1,000. The death rate from heart disease could also be viewed as: of the people who died, heart disease accounted for 41% of the deaths.

In 1970, the overall death rate had fallen to 1.22%, while heart deaths continued to account for 40% of these deaths (National Center for Health Statistics, 2011). The four in ten statistic provided the context for the impetus for change that preceded the 1977 *Dietary Goals for the United States* announced by Senator George S. McGovern, chair of the Senate Nutrition Committee (Carter J.P., 1977).

The four in ten death rate was quoted in the opening volume of The Seven Countries Study, with reference to data for American men "The urgency of finding means of prevention is sharpest for men in middle age for it is in that group that the social cost of CHD is greatest... Starting with men aged 40 through 59, the follow-up would show CHD causing close to 40% of all deaths in five years. It is understandable, then, that most work on the epidemiology of CHD begins with men of those ages" (p.I-1) (Keys, 1970a).

Evidence available and considered

Both the US and UK documents acknowledged that the evidence was not conclusive. Hegsted's introduction to the Dietary Goals for The United States noted "there will undoubtedly be many people who will say we have not proven our point" (p.3) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977). The UK publication referred to "a strong consensus of opinion" (p.24) (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983).

The evidence available to dietary committees at that time comprised epidemiological studies and randomised controlled trials (RCTs). There has been no review of this evidence to ascertain if the dietary fat guidelines introduced were supported by the then available data.

While the UK nutritional guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) made reference to epidemiological studies, the US committee document (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) did not. The UK guidelines referenced The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1980). The UK document also referenced studies in Framingham, Hawaii/Honolulu, London and Puerto Rico (Gordon et al., 1981; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Yano et al., 1978). An additional epidemiological study was not referenced (Paul et al., 1963). Keys acknowledged that epidemiological studies could reveal relationships, not causation (Keys, 1970a). "Randomised controlled trials that are well conducted remain the gold standard for evidence of efficacy" (p.2) (Barton, 2000).

The first RCT to test the administration of dietary fat, as an intervention, was published in 1965 (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Four more studies were undertaken prior to the US dietary review in 1977 (Dayton et al., 1969; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965). One additional study was available to the UK dietary review of 1983 (Woodhill et al., 1978).

Neither the US committee document (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977), nor the UK nutritional guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) made reference to any of the RCTs available at that time. However, the US Committee publication reported data from the non-randomised, cross-over trial, The Finnish Mental Hospital Study (Miettinen et al., 1983; Turpeinen et al., 1979).

Systematic reviews

Truswell undertook the first review of dietary fat intervention studies and their effect on coronary events and total mortality (Truswell, 1994). Truswell included multi-factorial trials, with smoking cessation, weight loss and medication interventions, and thus the dietary impact could not be isolated.

At the start of this century, Hooper *et al* conducted a systematic review of dietary fat trials with cardiovascular disease endpoints available, including strokes as well as coronary heart disease (Hooper et al., 2001). They included the six RCTs listed above and four more (Black et al., 1994; Burr et al., 1989; Frantz et al., 1989; Watts et al., 1992). The Black article documented the effect of a low-fat diet on the incidence of actinic keratosis and made no reference to heart disease. Meta-analysis of these ten RCTs found a pooled risk ratio of 0.98 (95% CI 0.86 to 1.12) for all-cause mortality and 0.91 (95% CI 0.77 to 1.07) for cardiovascular mortality; neither result statistically significant. Subsequent updates for the Cochrane Collaboration (Hooper et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2011) have reiterated that there were no significant findings for dietary fat intake and mortality from all-causes; cardiovascular disease or CHD. The 2011 Cochrane review suggested that “a small, but potentially important reduction in cardiovascular risk” was associated with “modification of dietary fat, but not reduction of total fat, in longer trials” (p.2) (Hooper et al., 2011). Similar language was used in the conclusion of the most recent review: the findings suggest “a small but potentially important reduction in cardiovascular risk on reduction of saturated fat intake” (p.2) (Hooper et al., 2015).

Mozaffarian *et al* examined the RCTs that increased polyunsaturated fat (PUFA) in place of saturated fat (SFA) (Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010). They concluded that “a shift toward greater population PUFA consumption in place of SFA would significantly reduce rates of CHD” (p.1). The authors were criticised (Ravnskov et al., 2014) for having excluded The Rose Corn Oil Trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965), and The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978), which observed

greater mortality from CHD and all-causes in the intervention groups. This meta-analysis was also the only one to include The Finnish Mental Hospital Study (Miettinen et al., 1983; Turpeinen et al., 1979). This cross-over trial has been excluded in all other systematic reviews for not being randomised or controlled and because a cross-over trial design is inappropriate for the study of a long term condition.

More than thirty years after the dietary fat guidelines were introduced; there has been no examination of the epidemiological and RCT evidence base for these recommendations. Furthermore, these guidelines have not been changed since they were announced; correspondingly, the validity of their evidence base remains relevant.

This thesis undertakes a systematic review and meta-analysis of the epidemiological and randomised control trial (RCT) evidence available to the US dietary committee in 1977 (Select committee on nutrition and human needs, 1977) and the UK committee in 1983 (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983), to evaluate the evidence base for the introduction of the two specific dietary fat guidelines. The epidemiological and RCT evidence currently available is subsequently reviewed to assess if dietary fat recommendations, which remain unchanged, have been supported in retrospect.

In ideal research circumstances, epidemiological studies would precede randomised controlled trials (RCTs). Epidemiological studies are able to establish associations, which can then be tested with well designed intervention trials. This did not happen with the development of the diet-heart hypothesis.

Regarding epidemiological studies, The Framingham Study started in 1948, although a diet history was not introduced until Exam 4 (p.131) (Gordon and Kannel, 1970). Exam 4 covered the period 1954 to 1958 (National Heart Institute, 1968). The Seven Countries Study started in 1956, but was not published until 1970 (Keys, 1970a). The first epidemiological study published was The Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963).

Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) ran in parallel with epidemiological studies. Recruitment started for The Oslo Diet Heart Study in 1956 (Leren, 1968; Leren, 1970). The Research Committee Low-fat Diet started in 1957 (Research Committee, 1965). By the time The Seven Countries Study was published, all of the RCTs that would be available to the 1977 US dietary committee were published (Dayton et al., 1969; Leren, 1968; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Only The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978) was

published after 1970, but before the deliberations of the UK dietary committee (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983).

If epidemiological trials had logically preceded randomised controlled trials, with the development of the diet-heart hypothesis, the evidence would have been examined in chronological order. Given that the cohort and intervention studies were running alongside, the evaluation of the evidence available to the US and UK dietary committees starts with the best evidence available to them at the time. The technique of meta-analysis was not defined until 1976, making this technique unlikely to have been known to the dietary guideline committees (Glass, 1976). However, an examination of the RCTs available at the time, without meta-analysis, would have provided the best evidence available.

RCT evidence currently available is examined to assess if this supports or contradicts the RCT evidence of the time. Epidemiology is then considered to examine whether prospective cohort studies, the best epidemiological evidence available, support or contradict the findings of RCTs, both at the time of the committee meetings and to the present day.

The epidemiological and RCTs are systematically reviewed in Chapters Three, Four, Five and Six and thus are not covered in detail in the review of the literature.

Research aims

The aims of this thesis are:

- 1) To provide a narrative review of the emergence of the diet-heart hypothesis – the tripartite association of cholesterol (dietary and serum), dietary fat (total and saturated) and the development of coronary heart disease – in order to contextualise the rationale for the introduction of dietary fat recommendations in 1977 (US) and 1983 (UK).
- 2) To undertake a systematic review and meta-analysis of the body of randomised controlled trial (RCT) evidence available to the US and UK committees at the time of the announcement of recommendations for dietary fat intake.
- 3) To undertake a systematic review and meta-analysis of the body of RCT evidence currently available relating to the introduction of recommendations for dietary fat intake in the US and UK.

- 4) To systematically review the epidemiological evidence available to the US and UK committees at the time of introducing recommendations for dietary fat intake (the data for meta-analysis are not available).
- 5) To undertake a systematic review and meta-analysis of the epidemiological evidence currently available relating to the introduction of recommendations for dietary fat intake in the US and UK.
- 6) To evaluate and discuss all RCT and epidemiological evidence examined to reach conclusions and review implications for dietary guidelines.

Research hypotheses

The following null hypotheses are tested:

The RCT evidence available to the national committees did not support the introduction of dietary fat guidelines in 1977 and 1983 with respect to:

- i) All-cause mortality;
- ii) CHD mortality;
- iii) Serum cholesterol levels.

The RCT evidence currently available does not support the introduction of dietary fat guidelines in 1977 and 1983 with respect to:

- i) All-cause mortality;
- ii) CHD mortality;
- iii) Serum cholesterol levels.

The epidemiological evidence available to the national committees did not support the introduction of dietary fat guidelines in 1977 and 1983 with respect to:

- i) CHD mortality;
- ii) Serum cholesterol levels.

The epidemiological evidence currently available does not support the introduction of dietary fat guidelines in 1977 and 1983 with respect to:

- i) CHD mortality;
- ii) Serum cholesterol levels.

RCTs are suited to the examination of all-cause mortality and CHD mortality. It is important to know if an intervention reduces deaths from one cause, but increases

deaths from another cause. Observational studies are suited to the examination of one end point, such as CHD mortality.

Research methods and thesis structure

In addition to the introduction, this thesis contains six further chapters, which are outlined below:

Chapter Two: Narrative review of the literature to contextualise the rationale for the introduction of dietary fat recommendations in 1977 (US) and 1983 (UK)

The review of the literature will establish when and why researchers first hypothesised about the relationships between dietary cholesterol, serum cholesterol, dietary fat and coronary heart disease. It will document the development of thinking about dietary and serum cholesterol, dietary fat and coronary heart disease, from the Russian animal experiments with dietary cholesterol in the 1900s, through the shift of focus from total fat to saturated fat in the 1950s, to the first statement of the diet-heart hypothesis based on total fat (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955). This provided the context for the start of The Seven Countries Study in 1956, which revised the diet-heart hypothesis to associate serum cholesterol, CHD and saturated, not total, fat.

Chapter Three: A systematic review and meta-analysis of the randomised controlled trial evidence available at the time of the introduction of dietary fat recommendations

In this chapter, the null hypothesis that the RCT evidence available to the US and UK committees, at the time of issuing recommendations did not support the advice that reducing dietary fat intake to 30% of total calories and saturated fat intake to 10% of total calories would contribute to a reduction in CHD mortality with no adverse impact on all-cause mortality, will be tested.

This chapter will report on two systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the randomised control trial evidence available at the time of the change in public health dietary fat guidelines. One will review the relationship between dietary fat interventions and all-cause mortality; the other will review the relationship between dietary fat interventions and CHD mortality.

Chapter Four: A systematic review and meta-analysis of the randomised controlled trial evidence currently available to evaluate if the introduced dietary fat guidelines have been supported in retrospect

In this chapter, the null hypothesis that RCT evidence currently available does not support the advice that reducing dietary fat intake to 30% of total calories and saturated fat intake to 10% of total calories would contribute to a reduction in CHD mortality with no adverse impact on all-cause mortality, will be tested.

The introduction of statin medications in 1987 largely ended the possibility of conducting controlled dietary interventions in any trials involving secondary participants (Endo, 2004). It became standard practice to administer cholesterol-lowering medications to patients who had suffered a myocardial infarction and thus the impact of dietary intervention could no longer be studied in isolation. The first dietary fat trial undertaken to measure the effect of dietary fat alongside medication interventions was published in 1992 (Watts et al., 1992). This study reviewed the diet and drug interventions separately enabling its inclusion in systematic review.

One dietary fat study from the past decade can be included (Howard et al., 2006). Although this involved participants taking medications, the interventions were dietary, not pharmacological and the subjects taking drugs were randomly and evenly distributed between intervention and control groups allowing the impact of the dietary intervention alone to be evaluated.

This chapter will report on two systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the randomised control trial evidence available up to, and beyond, the time of the change in public health dietary fat guidelines. One will review the relationship between dietary fat interventions and all-cause mortality; the other will review the relationship between dietary fat interventions and CHD mortality. The purpose of these reviews will be to establish if dietary fat recommendations have been supported in retrospect.

Chapter Five: A systematic review of the epidemiological evidence available at the time of the introduction of dietary fat recommendations

In this chapter, the null hypothesis that the epidemiological evidence available to the US and UK committees did not endorse their recommendations to reduce dietary fat intake to 30% of total calories and saturated fat intake to 10% of total calories, with the intention of reducing CHD mortality, will be tested.

Chapter Six: A systematic review and meta-analysis of the epidemiological evidence currently available to evaluate if the introduced dietary fat guidelines have been supported in retrospect

In this chapter, the null hypothesis that epidemiological evidence currently available does not support the advice that reducing dietary fat intake to 30% of total calories and saturated fat intake to 10% of total calories would contribute to a reduction in CHD mortality, will be tested.

This chapter will report on two systematic reviews and meta-analyses of the epidemiological evidence available up to, and beyond, the time of the change in public health dietary fat guidelines. One will review the relationship between total dietary fat intake and CHD mortality; the other will review the relationship between saturated dietary fat intake and CHD mortality. The purpose of these reviews will be to establish if dietary fat recommendations have been supported in retrospect.

Chapter Seven: Discussion

This chapter will integrate and interpret the research findings from the systematic reviews of randomised control trials and epidemiological evidence. It will realise the aims and develop the findings.

Chapter Two

Narrative review of the literature to contextualise the rationale for the introduction of dietary fat recommendations in 1977 (US) and 1983 (UK)

The diet-heart hypothesis

The review of the literature examines the origin of the hypothesis of relationships between dietary cholesterol, dietary fat (total), dietary fat (saturated), serum cholesterol and coronary heart disease (CHD). The review starts with the first use of the term arteriosclerosis (Gull and Sutton, 1872) and ends with the first statement of the diet-heart hypothesis, which related to total fat: "The results of this survey support the hypothesis that the dietary intake of fat influences the level of the serum cholesterol, and in turn may be one of the major factors influencing the pathogenesis of coronary heart-disease" (p.1107) (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955).

The focus on total fat provided the context for The Seven Countries Study, which started in 1956 (Keys, 1970a). The expression of the diet-heart hypothesis, as presented in The Seven Countries Study, referred to saturated, not total, dietary fat (Keys, 1970e). The verbatim findings of The Seven Countries Study were:

- "The incidence rate of CHD tends to be directly related to the distributions of serum cholesterol values."
- "The average serum cholesterol values of the cohorts tended to be directly related to the average proportion of calories provided by saturated fats in the diet."
- "The CHD incidence rates of the cohorts are just as closely related to the dietary saturated fatty acids as to the serum cholesterol level"(p.I-194) (Keys, 1970e).

The diet-heart hypothesis became the tripartite association of saturated fat, serum cholesterol levels and CHD, although the impact of dietary cholesterol and total dietary fat were also investigated.

The review of the literature examines:

- The origin of the hypothesis of cholesterol (dietary and/or serum) as a risk factor for CHD;
- The exploration of serum cholesterol as a factor in CHD;
- The examination of dietary cholesterol as a factor in serum cholesterol;
- The exploration of dietary fat as a factor in serum cholesterol;

- The exploration of dietary fat as a factor in CHD;
- The examination of associations between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD.

References are made in earlier literature to dietary fat generally. As research progressed, animal and vegetable fats became the more common terminology. Saturated and unsaturated fats were a later distinction and often used interchangeably with animal and vegetable fats, which is incorrect. All foods that contain fat, whether of animal or vegetable origin, contain saturated and unsaturated fat (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013). The transition from dietary fat to saturated fat, as the nutrient of concern, is documented.

Although not core to the diet-heart hypothesis, the origin of the hypothesis that unsaturated fat could be a potential protector is noted.

The origin of the hypothesis of cholesterol (dietary and/or serum) as a risk factor for CHD

Arteriosclerosis was first described in 1872 by Sir William Gull and Dr. Sutton (Gull and Sutton, 1872). Their paper, presented to the Medical and Chirurgical Society of London, used the term arterio-capillary fibrosis to describe the condition they had observed. This became known as arteriosclerosis, combining the Greek terms *arteria*, meaning arteries and *sclerosis*, meaning hardening.

The earliest documentation of what is now called CHD was credited to Sir William Osler. In the later editions of his *The Principles and Practice of Medicine*, Osler detailed the physiology of angina and heart attacks and described angina as "a disease of adult life occurring almost exclusively in men" (p.761) (Osler, 1904). Osler credited Gull and Sutton for the conception of the term arterio-sclerosis and defined it as a condition of thickening, diffuse or circumscribed, beginning in the intima. They noted that the process led in the larger arteries to what was known as atheroma (p.770). Later that year, at a conference in Leipzig, Felix Marchand first proposed the term atherosclerosis (Marchand, 1904).

The hypothesis that cholesterol could be a factor in heart disease was first explored in Russia. In the early 1900s, experiments were undertaken at the Pathology Institute of the Royal Military Medical Academy in St Petersburg. In 1908, Dr. Ignatowski observed a relationship between animal foods and experimental atherosclerosis, following the feeding of meat, milk and eggs to rabbits (Ignatowski, 1908a; Ignatowski, 1908b; Ignatowski, 1909). The rabbits, which are herbivores, developed nodular lesions

of the aorta. Ignatowski thought that toxins resulting from the digestion of meat could be atherogenic.

Stuckey fed rabbits the following diets: a) milk and egg white; b) milk and meat juice; c) milk and egg yolk; d) milk, whole egg and meat juice; and e) oats and hay for the control group (Stuckey, 1910; Stuckey, 1911). One rabbit in each group was killed and analysed at two, four and six months. Minor fatty deposits were found in subjects from groups a and b. Rabbits from groups c and d showed signs of fatty deposits and thickening of the intima. Stuckey concluded that egg yolk was the atherogenic agent.

Stuckey followed this experiment by testing four further substances, again delivered in milk to rabbits (Stuckey, 1912). The food stuffs were: tallow (beef or mutton fat processed from suet); cod liver oil; sunflower oil; and ox brain. The experiment was described as a test of four different fats, but ox brain is 10% fat, 76% water, 11% protein and 3% cholesterol (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013a). The other three substances are 100% fat. After four months, fatty deposits were observed in the ox brain group, but not in the other three groups. Stuckey noted that the lesions exhibited by rabbits fed ox brain were similar to those fed egg yolk. Stuckey concluded that a substance common to egg yolk and ox brain was the atherogenic agent.

Chalatow observed that the substances found in the livers of rabbits fed egg yolk or ox brain comprised cholesterol, lecithin (phospholipids) and fatty acids (Chalatow, 1912). Had Chalataw noted protein as well, he would have documented, as early as 1912, the four main substances carried by lipoproteins (Mangiapane and Salter, 1999).

Wesselkin tested cholesterol and lecithin by feeding rabbits four different diets for six months (Wesselkin, 1913). The diets were all delivered in milk: a) egg yolk and egg white; b) egg white and lecithin; c) egg yolk; and d) lecithin. The rabbits fed egg yolk (groups a and c) were the only ones to exhibit fatty changes in their aortas and livers. Wesselkin concluded that cholesterol, not lecithin, was the atherogenic agent.

Working initially with Chalataw and building on the work of Wesselkin, Nikolai Anitschkow hypothesised that the substance that produced lesions in rabbit aortas might be cholesterol. Anitschkow fed purified cholesterol to rabbits for between 10 and 139 days. The total cumulative dose of cholesterol administered varied between 3 and 82 grams (g), according to the duration of the experiment. Changes were observed in the aorta of the rabbits and the changes were more marked with increased duration of feeding – a dose response (Anitschkow, 1913). Anitschkow fed rats egg yolk in milk for up to five months producing no observed changes in the aortas (Anitschkow, 1933).

Further experiments on rabbits were undertaken by Kon (Kon, 1913; Kon, 1914) who produced lesions in rabbits fed beef liver powder, but not in those fed defatted liver powder and Steinbiss (Steinbiss, 1913) who fed rabbits dried horse liver, adrenal, thymus or muscle. The rabbits fed thymus died within a fortnight. Those fed adrenal died within a month. The horse liver group survived for up to four months.

One of these rabbit experiments questioned the validity of feeding animal products to herbivores; rabbits being unable to metabolise animal products (Knack, 1915). Knack tested whether cholesterol *per se* was a causal factor in the findings of his peers. Knack fed one group of rabbits a herbivorous diet supplemented with up to 4.5 g of cholesterol daily and a second group were fed egg, milk and vegetables, which provided 0.3 g of cholesterol per day. After 195 days on the herbivorous diet with added cholesterol, 8 out of 12 rabbits showed no arterial damage. All the rabbits on the egg and milk diet had pronounced atherosclerosis. Knack concluded that arterial damage preceded atherosclerosis and that the abnormal diet had caused the initial damage.

The first human pathology analyses are credited to Windaus, working with the pathologist Aschoff (Windaus, 1910). Windaus found that atheromatous aortas contained 6 times more free cholesterol than healthy arteries and over 20 times more cholesterol ester. Schoenheimer confirmed Windaus's findings in 1926 by observing that the total cholesterol content of the aorta increased with the prevalence of atheroma (Schoenheimer, 1926).

Anitschkow continued to experiment on animals for over two decades. He fed rats egg yolk in milk for up to five months producing no observable changes in the aortas (Anitschkow, 1933). Rats, unlike rabbits, are omnivores.

A Boston pathologist, Timothy Leary, repeated Anitschkow's experiments with rabbits and chickens. Leary was credited as being the first to describe atherosclerosis as a metabolic disease: "Atherosclerosis is a disease due to disturbances in the cholesterol metabolism and belongs with the other metabolic diseases, diabetes (carbohydrates), gout (purines), and obesity (fats)" (p.328) (Leary, 1935b). Leary's article later that year was entitled "Atherosclerosis, the important form of arteriosclerosis, a metabolic disease" (Leary, 1935a).

Experiments on rabbits continued beyond the publication of The Seven Countries Study (Carroll and Hamilton, 1975).

The origin of unsaturated fat as a potential protector

With much of the exploratory work on cholesterol and heart disease having been undertaken by Russians and Germans, the developing tensions throughout the 1930s and the onset of World War II in September 1939 halted progress at an important time.

The notable exception was the work of C. D. de Langen and his colleague Isadore Snapper. Snapper confirmed that the revolutionary ideas of Russian researchers had been neglected until the early 1950s (p.283) (Snapper, 1963). In 1934, at the second conference of the International Society of Geographical Pathology, de Langen reported a correlation between lipid content of the diet and incidence of atherosclerosis (de Langen, 1934). De Langen had witnessed one case of angina pectoris among Javanese patients, six cases among Chinese patients and “considerable evidence of coronary disease among his private Javanese and Chinese patients who followed a European diet rich in fat” (p.284) (Snapper, 1963).

In 1936, de Langen noted that the food intake of people visiting hospitals and clinics in Java contained little cholesterol and little cholesterol was found in the blood. He observed that blood cholesterol levels rose when people, in hospital or elsewhere, were given a diet rich in fat (De Langen and Lichtenstein, 1936) (as documented on p.284 (Snapper, 1963)).

Snapper reported that the exceptions to this rule were “uncomfortably frequent.” Large groups of Occidentals with coronary sclerosis had normal or even slightly low serum cholesterol levels. Moreover, a significant number of Occidentals with hypercholesterolemia lived to old age without any signs of heart disease (p.284) (Snapper, 1963).

This led Snapper to conclude that the rarity of atherosclerosis in the Orient could not be attributed solely to the restriction of dietary cholesterol and it led him to hypothesise that unsaturated fat could have a protective effect in heart disease (Snapper, 1941).

The exploration of serum cholesterol as a factor in CHD

World War II saw the emergence of Ancel Keys as a notable scientific researcher. Keys observed the introduction and extension of food rationing across Europe and was concerned that rationing could become starvation. His first major study was inspired by this observation and the realisation that there was no long term review of the impact of food deprivation on humans (Keys et al., 1950a). The Minnesota Starvation Experiment, started in 1944, was a definitive study of hunger and re-feeding.

After the publication of this study, Keys turned his attention to heart disease, which was emerging as the primary health concern for Americans. The opening page of The Seven Countries Study noted that it was urgent to find a means for preventing CHD, particularly in men aged 40 through 59, where CHD caused approximately 40% of all deaths in a five year follow-up period (p.I-1) (Keys, 1970a).

There were a number of important studies post World War II, which influenced Keys' work on CHD in the 1950s. In 1948, Morrison *et al* examined 200 cases of acute coronary thrombosis admitted to the wards of the Los Angeles County General Hospital and compared these with 66 control subjects. In 68% of 75 patients under 60 years of age, with proven acute coronary occlusion, hypercholesterolemia was present. In 52% of 125 patients over 60 years of age, with proven acute coronary occlusion, a normal cholesterol level was found (p.38) (Morrison, Hall and Chaney, 1948). Keys referred to this paper in his 1953 work (Keys, 1953b).

Keys confirmed a relationship between age and serum cholesterol levels with a study of 1,492 men aged 17-78 and 564 women aged 17-30. He found little variation in cholesterol levels in the 17-30 age group for men or women. For the age range 17-78 years in men, Keys found a pronounced curvilinear relationship between age and serum cholesterol concentration with a maximum in the sixth decade (p.1353) (Keys et al., 1950b).

The first mention of lipoproteins in relation to heart disease occurred in February 1950 with the work of John Gofman. Gofman *et al* used new ultra-centrifuge technology to examine if a particular carrier of cholesterol could be more particularly associated with CHD (Gofman and Lindgren, 1950). In a review of 104 patients with an established myocardial infarction, they found that 100 had low density lipoproteins of the Sf10-20 class (a measure of flotation), while only half the controls exhibited the same. This work was developed further in a paper in August of the same year. In this, Gofman *et al* concluded that a class of lipid and lipoprotein molecules had been found in the serum of man and the cholesterol fed rabbit, associated with atherosclerosis in both species. Gofman *et al* further found that the identified lipids were present with a higher frequency and at higher concentrations in patients who had survived a myocardial infarction than in people without known vascular disease (p.177) (Gofman et al., 1950). This later paper was referenced several times by Keys (Keys, 1952b; Keys, 1953a; Keys, 1953b).

In August 1950, Gertler *et al* published their study of 97 males with coronary disease against a control group of 146 males and a matched control group of 97 males (Gertler, Garn and Lerman, 1950). They found that mean serum cholesterol levels were 286 mg/dl for the 97 men with coronary disease, 224 mg/dl for the broad control group and 247 mg/dl for the matched control group.

Steiner *et al* compared the serum lipid pattern of 82 patients with coronary arteriosclerosis with that of 112 healthy adults (Steiner, Kendall and Mathers, 1952). The serum cholesterol values of the normal subjects varied from 118 to 297 mg/dl with a mean of 198 mg/dl. The serum cholesterol of the patients with coronary arteriosclerosis varied from 174 to 371 mg/dl with a mean of 263 mg/dl (p.606) (Steiner, Kendall and Mathers, 1952). The results were reported as statistically significant, but no *p* value was given.

The following year, 1953, a larger study was published where 149 male admissions with coronary artery disease were compared with 149 male control subjects (Oliver and Boyd, 1953). Mean cholesterol levels were categorised into age decades (30-39; 40-49; 50-59; 60-69; 70+) and fell progressively with rising decades in the coronary artery disease subjects: 278; 243; 224; 223 and 214 mg/dl respectively. The variation was much lower in the control subjects and did not progress uniformly with age. The mean cholesterol levels were 174, 180, 168, 166 and 171 mg/dl for men in their 30s, 40s, 50s, 60s and 70 or older respectively (table I, p.389) (Oliver and Boyd, 1953). Although mean serum cholesterol levels decreased through the age groups with the diseased subjects, they remained higher in every age group than for the healthy subjects.

Keys' 1956 publication on "Diet and the development of coronary heart disease" reported two findings from studies available at that time: (1) Populations with relatively high serum cholesterol averages – 220 mg/dl or more for middle-aged men – exhibit a relatively high incidence of CHD and (2) Populations with low serum cholesterol averages – less than 200 mg/dl for middle-aged men – exhibit relatively little CHD (p.365) (Keys, 1956). References for (1) were given as men in many parts of the United States (Keys, 1952b), in London (Keys and Keys, 1954), in upper-class men in Madrid (Keys et al., 1954b), Europeans in Cape Town, South Africa (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955), among others. References for (2) were given as southern Italy (Keys et al., 1954a), poor men in Madrid (Keys et al., 1954b), Bantu in Johannesburg and Cape Town (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955; Higginson and Pepler, 1954; Walker and Arvidsson, 1954), among others.

The examination of dietary cholesterol as a factor in serum cholesterol

Using the same 97 males with coronary disease and the same control group of 146 males, Gertler and Garn worked with Paul White to publish another finding from their research: "there is virtually no correlation between ingested cholesterol and the level of cholesterol in the serum" (p.696) (Gertler, Garn and White, 1950). Keys referred to both of these papers several times in his subsequent works (Keys, 1952a; Keys, 1952b; Keys, 1953a; Keys, 1953b; Keys et al., 1956).

Keys conducted a number of studies in the 1950s to test the hypothesis that cholesterol in food raised blood cholesterol levels. Keys' earliest documented work on this topic was in July 1950 (Keys et al., 1950c). He studied 393 healthy men who had markedly different dietary cholesterol intakes. Grouping the men into the age ranges 18 to 25 and 45 to 54, he found no difference between the mean serum cholesterol levels of men with the highest intake of dietary cholesterol vs. men with the lowest intake of dietary cholesterol. This was consistent across both age groups.

In 1952, Keys reported that he had studied more than 400 men for five consecutive years, with an age range of 18 to 60 years, and ranges of cholesterol intakes from approximately 1 to 8 g per week and that all the data was consistently negative (Federation Proceedings 8 (1949), 523). "In every one of the series of surveys the result has been the same – absolutely no indication of an effect of the dietary cholesterol on the blood level" (p.545) (Keys, 1952a).

Throughout his publications, Keys continued to reject the hypothesis that dietary cholesterol had an impact on the serum cholesterol level (Keys, 1952b; Keys, 1956; Keys and Anderson, 1954).

In an article in *The Journal of Nutrition*, Keys summarised the conclusions of the numerous studies that he had undertaken, without individual references to each study (p.53-54) (Keys et al., 1956):

- Two cross sectional surveys in Minnesota on young men and four on older men showed no relationship between dietary cholesterol and serum cholesterol levels.
- Two surveys in Sardinia failed to show any difference in the serum cholesterol levels of men, of the same age, physical activity, relative body weight and general dietary pattern, but with markedly different cholesterol intake.

- Study of 33 men for 4 years, whose diets were consistently very low in cholesterol, showed that their serum values did not differ from 35 men of the same age and economic status whose diets were very high in cholesterol.
- Comparisons made of 23 men before and after they had voluntarily doubled their cholesterol intakes and of 41 men who halved theirs failed to show any difference in the serum cholesterol level after 4 to 12 months, while the rest of the diet was mostly constant.
- A study of the dietary intakes of 119 Minnesota businessmen failed to show any significant increase in serum cholesterol levels with increasing dietary cholesterol intake.
- In a controlled experiment on 5 healthy men, the change from a rice-fruit diet containing 500 mg of cholesterol daily to the same diet devoid of cholesterol had no effect on the serum cholesterol level.
- In a similar experiment with 13 men receiving 66 g of fat daily there was no significant effect in changing from a cholesterol intake of 374 mg/day to one of 1,369 mg/day. In another 12 men the reverse change also had no effect on the blood serum cholesterol level.

Keys undertook several trials to investigate if dietary cholesterol raised blood cholesterol levels and concluded that it did not. "It is concluded that in adult men the serum cholesterol level is essentially independent of the cholesterol intake over the whole range of natural human diets. It is probable that infants, children and women are similar" (p.54) (Keys et al., 1956).

The most definitive statement made by Keys on this subject was recorded in a 1954 Symposium on Atherosclerosis: "The evidence – both from experiments and from field surveys – indicates that cholesterol content, *per se*, of all natural diets has *no* significant effect on either the cholesterol level or the development of atherosclerosis in man" (p.182 – original emphasis) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

The diet-heart hypothesis originally surmised that dietary cholesterol raised cholesterol levels and that this in turn caused heart disease. This is why Keys' early studies in the 1950s focused on trying to establish a relationship between cholesterol intake and cholesterol levels. When none could be found, Keys hypothesised that dietary fat could be associated with cholesterol levels.

This premise had a logical flaw. The only foods that contain cholesterol are animal foods: meat; fish; eggs and dairy products. Keys was aware of this: "Cholesterol occurs only in foods of animal origin" (p.79) (Keys et al., 1950c). This was reinforced in the 1952 publication, *The Cholesterol Problem*: "cholesterol is not contained in plants or plant products but it is present in all animal tissues" (p.542) (Keys, 1952a).

All foods that contain cholesterol contain dietary fat. They all contain all three types of dietary fat: saturated; monounsaturated and polyunsaturated. Only the proportions of each fat vary (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013). To increase the dietary cholesterol in his human subjects, Keys needed to feed them foods of animal origin. This had no impact on blood cholesterol levels, or the development of atherosclerosis in man (Keys and Anderson, 1954). Animal foods, *per se*, had been simultaneously exonerated.

The macronutrient that is largely absent from the foods that contain cholesterol is carbohydrate. Meat and fish have no carbohydrate content (with liver, offal, being an exception for any glycogen stored by the animal at the time of death). Eggs have a trace of carbohydrate. Dairy products approximate to five per cent carbohydrate content. Animal foods are either entirely, or in the main, water, protein and fat (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013).

The logical macronutrient for Keys to have studied was therefore carbohydrate, but attention was turned to fat.

The exploration of dietary fat as a factor in serum cholesterol

In parallel with his work on cholesterol in food and cholesterol in the blood, Keys investigated the relationship of diet more widely and its possible relationship to cholesterol in the blood.

An addendum to the 1950 Keys paper on "The relation in man between cholesterol levels in the diet and in the blood" appeared to be the earliest mention of dietary fat and serum cholesterol levels (Keys et al., 1950c). The addendum noted an experiment with one patient, A.H. When A.H. was changed from a diet completely free of both cholesterol and all fats to one containing vegetable fats (corn oil), but with no cholesterol or animal fats, his blood cholesterol level "returned to his previous high level almost as rapidly as it had fallen" (p.80). This passage contained the only reference to type of dietary fat, animal or vegetable; the terms saturated or unsaturated fat were not used. Keys noted that his findings were similar to animal studies performed by Abelin where vegetable oils in the diet increased cholesterol levels (p.81) (Abelin,

1948). These early findings contradicted later views that vegetable oils reduced cholesterol concentration.

In the short paper, "Human Atherosclerosis and the Diet", published at the start of 1952, Keys summarised that discussions about the possible effect of the diet on the development of atherosclerosis centred on five areas: i) calorie excess and obesity; ii) cholesterol in the diet; iii) animal fats in the diet; iv) total fats in the diet; and v) substances that may have a lipotropic effect such as lethicin, choline or inositol (Keys, 1952b). This paper contained four references to vegetable fat, one to animal fat and none to saturated or unsaturated fat.

Keys noted that atherosclerosis occurred in many people who were not overweight and thus rejected (i) as a controlling factor. Keys continued to reject (ii) as a factor and reiterated that the serum cholesterol in man was independent of intake of cholesterol. (v) was rejected for being a pharmacologic, rather than a dietary, matter, leaving animal fat and total fat in the diet as the two nutrients of focus. Carbohydrate was not investigated as a possible factor.

The article noted a number of experiments where dietary fat content was changed and serum cholesterol levels measured. All of the experimental diets were comparable in calories and proteins; the differences in fat intake were achieved by changing the amount of vegetable fat in the diet. No mention was made of any experiment involving animal fat and yet Keys concluded: "other things being equal, the serum cholesterol level in adult man is independent of the cholesterol intake... but the fat intake is quite another matter. However, there is not the slightest evidence for a difference between animal and vegetable fat in this regard" (p.116-117) (Keys, 1952b).

This presented two errors: 1) deductions about animal fat were made from observing vegetable fat and 2) vegetable fat could have been consumed as an isolated macronutrient, animal fat could not. The main vegetable fats of the time were corn oil and olive oil. All oils are 100% fat. Animal foods comprise meat, fish, eggs and dairy products. Animal foods are approximately 70% water and the remainder is a combination of protein and fat (with some carbohydrate, lactose, in dairy products). A study of animal foods is a study of all three macronutrients and all three fats. It is also a study of micronutrients, as these are substantially greater in animal foods than any oils (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013).

No mention was made of the different types of fat in these early Keys' papers: saturated; monounsaturated and polyunsaturated. The focus at this stage was on animal and

vegetable fats. The primary fat in the majority of animal foods (meat, fish, eggs, lard) is monounsaturated fat – the same as in olive oil (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013c) and corn oil (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013b).

A more comprehensive connection to total dietary fat was made in a 1952 publication, *The Cholesterol Problem* (Keys, 1952a). This publication was important for a number of reasons:

- First, it reinforced the conclusion from the blood cholesterol studies that Keys had undertaken: "In every one of the series of surveys the result has been the same – absolutely no indication of an effect of dietary cholesterol on the blood level" (p.545) (Keys, 1952a).

- Second, it noted that making inferences for humans from experiments on rabbits was inappropriate. Keys calculated that a human would need to ingest 43,400 calories from milk, eggs, butter, meat and cheese (with no allowance for breads, sugar, potatoes, fruits or vegetables) to produce a diet comparable to those used to produce atherosclerosis in the rabbit (p.544) (Keys, 1952a).

- Third, in this publication Keys detailed a study that varied dietary fat for 21 male subjects. Total fat intake was reduced from 110 g to 11 g per day and serum cholesterol levels fell, regardless of the amount of cholesterol in the diet (p.546) (Keys, 1952a). Keys clarified that the fat used was entirely of vegetable origin, mainly corn oil, but again claimed that animal fats also had this effect.

The possible impact of plant sterols on serum cholesterol levels was not explored in this 1952 paper, but was included in a paper two years later: "The possible effects of orally ingested plant sterols on the absorption of cholesterol in the gut or on the cholesterol metabolism are of interest, but the only question for present consideration is whether plant sterols in natural diets may have significant effects" (p.184) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

- Fourth, Keys introduced the impact of total calorie intake as an influence on serum cholesterol levels. A 5 month experiment was undertaken on 20 men who were persuaded to overeat and gain weight. The subjects started the experiment at normal weight and with normal serum cholesterol levels. The control diet was changed by increasing carbohydrate-containing foods and reducing the proportion of calories from fats. The men gained an average of 10kg body weight in five months (p.548). The

weight gain was correlated with a rise in serum cholesterol, the coefficient of correlation between the two variables being 0.47 (p.548) (Keys, 1952a).

- Finally, despite evidence indicting calorie intake, weight, carbohydrate intake and vegetable oil intake, one of the key conclusions of the paper was: "The major dietary factor which affects the serum cholesterol level is the total fat, or the proportion of calories supplied by all fat metabolism" (p.554) (Keys, 1952a).

In 1954 the first regional observational studies were published. Keys studied 1,492 clinically healthy men in non-manual work in the metropolitan area of Minneapolis and St. Paul (Keys et al., 1950b) and 83 clinically healthy men in Naples (Keys et al., 1954a). The average diets in the two groups provided approximately 40% and 20% respectively of total calories in the diet from fat (Keys, 1953a; Keys et al., 1950b), which was noted by Keys as reflective of the American and Italian diets generally (p.328) (Keys et al., 1954a). Writing about the men of Naples, Keys noted that "the majority of them were as fat as comparable Americans" (p.329) (Keys et al., 1954a) and so he dismissed differential obesity as a factor. The Neapolitan diet was based on bread and pasta, with meat, fish, milk, cheese and eggs described as luxuries. Sugar and potatoes were eaten only in very small amounts (p.329) (Keys et al., 1954a).

The title of the Minnesota publication was "The concentration of cholesterol in the blood serum of normal man and its relation to age" (Keys et al., 1950b). Age was the primary subject of interest, as it was observed that, from the age of 18 to 40, the serum cholesterol values in the Italians and Minnesotans were very nearly the same, as was the trend between serum cholesterol and age (a mean rise of approximately 2 mg/dl of serum per year of age). This mean rise was not significant (Fraser and Fogarty, 1989). In the 1954 symposium on atherosclerosis (Keys and Anderson, 1954), Keys stated that, with increasing age, the serum cholesterol levels continued to rise progressively in the Minnesotans, but not the men of Naples. This was not the case. The highest mean cholesterol reading for any age for the Minnesotan men was 256 mg/dl at the age of 55 (Keys, 1953a). The mean serum cholesterol levels for Minnesotan men aged 60, 65, 70 and 75 were 253, 237, 225 and, 212 mg/dl respectively (Table 2.1).

Additionally, the mean serum cholesterol measurements for the Minnesotan men were available for every age group from 20 to 75 at five year intervals, while the measurements for the comparator regions – Naples (Keys et al., 1954a), Slough (Keys and Keys, 1954) and Madrid (Keys et al., 1954b) – were only available for the four ages of 20, 30, 40 and 50.

Keys reported that in the 50s age group, the mean cholesterol value of the Minnesotans was approximately 40 to 50 mg/dl higher than in the Italians (p.187) (Keys and Anderson, 1954). The mean serum cholesterol level for Minnesotan men at the age of 50 was 248 mg/dl (Keys, 1953a). There was no comparable figure for Naples men aged 55 – the data was not available beyond the age of 50. The mean serum cholesterol for Naples men aged 50 was 218 mg/dl – a 38 mg/dl differential with the reading for Minnesotan men aged 55 and a 30 mg/dl differential with the reading for Minnesotan men of the same age of 50, not 40-50 mg/dl higher.

This first observation of different populations by Keys reported that dietary fat, as a proportion of calorie intake, was twice as high in Minnesotan men as Napoleon men. Keys found that cholesterol levels were very similar in both populations for the ages 20, 30 and 40; only at the age of 50 did the mean cholesterol levels diverge and no comparisons were possible beyond this age.

Table 2.1 Mean serum cholesterol (mg/dl) (\pm SD where available) and percentage of calories from total fat: data extracted from (tables 10-13, p.130-132) (Keys, 1953a).

	Minnesota (n = 1,492)	Naples (n = 83)	Slough (n = 48)	Madrid poor (n = 55)	Madrid rich (n = 57)
Calories from fat:	40%	20%	35%	22%	“Similar to US”
Age: 20 years	173 \pm 31	176	178	166	193
25	184 \pm 34				
30	195 \pm 40	204	193	199	201
35	200 \pm 43				
40	219 \pm 39	219	228	209	230
45	236 \pm 37				
50	248 \pm 45	218	238	197	251
55	256 \pm 46				
60	253 \pm 34				
65	237 \pm 34				
70	225 \pm 42				
75	212 \pm 37				

Keys concluded "It is now clear that, independent of other factors, the total fat content of the diet, or the proportion of the total metabolism supported by fats, exerts a powerful influence on the serum cholesterol level in man" (p.334) (Keys et al., 1954a).

In the 1954 Symposium on Atherosclerosis, Keys reported that a similar comparison between the Minnesotan men and 55 lower-class Spaniards in Madrid resembled the Naples comparison but with even larger cholesterol differences with age: being of the order of 60 to 80 mg/dl higher in the Minnesotans in the fifties (p.187) (Keys and Anderson, 1954). The average calories from fat in the diet of the poor Madrid men were 22% (Keys et al., 1954b). Again, the highest age data available for Madrid men was for the age of 50. The mean serum cholesterol levels were 197 mg/dl for Spanish men aged 50 and 248 mg/dl for Minnesotan men aged 50: a difference of 51 mg/dl, not 60 to 80 mg/dl.

Data for 57 rich Spanish men were also available. The dietary fat intake was described as similar to that eaten by wealthy men in the United States (p.132) (Keys, 1953a). The mean serum cholesterol level for the rich Spaniards from Madrid was 251 mg/dl at the age of 50.

48 men aged 40-55 were studied in Slough, England (Keys and Keys, 1954). The diet of the men derived 35% of calories from fat. The mean serum cholesterol level of the Slough men at the age of 50 was 238 mg/dl. This was described by Keys as much more like the Minnesotan and wealthy Spaniards than the poor Spaniards or the Neapolitans in their cholesterol values (p.188) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

The South African Bantu were studied by researchers, as the Bantu diet typically contained less than half the fat intake of Minnesotans (Higginson and Pepler, 1954; Walker and Arvidsson, 1954). The mean serum cholesterol levels between the Bantu and Minnesotans were not found to be significantly different in age groups below 40. Beyond the age of 40, the mean serum cholesterol levels of the Bantu were significantly lower. Walker and Arvidsson hypothesised that the low fat content and/or the fibre content of the staple corn and legumes could explain the lower cholesterol levels observed in those over 40 years old (Walker and Arvidsson, 1954).

Keys' publications in 1953-1954 continued to make no mention of the different types of fat: saturated; monounsaturated and polyunsaturated (Keys, 1953a; Keys and Anderson, 1954; Keys et al., 1954a; Keys and Keys, 1954; Keys et al., 1954b). The focus remained total fat, with sporadic mentions of animal or vegetable fats. A specific paper, reviewing the impact of blood coagulation following fat consumption, did not introduce the

saturated/unsaturated fat terminology although it did test the ingestion of butterfat (Buzina and Keys, 1956).

"The relationship of the diet to the development of atherosclerosis in man" documented the results of controlled experiments with vegetable oils in laboratory conditions (Keys and Anderson, 1954). An experiment had been undertaken involving 24 men, in which olive oil and cottonseed oil were compared. These fats were chosen for their chemical dissimilarity. "No difference between the effects of olive oil and of cottonseed oil on serum cholesterol could be found" (p.190) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

Olive oil has 14 g of saturated fat, 73 g of monounsaturated fat and 11 g of polyunsaturated fat per 100 g of product (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013c). Cottonseed oil has 26 g of saturated fat, 18 g of monounsaturated fat and 52 g of polyunsaturated fat per 100 g of product (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013e). The 1954 symposium paper provided no reference for the olive oil vs. cottonseed oil trial, but it found no difference between the effects of these different fat levels on serum cholesterol. The different dietary fats – saturated, monounsaturated and polyunsaturated – were not noted in this Symposium paper (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

After summarising the evidence from the studies of the men of Minnesota, Naples, Madrid and Slough, Keys stated: "It appears there are no exceptions to the rule that the average concentration of cholesterol in the blood serum of clinically healthy middle-aged men is roughly proportional to the percentage of total fats in the diet" (p.188) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

Having proposed a relationship between serum cholesterol and total dietary fat, this paper added a proposed relationship between heart disease and total dietary fat. Keys referenced his own correlation, between the death rate from degenerative heart disease and the proportion of fat calories in the national diet for six countries, from the 1953 Mount Sinai presentation (Keys, 1953a) as evidence for the second conclusion: "No other variable in the mode of life besides the fat calories in the diet is known which shows anything like such a consistent relationship to the mortality rate from coronary or degenerative heart disease" (p.189) (Keys and Anderson, 1954) (Fig 2).

A small intervention, with two male subjects aged 25 and 29, sought to test the impact of increasing total fat intake, while maintaining calorie intake, on mean serum cholesterol levels (Mann, 1955). The experiment found that two young men did not show a significant increase of serum cholesterol or various beta-lipoprotein fractions

during 15 days on a diet of which 57% of the calories came from fat as provided in Pemmican (p.233) (Mann, 1955).

The first references to saturated and unsaturated fats were found in the paper “Diet and the development of coronary heart disease” (Keys, 1956). Keys noted that a general distinction between animal and vegetable fats was unsatisfactory, but that there was no doubt that different food fats were not identical in their effect on the cholesterol-lipoprotein system (p.375) (Keys, 1956). Keys found an approximate, but far from perfect relationship, between the cholesterogenic effect of different food fats and their degree of saturation (p.375). Corn oil, highly unsaturated (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013b), was reported to have elicited substantial declines in serum cholesterol levels (p.375). This provided rationale for the first randomised controlled trial, which used corn oil as an intervention (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

The effect on cholesterol and coagulation was inconsistent. Waldron and Duncan found that the more saturated the fat, the less effect it had on blood coagulation (Waldron and Duncan, 1954). Keys confirmed that in his laboratory experiments, no relationship was found between saturation of dietary fats and their effects in producing hypercoagulability of the blood (p.375) (Keys, 1956).

Keys offered some dietary advice in this paper: “A reasonable, practical conclusion from the present evidence might be to propose for American adults a sharp reduction in the total dietary fat from their current intake in which fats account for some 40 per cent or more of the total dietary calories. In this dietary adjustment, emphasis might be placed on reducing the consumption of margarine, hydrogenated shortenings, butter fat, and meat fats” (p.375-6) (Keys, 1956).

The seminal paper to study the degree of saturation of fats as a factor in serum cholesterol was received for publication in January 1957 (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957). This paper noted that it had been shown that serum cholesterol levels reduced on low fat diets (Keys, 1953a; Keys et al., 1956; Mellinkoff, Machella and Reinhold, 1950; Starke, 1950). However, Ahrens *et al* hypothesised that some of the findings had been compromised by not maintaining food intakes at eucaloric levels (Ahrens, Blankenhorn and Tsaltas, 1954). Kinsell *et al* reported that diets high in vegetable fat reduced serum cholesterol levels, whereas isocaloric substitution of animal fats in these diets caused the levels to rise promptly (Kinsell et al., 1952). When six patients were studied under metabolic ward conditions with strict isocaloric substitution of mixed animal by mixed

vegetable fats and with constant intakes of the same dietary protein, Ahrens *et al* confirmed the conclusions of Kinsell *et al*.

Ahrens described the standard practice of referring to fats as animal or vegetable as “perhaps a greater handicap” than the eucaloric issue (p.933) (Ahrens, 1957) noting that the distinction was chemically meaningless and even misleading.

The aim of the Anderson *et al* paper was to study the impact of different food fats on cholesterol and of a low-fat diet *per se* (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957). The experiments were undertaken with 132 schizophrenic men institutionalised at the Hastings State Hospital. The “House Diet” was 3,200 calories comprising 90 g of protein and 140 g of fat, one third of which was butterfat. Fat accounted for approximately 40% of the total calorie intake, as typical of the American diet of the time. The House Diet was assessed over a four week period and then dietary interventions were made, each of four weeks in duration.

The low-fat diet intervention contained 9-12% of total calorie intake in the form of fat; fat was swapped isocalorically for carbohydrate in the form of sugar, jelly, bread, rice and potatoes. The different dietary fat experiments added 100 g daily of the following types of fat: butterfat; olive oil; cotton seed oil; corn oil; sunflower seed oil; coconut oil; and sardine oil. The experiments tried to maintain calorie levels, but this was not always achieved. The article listed the different diets reviewed by composition of saturated, mono-ethenoid and poly-ethenoid fatty acids (table 2, p.425) (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957).

The experiments found that olive oil, low-fat, cottonseed oil and sardine oil had the lowest effect on serum cholesterol and that the difference between these four was of border line significance. The sunflower oil diet gave a distinctly lower cholesterol level than any of these four diets, but no direct statistical comparison was possible because the oils were fed to different groups of men. Corn oil was described as being in a class by itself yielding the lowest serum cholesterol value of all the diets (p.434-5) (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957); further rationale for the Rose *et al* intervention (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The authors concluded that the serum cholesterol responses to the various fats corresponded roughly to the principle that saturated fats promoted higher cholesterol levels than polyunsaturated fats but neither degree of saturation nor content of linoleic acid fully explained the results (p.441) (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957).

The coconut oil findings did not support the hypothesis that saturated fat impacts serum cholesterol levels. Coconut oil was recorded as being 97% saturated fat and 3% unsaturated fat (table 2, p.425). Mean serum cholesterol levels of the men on the House (control) diet were 231.8 mg/dl, with a standard error of 11.1 mg/dl (table 5, p.429). Mean serum cholesterol levels of 12 men after 4 weeks of 100 g of coconut oil supplementation were 224.3 mg/dl, with a standard error of 9.0 mg/dl (table 12, p.434). The document summary reported: “Coconut oil, 100 gm daily, produced no significant change in the serum cholesterol compared with the control diet with the same total fat supplied in mixed form” (p.441) (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957).

Towards the end of 1957, Keys collaborated with Anderson and Grande again in another landmark paper (Keys, Anderson and Grande, 1957). This Lancet article presented the Keys equation for the first time. Keys *et al* used the data and experiments from the Hastings State hospital for 66 men aged 32 to 56 years and included three experiments from Shime, Japan, where 18 Japanese men aged 22 to 54 years had been studied. The goal of the work was to see if an equation could be established to predict the change in serum cholesterol that would follow changes in dietary fat in diets otherwise in calorie equilibrium. Keys *et al* proposed that the relationship $\Delta \text{cholesterol} = 2.74 \Delta S - 1.31 \Delta P$ held as a predictor of changes in cholesterol where which ΔS and ΔP were the changes in the per cent of dietary calories derived from saturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids respectively. This was the original form of the Keys equation.

Keys *et al* noted the narrow applications of these limited findings: “The prediction equations developed here apply only to the conditions of these experiments – namely, adult men aged 30-55, in calorie equilibrium, and with a constant rate of energy expenditure, who are consuming diets containing 10-40% of calories from fats, with periods on each diet of about two to four weeks. Moreover we are concerned with “control” serum-cholesterol levels less than 300 mg. per 100 ml. on ordinary diets of the type where S is about 18% and P about 4% of total calories. Finally, these predictions are for group averages; the reliability of individual prediction is low because of the intra- and inter-variability noted above and because the magnitude of $\Delta \text{Chol.}$ for a given dietary change tends to be related to the characteristic serum-cholesterol level of the individual” (p.965) (Keys, Anderson and Grande, 1957)

In 1965, Keys *et al* modified their formula to eliminate stearic acid from the saturated fatty acid term since it, like oleic acid, appeared to be neutral (Keys, Anderson and

Grande, 1965b). Hegsted also developed Keys' work: "The Hegsted equation was derived from the multiple-regression equation, $\Delta y = 2.16 \Delta S - 1.65 \Delta P + 6.77 \Delta C$, in which Δy is change in serum cholesterol in mg/dl; ΔS and ΔP are changes in intake of saturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids expressed as percentage of calories and ΔC is change in cholesterol intake expressed as decigrams/2600 kcal (p.299) (Hegsted, 1986). Hegsted noted in this 1986 paper that Keys was critical of Hegsted's work, suggesting that it grossly overestimated the serum cholesterol response to dietary cholesterol (Keys, Anderson and Grande, 1965a). Hegsted reviewed both equations and concluded that neither provided a satisfactory prediction of actual outcomes obtained.

The exploration of dietary fat as a factor in CHD

The study of coronary disease in young American soldiers killed in action in Korea found that lesions were commonly located at or near points of bifurcation; giving the impression that haemodynamics in the lumen in close proximity to bifurcations played an important part in the mechanism of plaque formation (p.1091) (Enos, Holmes and Beyer, 1953). The article reported that the intima of the coronary vessels in young Koreans was thick, but atheromatosis was rare. The researchers suggested that it was most unlikely that one factor alone would be the cause of coronary sclerosis and that their observations of the wear and tear on the intima, caused by circulation of blood at points of bifurcation, should be considered along with other basic factors, such as hormones and diet (p.1092) (Enos, Holmes and Beyer, 1953).

In their 1955 publication, Enos *et al* reported on 114 Japanese comparators that they had been able to study – 30 of whom were male, approximating the age group of the American soldiers. Plaques observed were located at the points of stress (bifurcation) in the Japanese subjects, as they were in the Americans. There were no plaques causing over 50% luminal narrowing in the young Japanese males, whereas the average age of 20 American soldiers with over 50% luminal narrowing was 22.6 years. The amount, and the distribution, of lipids forming the plaques were visibly different in the Americans, as compared to the Japanese. The conclusion was that certain plasma lipids were modified by diet and were an important factor in the development of CHD in young males (p.914) (Enos et al., 1955). The impact of stress on coronary disease for American soldiers dying in combat 8,500km from home, as compared to Japanese natives dying in normal circumstances, was a confounding variable. An additional finding to note was that there was no association between hypertension and coronary disease observed in the American soldiers.

McNamara *et al* reported on a study of 105 American soldiers, with a mean age of 22.1 years, killed in action in Vietnam (McNamara et al., 1971). 47 men exhibited some degree of atherosclerosis in one or more of the coronary vessels, leading the researchers to conclude that some degree of coronary atherosclerosis was present in 45% of young American males. Involvement of more than 1 vessel occurred in 26% of this group and severe atherosclerosis occurred in 5%. The suggestions of a dietary association, made by Enos *et al*, were not reiterated by McNamara *et al*; the Vietnam study making no reference to diet or dietary fat. This remained the case with subsequent pathological investigations, such as the Bogalusa Heart Study (Berenson et al., 1992) and the PDAY Study (McGill and McMahan, 1998). Fatty streaks in arteries were described and knowledge of lipids and lipoproteins advanced between the wartime studies of Enos and McNamara to the peacetime PDAY study, but these were not studies of dietary fat.

Total dietary fat was the key factor in one of Keys' best known and most important publications (Keys, 1953a). This publication was first presented at the Mount Sinai Hospital in New York City in January 1953. It is often referred to as the Mount Sinai presentation. This was Keys' first presentation of a graph of the relationship between mortality from degenerative heart disease and fat calories as a percentage of total calories in the diet for a number of countries, for men aged 45-49 and 55-59 (fig. 2, p134) (Keys, 1953a), replicated as Fig. 2.1 in this chapter. Degenerative heart disease was defined as coronary disease, angina pectoris, infarction, chronic myocarditis and myocardial degeneration. Keys presented the graph with data for Australia, Canada, England and Wales, Italy, Japan and the USA. The six data points suggested a strong relationship between fat calories as a percentage of dietary intake and deaths from heart disease for men aged 55-59.

Fig. 2.1

Fig. 2.1 is a replication of Keys' (fig. 2). Mortality from degenerative heart disease (categories 93 and 94 in the Revision of 1938, categories 420 and 422 in the Revision of 1948, International List. National vital statistics from official sources). Fat calories as percentage of total calories calculated from national food balance data for 1949 supplied by the Nutrition Division, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (p.134) (Keys, 1953a).

Keys concluded from the above: "Whether or not cholesterol etc., are involved, it must be concluded that dietary fat somehow is associated with cardiac diseases mortality, at least in middle age (p.134)" (Keys, 1953a).

Keys presented his graph of six countries with the explanation "So far it has been possible to get fully compatible dietary and vital statistics data from 6 countries" (p.133) (Keys, 1953a). This was refuted by Hilleboe (Hilleboe, 1957), who presented Yerushalmy's data for 12 countries for heart disease and calories derived from fat in the diet and then by Yerushalmy and Hilleboe in their co-authored 1957 paper, which presented data for 22 countries (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957). "Since no information is given by Keys on how or why the six countries were selected for fig. 1 [fig. 1 in

Yerushalmy and Hilleboe was a replication of Keys' fig. 2 from the Mount Sinai presentation, which is replicated in this chapter as Fig. 2.1], it is necessary to investigate the association between dietary fat and heart disease mortality in *all* countries for which information is available. This is shown in fig. 3 [replicated in this chapter as Fig. 2.2]. For males aged fifty-five to fifty-nine years in 22 countries. It is immediately obvious that the inclusion of all the countries greatly reduces the apparent association" (p.2345) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957).

Fig. 2.2

Fig. 2.2 is a replication of Yerushalmy and Hilleboe's (fig. 3). Mortality from arteriosclerotic and degenerative heart disease (B-26) and fat calories as per cent of total calories in males fifty-five to fifty-nine years. Calculated from national food balance data by F.A.O. (see text for definition) (p.2346) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957).

An important limitation of the data was noted by Yerushalmy and Hilleboe: the index for fat as a percentage of total calories in the diet was not based on food consumption, but on food available for consumption. Appendix B of their paper was an extract from a World Health Organisation document detailing the limitations and known inaccuracies of such data.

In their response to Keys, Yerushalmy and Hilleboe examined 1) the associations between heart disease and dietary components other than fat and 2) the association between dietary fat and causes of death other than diseases of the heart. The paper meticulously reviewed classifications of heart disease. Keys' fig 2. (p.134) (Keys, 1953a) included categories 420 (arteriosclerotic heart disease, including coronary disease) and 422 (other myocardial degeneration). Yerushalmy and Hilleboe noted that the International List of Causes of Death contained five potentially relevant categories: B-24 rheumatic fever; B-25 chronic rheumatic heart disease; B-26 arteriosclerotic and degenerative heart disease; B-27 other diseases of the heart; B-28 hypertension with heart disease. B-26 most closely approximated to the categories used by Keys: 420 and 422.

Close examination of individual country death rates, notably Chile, Mexico and France, convinced Yerushalmy and Hilleboe that B-26 and B-27 should be combined, as some deaths from arteriosclerotic and degenerative heart disease were being recorded as "other diseases of the heart" in these countries. Rank correlations for categories B-26 and B-27 combined showed that r was 0.390 for the percentage of total calories from fat and deaths from diseases of the heart, but r was 0.608 for the percentage of total calories from animal protein and deaths from diseases of the heart (table III, p.2348) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957). This led to their conclusion: "the dietary fat-heart disease association is *not* unique or specific since the association between *fat* and heart disease mortality is not as strong as that between *animal protein* and heart disease (p.2349) (original emphasis) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957). Yerushalmy and Hilleboe added that, using the Keys' category of B-26 alone, the rank correlation was still stronger for per cent of calories from animal protein and heart disease mortality (0.643) than for per cent of calories from fat and heart disease mortality (0.587).

To examine the second question, Yerushalmy and Hilleboe calculated the rank correlation coefficients between fat, protein and carbohydrate in the diet and causes of death other than diseases of the heart. The results were presented in table IV (p.2350) of their paper (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957). The rank correlation coefficient for the proportion of calories from fat and causes of death other than diseases of the heart was -0.657 ($p < 0.05$), indicating that a higher proportion of dietary fat was correlated with lower mortality from causes other than heart disease. There was also a negative correlation for the proportion of calories from animal protein and mortality from causes other than heart disease, with a rank correlation coefficient of minus 0.405 ($p < 0.05$).

Yerushalmy and Hilleboe did not comment upon the strongest positive correlation in table IV (p.2350): the proportion of calories from carbohydrate had an r value of 0.671 ($p < 0.05$), in correlation with mortality from causes other than heart disease.

Yerushalmy and Hilleboe's conclusion, from the examination of their two questions, was that the evidence from 22 countries for which data were available invalidated the claimed association between the proportion of fat calories available for consumption in national diets and deaths from heart disease. They found that the association was not specific for dietary fat or for heart disease mortality. Yerushalmy and Hilleboe described the claimed association as "tenuous" and one that could not serve as much support for the hypothesis which implicated fat as a factor in heart disease (p.2351) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957).

Yerushalmy and Hilleboe suggested that a more plausible explanation was that the dietary factors, which appeared to be positively related to heart disease, were a reflection of related national attributes. They proposed that the amount of fat and protein available for consumption was an index of a country's development, industrially, nutritionally, medically and no doubt in other respects as well (p.2350) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957). This has been explored in Appendix 1.

Keys' response to the critique of Yerushalmy and Hilleboe was published as an editorial in the *Journal of Chronic Disease* (Keys, 1957b). Keys defended his use of categories 420 and 422 to define CHD and not B-26, which included 421. Category 421 was described officially as "chronic endocarditis not specified as rheumatic, 'excluding' chronic endocarditis specified as syphilitic or gonococcal." Keys described this category as disorders of the valves of the heart where the physician does not specify that he is sure of the origin (p.553) (Keys, 1957b).

Keys' second argument was that deaths in one period should be compared with the diet of an earlier period. The example given was that, for deaths in 1950-1952 the critical age period might be in the middle 40s. Keys criticised Hilleboe's review of 12 countries for using dietary data for 1954, an average of 3 years after the mortality data. Keys' graph of 6 countries (Keys, 1953a) used mortality data from 1948-49 and food balance data for 1949, so this criticism could similarly apply.

Keys also challenged the validity of Yerushalmy and Hilleboe's dietary data, which was based on national average diets (p.557) (Keys, 1957b). This argument was undermined by two factors: i) the same Food and Agricultural Organisation (FAO) data was used by Keys, just for fewer countries and ii) Yerushalmy and Hilleboe did find a relationship

between dietary fat and deaths from CHD. Their argument was that a) there was a stronger correlation with animal protein and heart deaths than dietary fat and b) causation had not been established (Hilleboe, 1957).

Keys response to the association vs. causation issue was the statement: “I doubt that Dr. Hilleboe really believes he has adequate evidence to state that there is *not* a causal relationship between dietary fat and the tendency to develop atherosclerosis in man” (Keys’ emphasis) (p.552) (Keys, 1957b).

In the same month, July 1957, Yudkin undertook a comprehensive assessment of the hypothesis that coronary thrombosis was related to the amount of dietary fat, or a particular sort of fat (Yudkin, 1957). He reviewed three statistical approaches: 1) Diets and coronary mortality in 15 different countries for the same year (1951-52); 2) Diets and coronary mortality in different classes of people from the UK in the same year; and 3) Trends in diets and trends in coronary mortality in the UK since 1928 when the classification of deaths due to coronary thrombosis was introduced.

1) was presented in six diagrams, which plotted mortality per 100,000 men aged 55-64 (Keys proposed the strongest relationship for men aged 55-59 in the 1953 Mount Sinai presentation (Keys, 1953a)) for: total fat (grams per day); calories from fat as a percentage of total calories; animal fat (g/day); butter fat (g/day); vegetable fat (g/day); and margarine (g/day) (figs.1-6, p.155-156) (Yudkin, 1957). Yudkin found no relationship between total fat and coronary mortality, having observed that there was a range of coronary mortality of nearly fourfold with the same intake of fat (p.155) (Yudkin, 1957). There was almost no difference when fat as a percentage of calories was used instead of total fat. The relationship with animal fat was “less direct” than with total fats; there was “even less support” for butter fat; “there is no relationship between the intake of vegetable fat and coronary mortality”; “again, there is no relationship with the consumption of margarine” (p.156) (Yudkin, 1957). Yudkin proposed that there was a better relationship with intake of sugar than with any other nutrient examined. In parallel with Yerushalmy and Hilleboe (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957), Yudkin also proposed that coronary thrombosis was associated with higher living standards. “This is supported by the relationship which exists between coronary mortality and national income per head (fig. 11)” (p.158) (Yudkin, 1957).

2) The analysis of mortality in different classes of people in the UK drew on Registrar-General data for 1951: V unskilled; IV semiskilled; III skilled; II intermediate and I professional. Data for food consumption was available for five earning classes from the

Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Food. Yudkin assumed occupational class was related to income. He found considerable differences in coronary mortality by occupation, a semiskilled worker having approximately half the chance of dying from coronary disease than a professional man, but small differences in dietary fat intake (total or of different types).

3) Yudkin found no trend relationship for data since 1928 for total fat, animal fats, vegetable fat or margarine/other hydrogenated fats. Mortality rose steadily from 1928 to 1954, with a dip in the first years of World War II. Total fat intake and animal fat intake fell for three periods after 1938, while mortality continued to rise. Sugar intake was noted as lower between 1940 to 1950 than before the war, while coronary mortality doubled during that time. Yudkin reported "By far the best correlation I have found with trends in coronary mortality is in the number of radio and television licences (fig.24). There is nearly as good a correlation with the number of registered motor-vehicles" (p.159) (Yudkin, 1957).

Mann presented data for 23 countries which showed that there was no significant relationship between death rates from all causes, for all age groups, both sexes and total calories available for consumption (Mann, 1957). There was also no significant relationship between death rates from all causes, for all age groups, both sexes and the percentage of calories from total fat. There was a significant relationship ($r = 0.7121$, $p = 0.000138$) for deaths from heart disease (categories 420-422) and the percentage of calories from total fat. However, there was a stronger relationship ($r = 0.8255$, $p = 0.00001$) for deaths from heart disease (categories 420-422) and total calories available for consumption.

In a seminar on atherosclerosis, Ahrens noted that the correlation between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and the incidence of heart disease was widely accepted as a cause and effect relationship, but he cautioned that a direct correlation, no matter how strong, could not be used as proof of cause and effect (p.928) (Ahrens, 1957). Ahrens endorsed the most recent challenges of the time (Mann, 1957; Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957; Yudkin, 1957) as he reiterated stronger correlations that had been found between heart disease and the intake of animal protein or sugar, and heart disease and the number of television sets or car licenses (p.928) (Ahrens, 1957).

The role of dietary fat in CHD was the subject of much debate during the 1950s. Support for the hypothesis was led by Keys and many researchers with whom he collaborated: Anderson (Keys and Anderson, 1954); Bronte-Stewart (Bronte-Stewart,

Keys and Brock, 1955); Buzina (Buzina and Keys, 1956); Fidanza (Keys et al., 1952); Grande (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957); Karvonen (Roine et al., 1958); Kimura (Keys et al., 1958); Mickelsen (Keys et al., 1950a); Miller (Keys et al., 1950c); Taylor (Keys et al., 1950a). Mickelsen and Taylor were research partners of Keys for the Minnesota Starvation Experiment (Keys et al., 1950a). Keys went on to collaborate with Buzina, Fidanza, Karvonen, Kimura and Taylor in The Seven Countries Study.

Opposition to the hypothesis lacked comparable prominent leadership. Mann and Stare presented together at the Symposium on Atherosclerosis (National Research Council, 1954) setting out their differences with Keys and Anderson who presented at the same symposium. Yerushalmy and Hilleboe were not convinced by the hypothesis (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957) and Yudkin offered an alternative hypothesis that sugar was the important dietary factor in CHD (Yudkin, 1957).

The examination of associations between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD

Dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD were connected together in a 1955 publication, which studied a number of different ethnic groups in Cape Town. Between February and May 1955, 364 men were studied from three different racial groups: (white) Europeans, (black) Bantu and what was called "Cape coloured" at the time – a term not used today (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955). The subjects were between the ages of 40 and 58. Men with evidence of present or previous heart disease were excluded: nine Europeans, five Cape coloured and one Bantu. This was interesting *per se*, as incidence of heart disease was strongly associated with previous heart disease, so results could have been forecast from this fact alone.

Table 2.2 Mean serum cholesterol (mg/dl) (\pm SD) and grams from vegetable and animal fat per day: data extracted from (table I, p.1104 and fig.1 p.1105) (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955).

	Bantu	Cape coloured	European
Men	132	118	114
Age (mean)	45.8 \pm 5.5	46.5 \pm 5.0	47.0 \pm 5.2
Mean serum cholesterol (mg/dl)	166.3 \pm 47.2	204.1 \pm 54.8	234.0 \pm 52.9
Vegetable fat intake (g/day)	10	22	14
Animal fat intake (g/day)	40	60	80

The study noted the higher animal fat and total fat intake of Europeans relative to Cape Coloured and Bantu. This correlated with CHD. For people aged 35 or over, the death rate from CHD, was more than twice as high in Europeans as in Cape Coloureds. Bantu deaths from CHD were very rare; possibly one to three being registered each year (p.1105) (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955).

This paper confirmed Keys' categorisation of animal and vegetable fats, as opposed to saturated or unsaturated fats. The Bronte-Stewart paper also confirmed that Keys remained most interested in total fat at this stage of his work. He reiterated that, of all dietary factors under review, the proportion of fat in the diet was the one bearing the closest relationship to the incidence of CHD and the level of blood cholesterol (p.1106) (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955).

The paper concluded with what may have been the first statement of the diet-heart hypothesis: "The results of this survey support the hypothesis that the dietary intake of fat influences the level of the serum cholesterol, and in turn may be one of the major factors influencing the pathogenesis of coronary heart-disease" (p.1107) (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955).

The 1950s was the decade when randomised controlled trials (RCT) started to examine the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD. The first RCT published was the study of corn and olive oil (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The first RCT started was The Oslo Diet Heart Study, which recruited and evaluated participants between 1956 and 1958 (Leren, 1970). The Research Committee Low-fat Diet was the second started (1957) and the second to be published (Research Committee, 1965). Two RCTs commenced in 1960 and were published in 1968 (Medical Research Council, 1968) and 1969 (Dayton et al., 1969) respectively. The Sydney Diet Heart Study started in 1966 and was published in 1978 (Woodhill et al., 1978). These RCTs are systematically reviewed in Chapter Three.

Summary

The review of the literature established the following:

The origin of the hypothesis of cholesterol (dietary and/or serum) as a risk factor for CHD

The summary of findings from the original animal studies was that: rabbits (herbivores) fed animal foods developed fatty deposits/changes in the aortas; rats (omnivores) fed

animal foods produced no observable changes in the aortas; and rabbits fed cholesterol in plant food showed no arterial damage.

The exploration of serum cholesterol as a factor in CHD

Evidence was found for a relationship between serum cholesterol and CHD (Gertler, Garn and Lerman, 1950; Keys, 1956; Steiner, Kendall and Mathers, 1952) although age was a confounding variable (Keys et al., 1950b; Morrison, Hall and Chaney, 1948).

The examination of dietary cholesterol as a factor in serum cholesterol

The most definitive position on this topic was presented in the Symposium on Atherosclerosis: "that the cholesterol content, per se, of all natural diets has *no* significant effect on either the serum cholesterol level or the development of atherosclerosis in man" (p.182) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

The exploration of dietary fat as a factor in serum cholesterol levels

In the early 1950s, literature referred to animal and vegetable fat and not the degree of saturation of fat (Keys, 1952a; Keys, 1952b; Keys et al., 1950c). Interventions with vegetable fat were extrapolated to conclusions about animal fat, without animal fat having been tested (Keys, 1952a; Keys, 1952b).

The first references to saturated and unsaturated fats occurred later in the decade (Keys, 1956). Keys' earliest findings were that there was no relationship between the saturation of fats and their effects in producing hypercoagulability of the blood after they were eaten (Keys, 1956).

Following observational studies of men in Minnesota, Naples, Slough and Madrid, Keys concluded that the total fat content of the diet (as a proportion of calories) exerted a powerful influence on the serum cholesterol level in man (Keys et al., 1954a). Age appeared to be a confounder, with cholesterol rising to the age of 50-55 in Minnesotan and Slough men and rich men in Madrid. Neapolitan men and poor men in Madrid demonstrated stable and falling cholesterol levels respectively between the ages of 40 and 50; rising before these ages.

Corn oil was identified as a particular fat of interest, as it had a significant impact on serum cholesterol levels in studies (Anderson, Keys and Grande, 1957; Keys, 1956). This explained the administration of corn oil in the first dietary intervention randomised controlled trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

The exploration of dietary fat as a factor in CHD

The graph of deaths from heart disease and calories from total fat in men aged 55-59, from the Mount Sinai presentation of 1953 is still referenced today as the seminal diagram showing an association between total dietary fat and CHD in six countries (Keys, 1953a). The response of Yerushalmy and Hilleboe demonstrated that data were available for 22 countries (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957).

Keys concluded that no other variable, besides the fat calories in the diet, showed such a consistent relationship to the mortality rate from CHD (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

Ahrens cautioned that a direct correlation, no matter how strong, did not prove cause and effect (Ahrens, 1957) and noted that stronger correlations had been found with heart disease and the intake of animal protein or sugar, and the number of television sets or automobile licenses (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957; Yudkin, 1957).

The examination of associations between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD

The first statement of the diet-heart hypothesis appeared to have been made in a 1955 publication, which explored the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD in different ethnic groups in Cape Town (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955). This paper confirmed that total fat intake and animal fat intake were the subjects of examination. Saturated fat was not mentioned.

The Keys and Anderson contribution to the Symposium on Atherosclerosis summarised Keys' views two years before the start of The Seven Countries Study (Keys and Anderson, 1954). Obesity was rejected as a possible factor. Alcohol was dismissed as a factor, unless protective.

In 1957, Keys published another summary paper on "Diet and the epidemiology of coronary heart disease" (Keys, 1957a). His position on fat, cholesterol and heart disease became more certain. He described the American diet as dominated by "innumerable fat-loading meals", the results of which were "hypercholesteremia, which promotes atherosclerosis". Keys differentiated that food fats were not identical in promoting hypercholesteremia, but those most prevalent in fatty diets were more powerful in this direction than food oils that had an opposing effect. As a final complication, Keys noted that different fats had differing effects on serum cholesterol and blood coagulation (p.1912) (Keys, 1957a).

This was the context for the start of The Seven Countries Study in 1956-1958 – the subject of systematic review in Chapter Five.

Chapter Three

A systematic review and meta-analysis of the randomised controlled trial evidence available at the time of the introduction of dietary fat recommendations

Introduction

US public health dietary advice was announced by the Select Committee on Nutrition and Human needs in 1977 (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) and was followed by UK public health dietary advice issued by the National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education in 1983 (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983). Dietary recommendations in both cases focused on reducing dietary fat intake; specifically to i) reduce overall fat consumption to 30% of total energy intake and ii) reduce saturated fat consumption to 10% of total energy intake.

The recommendations were an attempt to address coronary heart disease (CHD) mortality. Both documents acknowledged that the evidence was not conclusive. Hegsted's introduction to the Dietary Goals for The United States noted "there will undoubtedly be many people who will say we have not proven our point "(p.8) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977). The UK publication referred to "a strong consensus of opinion" (p.24) (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983).

The evidence available to dietary committees at that time comprised epidemiological studies and randomised controlled trials (RCTs). The most comprehensive population study undertaken was The Seven Countries Study by Keys *et al* (Keys, 1970a). This reported that CHD "tended to be related" to serum cholesterol values and these in turn "tended to be related" to the proportion of calories provided by saturated fats in the diet (p.I-193-4) (Keys, 1970e). Keys acknowledged that epidemiological studies could reveal relationships, not causation (Keys, 1970a). RCTs provide the best evidence (Barton, 2000; Burns, Rohrich and Chung, 2011).

While the UK nutritional guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) made reference to The Seven Countries Study, the US committee document (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) did not. Neither publication made reference to any of the RCTs available at that time. However, the US Committee report reported data from the non-randomised, cross-

over trial, the Finnish Mental Hospital Study (Miettinen et al., 1983; Turpeinen et al., 1979).

Although a number of reviews of RCTs have been undertaken, no review has examined the RCT evidence available at the time dietary fat guidelines were introduced (Hooper et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2011; Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010; Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014). Furthermore, these guidelines have not been changed since they were announced, correspondingly, the validity of their evidence based remains current.

This chapter will report on a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess if the published RCTs available to the dietary committees supported their recommendations on dietary fat. With this in mind, the hypothesis is that RCT evidence available to the dietary committees at the time of issuing recommendations did not support the contention that reducing dietary fat intake would contribute to a reduction in CHD risk or related mortality.

Methods

A systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009) (Appendix 2).

Search strategy

A search was undertaken to identify RCTs that examined the relationship between modified or reduced dietary fat intake, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD and all-causes. Exclusion criteria were: studies being observational; non-randomised and/or multi-factorial in design. Inclusion criteria were: randomised dietary intervention studies; study hypothesis relating to a reduction or modification of dietary fat; participants were human adults; studies were a minimum of one year in duration; primary study outcome was all-cause and CHD mortality; data on all-cause mortality, CHD mortality and cholesterol measurements were available.

Searches of the literature were performed to 1983 using MEDLINE and the Cochrane Library. AMED, CAB abstracts, CINAHL, Embase, HMIC and SIGLE (grey literature sources) were not relied upon, as their periods covered were not compatible: from 1985, 1973, 1981, 1980, 1983 and 1992 respectively (National Institute of Clinical Excellence (NICE), 2014; SIGLE System for Information on Grey Literature in Europe, Founded 1992) (Fig. 3.1). The search was undertaken in September 2014.

Selection of studies

Of 98 identified articles, 80 were rejected upon review of the title and abstract. 42 were rejected for being: reviews (24); letters/editorials (14); case reports (2) and research reports (2). Nine were rejected for being surgical or pharmacological interventions. Six were primarily about conditions other than heart disease – four about diabetes, one about pregnancy and one about menstrual activity. Four were rejected for having non human adult subjects i.e. animals or children. Four exercise studies and one epidemiological review were excluded. 10 papers contained the term diet and heart disease but were discussions about matters other than clinical trials for dietary fat and heart disease (four reviewed hospital diets in coronary wards, three involved vegetarian diets, two focused on salt/phosphatide intake and one had weight gain as an outcome). Four papers involved multiple interventions – three of these documented the MRFIT study (The Multiple Risk Factor Intervention Trial Research Group, 1990).

The remaining 18 papers covered 8 trials once duplication was resolved. Six RCTs met the inclusion criteria for the meta-analysis: The Rose Corn Oil Trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965); The Research Committee Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965); The MRC Soya-bean Oil Trial (Medical Research Council, 1968); The LA Veterans Study (Dayton et al., 1969); The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1968; Leren, 1970); and The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978).

The Anti-Coronary Club Trial (Christakis et al., 1966) and The Finnish Mental Hospital Study (Miettinen et al., 1983; Turpeinen et al., 1979) were excluded from the systematic review and meta-analysis, as they were not randomised. The Finnish study was also a cross-over trial. This was not appropriate for the examination of long-term mortality, as deaths in the second phase may have been due to conditions imposed during the initial phase.

To ascertain the validity of eligible randomised trials, a pair of reviewers (ZH and FG) worked independently to determine which studies met the inclusion criteria. The same six were agreed upon. Risk of bias was further assessed using the Cochrane Collaboration assessment tool for: selection bias (random sequence generation, allocation concealment); performance/detection bias (blinding of participants and personnel, blinding of outcome assessment); attrition bias (incomplete data outcome); and reporting bias (selective reporting) (Fig. 3.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). Additionally the meta-analyses for all-cause mortality (Fig. 3.3) and CHD deaths (Fig. 3.4) were tested for sensitivity analysis of the exclusion of any one study.

Data Extraction

Table 3.1, following the systematic review, details data extraction from that systematic review of: study name, duration, year of publication and confirmation of study design; participant characteristics; details of intervention and comparison diet; and outcomes relating to all-cause mortality, CHD related deaths and changes in mean serum cholesterol levels. Where a study contained more than one intervention, both were included (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

The systematic review extracted data in accordance with the PICOS format of the PRISMA methodology: **P**articipants; the dietary **I**ntervention; **C**omparisons between the intervention and control groups; **O**utcomes (cholesterol levels; coronary heart disease deaths and all-cause mortality- as recorded by each study); and **S**tudy design (including flaws and the study's own conclusions) (Moher et al., 2009). Data have also been extracted during the systematic review for the Cochrane Collaboration assessment tool for: selection bias (random sequence generation, allocation concealment); performance/detection bias (blinding of participants and personnel, blinding of outcome assessment); attrition bias (incomplete data outcome); and reporting bias (selective reporting) (Fig. 3.2) (Higgins et al., 2011).

Statistical Analysis

The overall pooled effect was calculated using random effects meta-analysis. Heterogeneity was evaluated using the Q-value, I^2 and T^2 calculations. Funnel plot methodology and Egger's regression intercept (Egger et al., 1997; Sterne et al., 2011) have been calculated, noting the caution for analysing publication bias using funnel plot asymmetry where the meta-analysis has fewer than 10 studies (Higgins JPT and Green S, 2011). Analyses were performed using Comprehensive Meta-Analysis (Borenstein et al., 2005).

Fig. 3.1 (Moher et al., 2009) Summary of systematic review profile.

Results: Systematic review

The six clinical trials systematically reviewed were, in order of publication: 1) The Rose Corn Oil Trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965); 2) The Research Committee Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965); 3) The MRC Soya-bean Oil Trial (Medical Research Council, 1968); 4) The LA Veterans Study (Dayton and Pearce, 1969; Dayton et al., 1969); 5) The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1968; Leren, 1970); and 6) The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978). Trial (6) was available to the UK dietary committee, but not the US dietary review.

Most of the studies published before 1983 were multi-factorial, to an extent, but not described as such. The systematic review notes where more than one dietary intervention was made and where smoking cessation and/or weight reduction were also part of the study.

1) The Rose Corn Oil Trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965)

The study design and participants: The Rose Corn Oil Trial was a three way secondary study with one control group and two oil groups. Men under 70 years old were selected, with previous heart disease, but absence of heart failure. Patients receiving anticoagulant medication were excluded from the trial. 26 men were randomly allocated to the control group, 26 were randomly allocated to an olive oil group and 28 to a corn oil group. When a new patient was accepted for the trial, a sealed envelope was opened containing the allocation instructions. Participants allocated to an intervention group were given a code, so that they did not know which type of oil they would receive. Physicians knew which participants were in an intervention group, but they did not know the oil allocated. Assessment involved medical history, physical examination and electrocardiography. The electrocardiograms were assessed without knowledge of the patient's treatment group.

There were some baseline differences, for example the mean age at entry was 58.8 years in the control group, 55.0 in the olive oil group and 52.6 in the corn oil group. However, there were “no significant differences between the groups with regard to any of the characteristics listed (P in each case >0.05), and it seems likely that at the start of the trial the prognosis for each of the three groups was approximately similar” (p.1532) (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

The trial was planned to last for three years, but results were reported at the end of two years because one half of the patients had been lost to the trial, as a result of death,

reinfarction or absence from follow-up. This has not been judged as attrition bias, as all participants were accounted for at trial end.

The dietary intervention and comparison: Oil intake was intended to be 80 grams a day, taken in three equal doses at meal times. Adherence to the prescribed diet was determined by reviewing the number of cans of oil issued, the amounts left in returned cans and the patients' own statements. Dietary assessments were continued for the two year duration of the trial. This enabled researchers to determine the actual mean intakes of oil as being 58 g per day for olive oil and 64 g per day for corn oil. The participants did not meet the 80 g per day dose, as they did not find the additional oil palatable. The consumption of oil was described as burdensome and complaints of "distaste, nausea and diarrhoea" were recorded (p.1532) (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

The study purpose was described as "to study the effects of prescribing a vegetable oil and a restricted fat diet to patients with ischaemic heart disease" (p.1531). The study aims stated: "It seemed likely that if any differences emerged between the olive-oil and corn-oil groups these would reflect the specific effects of polyunsaturated fatty acids" (p.1531) (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). This may not be the case.

Corn oil is 8% saturated, 59% monounsaturated and 29% polyunsaturated (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013b). Olive oil is 14% saturated, 73% monounsaturated and 11% polyunsaturated (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013c). Compositions of all three fats were different in the two intervention groups – the impact of polyunsaturated fat alone could not be isolated. Additionally, and more importantly, patients in both oil groups were instructed to avoid fried foods, fatty meat, sausages, pastry, ice-cream, cheese, cakes (except plain sponge) and similar processed foods. Milk, eggs, and butter were also restricted. No further dietary advice was given to control patients. Substantial food intake changes were thus made in the intervention groups, not replicated in the control group.

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: The mean serum cholesterol levels at the start of the trial were recorded as 262 mg/dl for the olive oil group, 263 mg/dl for the corn oil group and 253 mg/dl for the control group. Changes in mean serum cholesterol levels were recorded for the first six months, second six months, third six months and final six months of the two year period. The mean serum cholesterol levels for the final period were 261 mg/dl for the olive oil group, 243 mg/dl for the corn oil group 250 mg/dl for the control group. Rose *et al* noted that their method of cholesterol measurement had a likely error of 18 mg/dl, making only the corn oil group changes significant. The 1989

publication by Fraser and Fogarty reported a difference in cholesterol concentration of 19% as the requirement for significant difference (Fraser and Fogarty, 1989); making the corn oil changes unlikely to be significant.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: There were three deaths in the olive oil group, five in the corn oil group and one in the control group. All deaths were from CHD.

Study design – Flaws: First, all three fats were varied, although the study claimed that the specific effects of polyunsaturated fats would be reflected. No one fat was isolated as a controlled variation.

Second, both the corn and olive oil intervention groups were instructed to avoid many processed foods. The administration of oil was not the only dietary variation therefore, which undermined the notion of a controlled experiment. This would have been of greater concern had the intervention groups outperformed the control group.

The study's own conclusion: "The patients receiving the key treatment (corn oil) fared worse than those in the other two groups: two years from the start of treatment infarction or death had occurred in one quarter more of the corn-oil than of the control group. This difference closely approaches the conventional significance level ($0.1 > P > 0.05$). The probability that a true difference of the same magnitude but in the other direction may have been missed by chance is less than 1 in 1,000. It is concluded that under the circumstances of this trial corn oil cannot be recommended as a treatment of ischaemic heart disease. It is most unlikely to be beneficial, and it is possibly harmful" (p.1533) (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

2) The Research Committee Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965)

The study design and participants: The Research Committee Low-fat Diet was a secondary study. 264 men, under the age of 65, who had recently recovered from a first myocardial infarction and who had been in either of two Middlesex hospitals took part in the trial. Patients receiving long-term anticoagulant medication were excluded from the trial. On leaving hospital they were allocated at random to one of two groups. There was no evidence of allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011). One group was placed on a low-fat diet, while the control group continued with their normal diet.

A number of characteristics were measured at baseline: age; weight; social class; activity of work; duration of previous angina; severity of first attack; and the duration of anticoagulant treatment. None was statistically significant. Weight differed slightly –

the mean weight of the control group was 166 lb against 161 lb for the intervention group, but this was not significant ($0.1 > p > 0.05$).

The trial ran from 1957 to 1963 and the mean follow-up for both the diet and control groups, during this period, was three years. 12 patients admitted to the trial were later rejected because long-term anticoagulants were needed, or because they relapsed before starting the diet, or because they did not cooperate, leaving 252 patients for final analysis.

The study purpose was to test whether a low-fat diet, given to men with coronary heart disease, would reduce the risk of recurrences.

The dietary intervention and comparison: The dietary intervention was to allow the experiment group 40 g of fat daily. "The daily allowance included 14 g. (1/2 oz.) butter, 84 g. (3 oz.) of meat, 1 egg, 56 g. (2 oz.) cottage cheese, and skimmed milk. The nature of the fat consumed was not altered, nor were any additional unsaturated fats given" (p.501) (Research Committee, 1965).

Overweight patients were given weight reducing diets, irrespective of their group. "In the control group this was done so far as possible by reducing carbohydrates rather than fats. 21% of the control patients and 15% of the diet group were advised to reduce, but apart from this advice control patients were told that no alteration in diet habits was needed" (p.501) (Research Committee, 1965).

Adherence to the diet was measured in two ways. i) Patients in both groups were asked to record the weight of all food consumed on a different day each week for the first seven weeks after admission to the trial and thereafter on the first day of each month. ii) An independent dietician interviewed a number of patients in each group. "69% of all the patients had between 80% and 100% of the possible diet sheets available for analysis" (p.502) (Research Committee, 1965). This enabled researchers to record average daily fat intake as between 43-45 g of fat per day for the intervention group during five years of review and 106-128 g of fat per day for the control group during the same period.

The assessment of relapse was made by one physician who did not know the dietary group of the patient concerned (p.501) (Research Committee, 1965).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: The starting mean serum cholesterol levels were 260 mg/dl for the diet group and 266 mg/dl for the control group. After three years, the

mean serum cholesterol levels were 216 mg/dl for the diet group and 233 mg/dl for the control group.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: There were 20 deaths from all causes in the diet group and 24 deaths from all causes in the control group. There were 17 and 20 deaths from CHD in the diet and control groups respectively.

Study design – Flaws: The average starting weight of men in the control group (166 lb) was slightly higher than the average starting weight of men in the diet group (161 lb). The calorie intake of the diet group was substantially lower than the control group, peaking at over 780 calories difference at the 4 year observation point. At this point, the diet group was consuming, on average, 70% of the calorie intake of the control group. The smallest difference between the calorie intakes for the two groups was observed at the two year review point – the diet group average intake was 2,030 calories and the control group 2,360 – a difference of 330 calories. The weight difference between the two groups reflected these substantial differences. The average weight of the diet group reduced from 161 lb at study entry to 148 lb at 6 months, where it remained remarkably steady until an average weight of 151 lb was recorded after 4 years. The control group average weight reduced from 166 lb at study entry to 159 lb, where it also stayed remarkably steady until the 4 year figure of 158 lb was recorded. The recorded changes in weight undermined direct associations between a low-fat diet intervention and coronary event outcomes, by introducing an indirect variable of weight, which could also have impacted coronary event outcomes.

The study's own conclusion: "A controlled trial of a 40 g. low-fat diet was carried out on 264 men who had survived a first infarction. Despite a lowering of the blood-cholesterol and a greater fall in body-weight in the treated group, the relapse-rate was not significantly different in the two groups. A low-fat diet has no place in the treatment of myocardial infarction" (p.504) (Research Committee, 1965).

3) The MRC Soya-bean Oil Trial (Medical Research Council, 1968)

The study design and participants: The MRC Soya-bean Oil Trial was a secondary study undertaken for between 2 and 7 years on 393 male patients, under the age of 60, who had recovered from their first myocardial infarction, and who had been discharged from one of four hospitals in London. Patients receiving anticoagulant medication were excluded from the trial; hypotensive drug requirement was an exclusion criterion. The men were randomly allocated to the intervention (diet) or control group within hospitals. There was no evidence for allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011). The

trial was conducted between 1960 to 1967. The shortest individual period in the trial was two years and the longest was six and three-quarter years. Approximately half the men were in the trial for four years or more.

A large number of factors were compared at baseline: angina before first infarction; grading of first infarction; absent peripheral pulses; intermittent claudication; thrombosis; age; parent age of death; height; weight; cholesterol measurement; blood pressure – systolic and diastolic; smoking; social class and sedentary occupation. There was no significant difference in any of these factors with the exception of height, the controls being significantly shorter than men allocated to the intervention diet ($0.01 < p < 0.02$). This one difference was not assumed to impact the overall group comparisons.

The objective of the trial was to determine whether a diet in which saturated fats were replaced by polyunsaturated fats would reduce the incidence of myocardial reinfarction in men who had survived a first attack.

The dietary intervention and comparison: There were 194 control patients who continued their normal diet. 199 men, randomly allocated to the experimental group, were subject to the following dietary changes. They were required "as far as possible" to remove saturated fats from the diet and were instructed to consume 85 g of soya-bean oil daily. The intervention group was allowed up to 85 g of lean meat daily, any fish, skimmed milk, and clear soups. They were not allowed to consume butter, other margarines, cooking-fat, other oils, meat fat, whole milk, cheese, egg yolk, and most biscuits and cakes.

Adherence to the diet was measured similarly to The Research Committee Low-fat Diet: i) Patients in both groups were issued with scales and diet sheets and asked to record the weight of all food consumed on a different day each week for the first seven weeks after admission to the trial and thereafter on the first day of each month. ii) An independent dietician interviewed a sample of patients' wives in each group – 65 from the diet group and 34 from the control group. The interviews with wives were consistent with patient interviews with dieticians and with the diet sheets.

“The decisions of the review committee [on deaths and relapses] were made 'blind' in that the treatment group to which the patient belonged was not disclosed” (p.694) (Medical Research Council, 1968).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: The mean serum cholesterol in the diet group decreased from an initial figure of 272 to 213 mg/dl at six months (22% reduction). This was described as "highly significant", but no significance level was reported. The level in the control group decreased from 273 to 259 mg/dl (6% reduction). This six month reading was the lowest and mean serum cholesterol levels rose steadily in both groups thereafter reaching 226 mg/dl in the diet group and 257 mg/dl in the control group after three years.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: During the trial, there were 45 major CHD relapses (i.e., definite reinfarctions or deaths from coronary heart-disease) in the diet group compared with 51 in the control group. Of these major relapses, 27 in the diet group and 25 in the control group were fatal. The study reported: "None of the differences found is significant. Relapses were not related to initial cholesterol level, to change in cholesterol level during the trial, nor, in any consistent way, to observance of the dietary regimen" (p.693) (Research Committee, 1965).

There was 1 death for other reasons in the diet group and 6 in the control group, making all-cause mortality 28 and 31 in the diet and control groups respectively.

Study design – Flaws: The intervention group had many additional dietary changes beyond the administration of soya-bean oil. This meant that the addition of soya-bean oil was not the sole dietary intervention and thus this was not a controlled intervention of soya-bean administration alone.

The study objective was to determine whether a diet in which saturated fats were replaced by polyunsaturated fats would reduce the incidence of myocardial reinfarction in men who had survived a first attack. Soya-bean oil is relatively high in polyunsaturated fat, but it also has significant levels of saturated fat. Soya-bean oil is approximately 16% saturated fat, 23% monounsaturated fat and 68% polyunsaturated fat (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013d). The dietary intervention administered 14 g of saturated fat daily in the soya-bean oil. Pork, for example, can contain 1.5% saturated fat – less than one tenth of the saturated fat content of soya-bean oil (United States Department of Agriculture, 2013f).

The study's own conclusion: "There is no evidence from the London trial that the relapse-rate in myocardial infarction is materially affected by the unsaturated fat content of the diet used" (p.693) (Research Committee, 1965).

4) The LA Veterans Study (Dayton and Pearce, 1969; Dayton et al., 1969)

The study design and participants: In 1968, an eight year study was completed. The subjects had been middle aged and elderly male veterans living in a 2,600 bed veterans' residence home in Los Angeles. 846 volunteers were allocated at random to one of two groups – 422 to a control group and 424 to an experiment group. As allocation occurred within the veterans' home, there was no evidence for concealment (Higgins et al., 2011). Exclusion criteria included: history of alcoholism; behavioural problems; being under 55 years old (younger residents tended to leave the home within a short period); and having a known disease likely to result in death within five years. Pre-existing complications of atherosclerosis were not disqualifying. Thus this was a combined study of primary and secondary subjects. Medications were not an exclusion factor. At the baseline assessment, details of medications being taken, and having been taken during the year prior to the study, were recorded (table 11, p.II-13) (Dayton et al., 1969). Except for digitalis glycosides and diuretics, few drugs were being taken and there were no differences between the diet and control groups.

The *Circulation* journal article recorded that 348 men in the control group and 345 men in the diet group had no previous anginal syndrome at entry (table 6, p.II-11) (Dayton et al., 1969). This represented 82% and 81% of men in each respective group. 327 men in the control group and 349 men in the diet group had no previous MI at entry (table 7, p.II-12) (Dayton et al., 1969). This represented 77% and 82% in each respective group. Approximately one fifth of the men in each group were secondary subjects and the remaining four fifths primary subjects.

The dietary intervention and comparison: The purpose of the study was to review the impact of substituting unsaturated fat for saturated fat. The control diet contained approximately 40% of calories from fat, mostly of animal origin. The intervention diet maintained total fat intake at approximately 40% of dietary calorie intake, but with vegetable oils comprising two thirds of the fat intake – in substitution for animal fat. Multiple vegetable oils were used, including corn, soya-bean, safflower, and cottonseed. The vegetable oils were incorporated into the experimental diet in milk, imitation ice cream, margarine, special sausage products and filled cheeses. Egg yolks were restricted to seven per week for the experimental diet. The study intervention was thus primarily a substitution of vegetable oils for animal fats. There would be a secondary impact on intakes of saturated, monounsaturated and polyunsaturated fat.

Animal fats tended to be synonymous with saturated fat and vegetable oils synonymous with unsaturated fats in literature at the time, but this was not accurate or helpful. The Dayton paper described "a replacement of the saturated animal fats and hydrogenated shortenings of the conventional diet by equal quantities of unsaturated fat in the form of vegetable oils" (p.II-3) (Dayton et al., 1969). All animal fats other than dairy products have more unsaturated than saturated fat and vegetable oils are not entirely unsaturated fats (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013). Rose also used the term unsaturated vegetable oils (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

Unlike previous dietary interventions, The LA Veterans Study had the advantage of being contained within a veterans' home. Food was prepared for the participants and was controlled in its administration. The meals were served in different dining rooms in the residence to ensure that one group did not consume the food of the other. At each meal a standard tray for each diet was prepared in accordance with the total fat and composition of fat required for the intervention and control groups accordingly.

The study was reported as double blinded (p.II-2), but the dietary changes were too significant for this to be plausible. The study confirmed that the therapists were not blinded: "All participants in the study were personally known to the dieticians and food service workers, who were thus further able to minimize deviations from prescribed diet within the dining room" (p.II-4). The assessors were blinded; they were kept uninformed about diet assignments of individual participants (p.II-5) (Dayton et al., 1969).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels were essentially the same at study entry: 232.7 mg/dl in the diet group and 234.3 mg/dl in the control group (table 14, p. II-14) (Dayton et al., 1969). The article did not report mean serum cholesterol levels after entry. Instead fig. 5 (p.II-19) plotted the ratio of serum cholesterol levels to the baseline over time. From this plot it can be established that mean serum cholesterol levels in the control subjects showed a small rise over the first 20 months, followed by a progressive decline for the next 6 years. In the diet subjects, there was a decrease in mean serum cholesterol levels of approximately 11%, followed by a slow decline paralleling that in the control group. After eight years, the mean serum cholesterol levels for the diet group were 0.82 of baseline levels and they were 0.86 of baseline levels for the control group. This was used to estimate mean serum cholesterol measures at eight years of 191 mg/dl for the diet group and 201 mg/dl for the control group respectively. The notes at the foot of fig. 5 cautioned: "This mode of data presentation

was chosen because follow-up data are incomplete, especially late in the study. The purpose was to avoid comparing the mean for a small group of survivors with the baseline level for the entire original group; the survivors may have started, on the average, at a different level than did the whole group" (p.II-19) (Dayton et al., 1969).

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: The primary end point in the study was new coronary events in the form of sudden death or definite myocardial infarction. In these categories, there were 60 events affecting 52 men in the diet group and 78 events affecting 65 men in the control group. The study reported "the differences are not significant by the chi-square test" (p.II-26) (Dayton et al., 1969).

Deaths from CHD were recorded as 41 in the diet group and 50 in the control group. The statistical significance of this was not presented. All-cause mortality was 174 in the diet group and 177 in the experiment group. These differences were presented as non significant.

Study design – Flaws: The random allocation matched men well for ethnicity and religion, but less well for the important factor of age. The study reported the geometric mean age as virtually identical (65.6 years for the control group and 65.4 years for the diet group), but the diet group had 3 people in the most at-risk age group of 85-89, compared to 9 in the control group. The diet group had 12 octogenarians in total, compared with 21 in the control group (p.II-2) (Dayton et al., 1969). In an 8 year study, not many subjects beyond the age of 80 at study entry would survive.

Smoking at entry was significantly different (table 13, p.II-14) (Dayton et al., 1969). There were 99 non smokers in the diet group and 86 in the control group, 23% and 20% of their respective groups ($p < 0.01$). 11% of the diet group were heavy smokers (more than one pack a day) compared with 17% of the control group. Smoking is a known risk factor in heart disease (Tunstall-Pedoe et al., 1997).

The LA Veterans Study was one of the longest studies, but the precise number of people in the study was difficult to quantify for a precise period of time. Recruitment was continuous from the summer of 1959 to early 1967. Most of the subjects were recruited in the first two years, but a number left the study throughout the duration and turnover was highest in the first year. Being based in a veterans' home, the study risked men being discharged from the home and 136 and 138 were discharged from the home among the 422 control and 424 experiment subjects in the first year. 20 subjects in each group were re-admitted to the centre during the first year and there were a number of additional withdrawals from the study from subjects remaining in the veterans' home.

There were 24 withdrawals from the control group and 69 withdrawals from the experiment group in the first year. Some withdrawals were involuntary, with subjects being placed on a therapeutic diet for other reasons. The higher number of withdrawals in the experiment group was attributed to two difficulties with the experiment diet: i) some subjects objected to the restriction of eggs and ii) the soya-bean oil was administered in milk (with the butterfat removed and the vegetable oil inserted instead) and some participants found this objectionable.

The pattern of discharges, re-entries and withdrawals continued each year throughout the study. Participants at the start numbered 422 in the control group and 424 in the diet group; participants at the end of the study numbered 169 in the control group and 100 in the diet group (table 17, p.II-17) (Dayton et al., 1969). This was judged to indicate attrition bias.

The article reported "...surveillance for events and deaths was pursued even after withdrawal" (p.II-18) i.e. even after people withdrew from the experiment, their subsequent incidents were still attributed to their group. Twice as many men withdrew from the intervention diet, but incidents were still attributed to that group (Dayton et al., 1969).

The LA Veterans Study was given the most weight (48.91%) in the meta-analysis for dietary intervention and all-cause mortality deaths (Fig. 3.3). It was given the second highest weighting, behind Leren, in the dietary intervention and CHD deaths meta-analysis with a weighting of 19.91%. This weighting does not seem justified based, as it is, on participants at study entry when so many men dropped out of the study throughout its duration.

The study's own conclusion: "Total longevity was not affected favorably in any measurable or significant degree... For this reason, and because of the unresolved question concerning toxicity, we consider our own trial, with or without the support of other published data, to have fallen short of providing a definitive and final answer concerning dietary prevention of heart disease" (p.II-56) (Dayton et al., 1969).

5) The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1968; Leren, 1970)

The study design and participants: The aim of The Oslo Diet Heart Study was to assess "what effect a reduction of the plasma cholesterol concentration by means of diet would have on morbidity and mortality from coronary heart disease (CHD relapses) in male survivors of myocardial infarction" (p.1012) (Leren, 1968).

412 men, aged 30-64, were involved in the study. They had been discharged from hospitals in Oslo between 1956 and 1958 following a first myocardial infarction. There was no mention in the narrative or baseline information of medications being taken. The men were allocated in equal numbers at random to either the diet or the control group within two years of their first heart attack. There was no evidence for allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011). The initial study period was five years long. Information for deaths and incidents was available after 11 years of follow-up, making this one of the longest studies undertaken.

A number of factors were recorded at baseline. Blood pressure (p.939), smoking (p.940) and weight (p.939) were reviewed separately and the two groups were recorded as “about the same” at entry. The discussion noted “In the present study the groups were randomized after accepted statistical principles, and it seems justified to conclude that the two groups were equally at risk at the start of the trial” (p.940) (Leren, 1970).

The dietary intervention and comparison: A diet low in saturated fat and high in polyunsaturated fat was recommended for the intervention group. The diets of 17 men in the experiment group were analysed and presented in the five-year review. Neither the rationale for the selection of this number of men nor the method of selection was given. The mean daily intake for the 17 diets analysed was: 92 g of protein; 104 g of fat; 269 g of carbohydrate and 264 mg of cholesterol. Daily calorie intake was 2,387, with calories from fat comprising 39% of the total. The sources of fat were: soya-bean oil (72%); fish fat (12%), animal fat (9%), cereal fat (5%), and fat from other sources (2%). Of the mean dietary fat, 21.6% was saturated, 25.7% monounsaturated, and 52.7 % polyunsaturated. The control group maintained their normal diet (p.1013) (Leren, 1968).

Adherence to the diet was controlled by a physician and a dietician who worked in the homes of the patients. The degree of adherence was ascertained by means of a detailed questionnaire used six times during the first five years. The questionnaire results rated 62.2% of dieters to be excellent adherents, 22.1% good, 10.3% fair and 5.4% poor. The control group was also monitored with personal contact and questionnaire and also by serum cholesterol levels. The latter remaining relatively unchanged concurred with personal contact and the questionnaires that the control group diet had remained largely unchanged. This process meant that neither participant nor therapist was blinded. The assessment of death was noted as “not carried out blindly with regard to study variables” (p.937) (Leren, 1970).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels for both the control and diet groups at the start of the study were 296 mg/dl. After five years, the mean serum cholesterol levels were 244 mg/dl in the diet group and 285 mg/dl in the control group. The reduction in cholesterol in the diet group was described as significant, but statistical values were not reported.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: Death rates in both groups were high after 11 years, reflecting the length of the study and the age of some men on entry. Total mortality from all causes was approximately half of the men: 101 out of 206 men in the diet group and 108 out of 206 men in the control group. This difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.35$). Total cardiovascular mortality was 79 out of 206 men in the diet group and 94 out of 206 men in the control group ($p = 0.097$).

Study design – Flaws: The study discussion noted that the size of the test groups was too small to be significant for fatal incidences. The summary also noted that CHD mortality was correlated with age, blood pressure, body weight, smoking habits and a combination of these factors. The association with diet alone could not be isolated.

Age information was detailed in the 11 year report. At the start of the study men were not evenly allocated by age. 65% of the men in the diet group were under the age of 60 (35% over 60); 60% of the men in the control group were under the age of 60 (40% over 60). More deaths and coronary incidents would be expected in the control group reflecting this age differential and there were more CHD deaths in the control group ($p = 0.097$). Age was an important factor in this study, as it is in heart disease generally. 48% of men over the age of 60 died from CHD during the study, compared to 39% under the age of 60 at study entry (Leren, 1970).

The study's own conclusion: After five years, the study conclusion was: "The cholesterol-lowering diet reduced the incidence of total CHD relapses. There was a distinct difference in the effect on patients below the age of 60 and those of 60 and over. The difference was highly significant [values not given] in the younger group but not in the older" (p.1020) (Leren, 1968).

The 11-year conclusion was more multi-factorial in approach: "Epidemiological studies have demonstrated several factors associated with the risk of developing first manifestations of coronary heart disease. Blood lipids, blood pressure and cigarette smoking are such risk variables. The present study demonstrates that these factors are of prognostic significance even after a myocardial infarction... In spite of the small numbers this observation lends some support to the view that the multi-factorial

approach is the best way to the solution of the coronary heart disease problem" (p.941) (Leren, 1970).

6) The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978)

The study design and participants: 458 men, aged 30-59, with coronary heart disease took part in a secondary prevention trial for 2 to 7 years. There was no mention in the narrative or baseline information of medications being taken. The study was conceived in 1964 and began in 1966. Woodhill *et al* noted that "at the time there was a strong belief among epidemiologists and medical scientists that the high dietary intake of saturated fats and cholesterol in the Western nations was a major determinant of premature vascular disease, especially angina pectoris and myocardial infarction" (p.318). They further noted that "It had also been established that substitution of polyunsaturated fatty acids for saturated fatty acids in the diet lowered serum cholesterol" (p.318). As the American Heart Association had recommended changes in the American diet to reflect these beliefs, this study sought to submit this hypothesis to a field test.

Following first infarction, the majority of participants had already made changes to their diet, smoking habits and had lost weight. The men were randomly allocated to either Group F – the diet intervention group (221) men or Group P – the control group (237 men). The allocation was done "by random numbers" (p.319) (Woodhill et al., 1978), but it was not clear if this qualified as allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011).

The baseline variables for: age; weight at the time of infarction; weight at the time of study entry; systolic and diastolic blood pressure; serum cholesterol; serum triglyceride; and serum uric acid revealed no difference in entry characteristics (table 1, p.320) (Woodhill et al., 1978). Both groups had reduced mean weight levels from 73kg at entry to 71kg at follow-up.

The study made an important observation: "It is concluded that because of multiple changes in lifestyle, men who have myocardial infarction are not a good choice for testing the lipid hypothesis. Weight loss, reduction in cigarette smoking, increase in physical activity and other readjustments may well have more important beneficial effects than change in dietary lipids" (p.318). The study noted that "what was planned as a test of the lipid hypothesis became a multifactorial study" (p.326) (Woodhill et al., 1978). This is true of every secondary study, as many lifestyle adjustments are made following a heart attack.

The dietary intervention and comparison: The diet group were tutored individually to reduce saturated fat intake to approximately 10% of calories and dietary cholesterol to 300 mg or less per day. They were encouraged to consume foods containing polyunsaturated fats to make this fat 15% or more of daily calories. The control group were given no specific instructions, other than to restrict calories if deemed overweight. They could opt for polyunsaturated margarine instead of butter if they wished.

Adherence to the diet was assessed by interview and/or food diaries analysed three times in the first year and twice yearly thereafter. The dietary data was converted to mean daily nutrient intake on a computer programme and used in subsequent analysis of survival. Blinding for participant and the diet assessor was not possible. There was no information in the journal article about assessor blinding. The study was the first to undertake multivariate computer analyses; an indication of rigour.

The audited outcome was that the diet group consumed 9.8% of daily calories from saturated fat and 15.1% from polyunsaturated fat. The control group consumed 13.5% of daily calories from saturated fat and 8.9% from polyunsaturated fat.

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels on entry to the study were 281 mg/dl and 282 mg/dl for the diet group and control group respectively – remarkably similar. Mean serum cholesterol levels at the five year follow-up were 250 mg/dl and 262 mg/dl for the diet and control groups respectively. This was the first RCT in the systematic review that included standard deviations in mean serum cholesterol levels at study entry and at follow-up. The changes in mean serum cholesterol were not significant at the tested level ($p>0.01$) (table 1 p.320) (Woodhill et al., 1978).

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: There were 67 deaths in total during the follow-up period. 39 occurred in the diet group (F) and 28 of these occurred in the control group (P). 60 of the 67 deaths were from coronary heart disease (3 were from a stroke, 2 from cancer and 2 from road accidents). Truswell took this 60/67 ratio and estimated that 35 deaths occurred from CHD in the intervention group and 25 in the control group (Truswell, 1994). This review adopts the same method.

Study design – Flaws: The study noted that it is "insuperable" to isolate dietary factors in a secondary study. This is a flaw of all secondary studies, not a unique flaw of this study. Woodhill noted that "changes in smoking habit, dietary pattern, body weight, lifestyle and physical activity before and after entry to the trial may well have had a significant effect on prognosis" (p.326) (Woodhill et al., 1978).

The study's own conclusion: "Survival was significantly better in the P [control] Group."
 "It must be concluded that the lipid hypothesis has gained little support from secondary intervention studies" (p.329) (Woodhill et al., 1978).

Fig. 3.2 Methodological quality summary: review authors' judgements about each methodological quality item for each included study (Higgins et al., 2011).

Results: Meta-analysis

Participants and Study Design

The identified RCTs included a total of 739 deaths and 422 deaths from CHD among 2,441 male participants (Table 3.1). All but one trial exclusively studied secondary participants. The LA Veterans Study comprised one fifth secondary subjects and four fifths primary subjects (Dayton et al., 1969).

The mean duration of the six trials was 5.4 ± 3.5 years. The weighted mean (person years by people) was 6.5 ± 1.0 years.

All trials were parallel and randomised, avoiding selection bias (Fig. 3.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). One study reported allocation concealment (Rose, Thomson and Williams,

1965); the remaining five were unclear for this aspect of selection bias. Four were blinded for outcome assessment and thus at low risk of detection bias (Dayton et al., 1969; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Two were open, with no blinding on either side, at high risk of performance and detection bias (Leren, 1970; Woodhill et al., 1978). The LA Veterans Study was reported as double blinded, but the dietary changes were so substantial that this was implausible (egg consumption quantified, vegetable oils added and animal fats restricted (Dayton et al., 1969)). The open enrolment and departure in the veterans institution produced attrition bias (Dayton et al., 1969). All studies were judged low risk for reporting bias, as there was no evidence of any data being withheld (Fig. 3.2).

The meta-analyses for all-cause mortality (Fig. 3.3) and CHD deaths (Fig. 3.4) were tested for sensitivity analysis of the exclusion of any one study. There were no circumstances in which the exclusion of any one study made the overall effect size significant.

Statistical evidence for substantial between study heterogeneity was not found. For all deaths, the Q-value was 5.503 (6 degrees of freedom). I^2 was 0.000 and T^2 was 0.000. For CHD deaths, the Q-value was 6.918 (6 degrees of freedom). I^2 was 13.274 and T^2 was 0.010.

Visual inspection of the funnel plots revealed that none of the studies lay outside the standard error funnel for the meta-analysis of all deaths or CHD deaths (Appendix 3). The two, small, Rose *et al* studies produced asymmetry on the lower right hand side of the funnels (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Egger's regression test confirmed some asymmetry, noting the caution for the small number of studies (Higgins JPT and Green S, 2011). The Egger's regression intercept was 0.725 (95% CI, two-tailed, -0.687 to 2.137) (one-tailed $p = 0.122$; two-tailed $p = 0.244$) for the all deaths meta-analysis and 1.162 (95% CI, two-tailed, -0.443 to 2.767) (one-tailed $p = 0.061$; two-tailed $p = 0.122$) for CHD deaths.

Interventions and Comparisons

Five of the six RCTs did not examine either a total fat consumption of 30%, or a saturated fat consumption of 10%, of energy intake. The trials examined: the administration of vegetable oil (Dayton et al., 1969; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965); the replacement of saturated fats with vegetable oil (Dayton et al., 1969; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968) and an approximate 20% fat diet (Research Committee, 1965). A single RCT examined

the consequence of a 10% saturated fat diet and reported higher incidence of all-cause mortality and CHD deaths in the intervention group (Woodhill et al., 1978).

Outcomes: All-cause mortality

Across 6 studies, containing 7 dietary interventions, involving 1,227 people in the intervention groups and 1,214 people in the control groups, there were 370 deaths in the intervention groups and 369 deaths in the control groups. All-cause mortality was 30.2% in the intervention groups and 30.4% in the control groups.

The mean death rate was high reflecting the fact that, LA Veterans excepted, these were secondary studies. Unsurprisingly death rates were higher in the longer term studies. The lowest death rate was observed in the control group of Rose *et al* (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). This is an important finding in itself. The 1997 Scottish review of 27 risk factors for coronary heart disease and death found that the biggest risk factor for dying from heart disease, for men and women, was having had a previous myocardial infarction (Tunstall-Pedoe et al., 1997). This is now so well known as to be deemed obvious, but the original randomised controlled trials, being secondary studies, proved this now familiar fact.

In the meta-analysis of all-cause mortality, the LA Veterans Study carried the greatest weight, 48.91%, (Fig. 3.3 random effects methodology) (Dayton et al., 1969). The corn and olive oil interventions had negligible impact on the overall effect, with weights of 0.16% and 0.27% respectively (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The risk ratio (RR) for all 7 studies was 0.982 (95% CI, 0.878 to 1.098). The overall effect measurement lies on the line of no effect. There was no statistically significant relationship between dietary interventions and all-cause mortality.

CHD mortality

The 7 interventions recorded 207 deaths from CHD in the intervention groups and 215 in the control groups. The forest plot for the dietary interventions and deaths from CHD, produced the meta-analysis shown in Fig. 3.4 (random effects methodology).

In the meta-analysis of CHD mortality, The Oslo Diet Heart Study carried the greatest weight, 42.30%, (Fig. 3.4 random effects methodology) (Leren, 1970). The corn and olive oil interventions carried the least weight with 0.47% and 0.80% respectively (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The risk ratio (RR) for all 7 studies was 0.951 (95% CI, 0.784 to 1.155). The overall effect measurement lies on the line of no effect.

There was no statistically significant relationship between the dietary interventions and heart deaths.

Significance reported by the studies

Three studies (Dayton et al., 1969; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965) and the olive oil (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965) intervention reported no significant differences in deaths. The corn oil deaths were reported as significantly different, in favour of the control group ($0.1 > p > 0.05$) (p.1,533) (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Leren reported that the difference in all-cause mortality was not statistically significant ($p = 0.35$) (Leren, 1970). Total CHD mortality was 79 out of 206 men in the diet group and 94 out of 206 men in the control group ($p = 0.097$). Woodhill *et al* recorded 39 deaths in the intervention group and 28 in the control group (Woodhill et al., 1978). There were 35 deaths from CHD in the intervention group and 25 in the control group. These were described as significant, but statistical values were not reported.

Serum cholesterol levels

Mean serum cholesterol levels decreased in all groups: control and intervention. The standardised mean difference in serum cholesterol levels, for the six trials (seven interventions) combined, was $-12.6\% \pm 6.7\%$ for the intervention groups and $-6.5\% \pm 5.1\%$ for the control groups (Table 3.1). The effect size was 1.04 (Coe, 2002).

Table 3.1 Outcome data from included trials of diet and events for intervention (Int) and control (Ctrl) groups.

Study	Participants		Intervention		Outcomes		
	Int/Ctrl	Type	Years	Diet	All deaths Int/Ctrl	CHD deaths Int/Ctrl	Change in mean serum cholesterol Int/Ctrl (%)
Corn oil	28/26 * (under 70)	S	2	64 g corn oil/day + many banned foods	5/1 *	5/1 *	-7.6/-1.2
Olive oil (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965)	26/26 * (under 70)	S	2	58 g olive oil/day + many banned foods	3/1 *	3/1 *	-0.4/-1.2
Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965)	123/129 (under 65)	S	3	40 g fat/day	20/24	17/20	-16.9/-12.4
MRC Soybean Oil (Medical Research Council, 1968)	199/194 (under 60)	S	3.4	85 g soya-bean oil/day + many banned foods	28/31	27/25	-16.9/-5.9
The LA Veterans Study (Dayton et al., 1969)	424/422 (age 55+)	P/S	8	40% calories from fat, 2/3 fat from veg oils	174/177	41/50	-18.0/-14.1
The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1970)	206/206 (30-64 yr)	S	11	40% calories from fat, 72% fat from soya-bean oil	101/108	79/94	-17.6/-3.7 (5 yr data)
The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978)	221/237 (30-59 yr)	S	5	10% sat/15% poly vs 14% sat/9% poly	39/28	35/25	-11.0/-7.1
TOTAL	1,227/1,214				370/369	207/215	Mean -12.6/-6.5 S.D. 6.7/5.1

Table notes: * Control not double counted Type: P = Primary study; S = Secondary study

Fig. 3.3 Estimates of total mortality (95% confidence intervals) from meta-analysis.

Fig. 3.4 Estimates of CHD mortality (95% confidence intervals) from meta-analysis.

Discussion

The main findings of the meta-analysis of the six RCTs available at the time of issuing dietary guidelines in the US and UK indicate that all-cause mortality was identical at 30% in the intervention and control groups. There was no statistically significant difference in deaths from CHD. Statistically significant reductions in mean serum cholesterol levels did not result in a reduction in deaths.

It is a widely held view that reductions in cholesterol are healthful *per se*. The original RCTs did not find any relationship between dietary fat intake and deaths from CHD or all-causes, despite significant reductions in cholesterol levels. (All reductions were within the 19% critical difference determined years later by Fraser and Fogarty (Fraser and Fogarty, 1989)). This undermines the role of serum cholesterol levels as an intermediary to the development of CHD and contravenes the theory that reducing dietary fat potentiates a reduction in CHD risk.

An equally important finding was that the RCTs available to the dietary committees in 1977 and 1983 lacked generalisability. The totality of RCT evidence available at the time comprised 2,467 male participants enrolled to 6 studies, 5 of which were secondary prevention studies and 1 included secondary and primary prevention subjects. The exclusion of women also negated the possibility of explaining the paradox of women having higher mean serum cholesterol than men and lower CHD.

Design limitations

There are some important design limitations among the available RCTs. The LA Veterans Study provided meals in a contained environment, but was undermined by open enrolment, allowing participants to leave and join (Dayton et al., 1969). The other five RCTs relied upon dietary advice, with meetings and periodical dietary analysis to monitor adherence. A number of studies impaired assessment of one intervention (administering oils) by adding other dietary restrictions (Dayton et al., 1969; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968).

Woodhill *et al* made an important observation that men who have suffered an MI subsequently make multiple lifestyle changes (weight loss, smoking cessation, increase in physical activity, for example), which makes them a poor group for testing the lipid hypothesis. In this respect, the reporting of cholesterol decreases in control and intervention groups supports the observation that multiple lifestyle changes are made.

Weight changes were not recorded in two studies (Leren, 1970; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Two studies noted no significant weight change in intervention or control groups (Dayton et al., 1969; Medical Research Council, 1968). The Research Committee study reported mean weight loss as 7.5% in the intervention group and 4.8% in the control group (Research Committee, 1965). Woodhill *et al* reported a mean weight loss of 6.5% and 6.0% in the intervention and control groups respectively (Woodhill et al., 1978).

The phytosterol content of vegetable oils could explain reductions in cholesterol levels with no concomitant reductions in deaths (Bresson, 2008; Harcombe and Baker, 2014).

A limitation of the present review and meta-analysis relates to the detailed information in the original studies in order to determine the saturated, monounsaturated and polyunsaturated content of the control and intervention diets. Woodhill *et al* was the single study to detail the composition of the three fats in the intervention and control diet; a 10% saturated fat intake being the intervention goal (Woodhill et al., 1978). Leren documented the intervention diet as 40% of total calories as fat; 8.3% of total calories as saturated fat and a polyunsaturated to saturated fat ratio of 2.4:1 (Leren, 1970). No comparable measures were given for the control diet in this study. Other studies recorded total fat intake as a percentage of calories, but not individual fat composition. Consequently, deductions about the relationship between different fats and serum cholesterol levels cannot be made.

Deductions can be made about the dietary interventions and mortality from all-causes and CHD. The Rose *et al* interventions most notably favour the control in both forest plots, but the wide confidence intervals render these, as with all the studies, non-significant (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965).

Study conclusions

Only one study made a positive claim for its intervention after five years (Leren, 1968) and subsequently this was moderated (Leren, 1970). Rose *et al* warned of possible harm by administering corn oil (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The Research Committee concluded "A low-fat diet has no place in the treatment of myocardial infarction" (p.504) (Research Committee, 1965). The MRC Soya-bean Oil Trial found no evidence that myocardial infarction relapse would be materially affected by unsaturated fat in the diet (Medical Research Council, 1968). The LA Veterans Study reported that total longevity was not affected and expressed concern about unknown

toxicity of their intervention (Dayton et al., 1969). Woodhill *et al* noted that survival was significantly better in the control than the diet group (Woodhill et al., 1978).

From the literature available, it is clear that at the time US and UK dietary advice was introduced, there was no evidence that could be extrapolated to whole populations. The evidence available did not support recommendations and lacked generalisability, even had it been conclusive. 2,467 men had been observed in RCTs. No women had been studied; no pure primary study had been undertaken; no RCT had tested the dietary fat recommendations; no RCT had concluded that dietary guidelines should be introduced. It seems incomprehensible that dietary advice was introduced for 220 million Americans (United States Census Bureau, 1977) and 56 million UK citizens (Office for National Statistics, 2003) given the contrary results from a small number of unhealthy men.

There was best practice, randomised controlled trial evidence available to the dietary committees, which was not considered and should have been. The results of the present meta-analysis support the hypothesis that the available RCTs did not support the introduction of dietary fat recommendations in order to reduce CHD risk or related mortality.

Chapter Four

A systematic review and meta-analysis of the randomised controlled trial evidence currently available to evaluate if the introduced dietary fat guidelines have been supported in retrospect

Introduction

The systematic review and meta-analysis in Chapter Three was the first to examine the RCT evidence available at the time of the introduction of national dietary guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983; Select committee on nutrition and human needs, 1977).

This chapter reports on a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess if the published RCTs available to the dietary committees and those published afterwards, support the recommendations on dietary fat. With this in mind, the hypothesis is that RCT evidence currently available does not support the contention that reducing dietary fat intake would contribute to a reduction in CHD risk or related mortality. The guidelines have not been changed since they were announced; therefore, the validity of their evidence base remains relevant.

Methods

A systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted in accordance with the PRISMA guidelines (Moher et al., 2009) (Appendix 4).

Search strategy

A search was undertaken to identify RCTs that examined the relationship between modified or reduced dietary fat intake, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD and all-causes. Exclusion criteria were: study being observational; non-randomised and/or multi-factorial in design. Inclusion criteria were: randomised dietary intervention studies; study hypothesis relating to a reduction or modification of dietary fat; participants were human adults; study was a minimum of one year in duration; primary study outcome was all-cause and CHD mortality; data on all-cause mortality, CHD mortality and cholesterol measurements were available.

Searches of the literature were performed using MEDLINE, Embase and the Cochrane Library. AMED and SIGLE (grey literature sources) were not relied upon, as their periods covered were not compatible: from 1985 and 1992 respectively (National Institute of Clinical Excellence (NICE), 2014; SIGLE System for Information on Grey

Literature in Europe, Founded 1992) (Fig. 4.1). The search was undertaken in December 2014.

Selection of studies

Of 486 identified articles, 346 were rejected upon review of the title and abstract. Of these, 119 were rejected for being review, discussion or historical articles. 88 were commentaries, editorials or letters. 48 were rejected for having an intervention relating to a particular food or supplement, rather than dietary fat. There were 30 studies where animals or children/adolescents were the primary focus. A further 27 papers considered the design and challenges of dietary interventions, for example examining the difficulties of achieving compliance. 25 were rejected for being surgical and/or pharmacological interventions. 9 related to conditions other than CHD, such as cancer and stress. 140 papers remained. 61 were rejected on closer inspection of the paper for being epidemiological/cohort studies and 39 were rejected for not meeting the inclusion criteria.

The remaining 40 papers covered 11 trials, once duplication was resolved. 10 RCTs met the inclusion criteria: The Rose Corn Oil Trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965); The Research Committee Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965); The MRC Soyabean Oil Trial (Medical Research Council, 1968); The LA Veterans Study (Dayton et al., 1969); The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1968; Leren, 1970); The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978); the dietary fat intervention from The Diet And Reinfarction Trial (DART) (Burr et al., 1989); The Minnesota Coronary Survey (Frantz et al., 1989); The St Thomas' Atherosclerosis Regression Study (STARS) (Watts et al., 1992) and The Women's Health Initiative (WHI) (Howard et al., 2006). Following correspondence, the PREDIMED study was rejected for non-availability of CHD mortality and total cholesterol data (Estruch et al., 2013).

To ascertain the validity of eligible randomised trials, a pair of reviewers (ZH and BD) worked independently to determine which studies met the inclusion criteria. The same 10 were agreed upon. Risk of bias was further assessed using the Cochrane Collaboration assessment tool (Higgins et al., 2011) for: selection bias (random sequence generation, allocation concealment); performance/detection bias (blinding of participants and personnel, blinding of outcome assessment); attrition bias (incomplete data outcome); and reporting bias (selective reporting) (Fig. 4.2). Additionally the meta-analyses for all-cause mortality (Fig. 4.3) and CHD deaths (Fig. 4.4) were tested for sensitivity analysis of the exclusion of any one study.

Data Extraction

Table 4.1, following the systematic review, details data extraction from that systematic review of: study name, duration, year of publication and confirmation of study design; participant characteristics; details of intervention and comparison diet; and outcomes relating to all-cause mortality, CHD related deaths and changes in mean serum cholesterol levels. Where a study contained more than one intervention, both were included (Frantz et al., 1989; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965), which resulted in 12 interventions for review.

The systematic review extracted data in accordance with the PICOS format of the PRISMA methodology: **P**articipants; the dietary **I**ntervention; **C**omparisons between the intervention and control groups; **O**utcomes (cholesterol levels; coronary heart disease deaths and all-cause mortality- as recorded by each study); and **S**tudy design (including flaws and the study's own conclusions) (Moher et al., 2009). Data have also been extracted during the systematic review for the Cochrane Collaboration assessment tool for: selection bias (random sequence generation, allocation concealment); performance/detection bias (blinding of participants and personnel, blinding of outcome assessment); attrition bias (incomplete data outcome); and reporting bias (selective reporting) (Fig. 4.2) (Higgins et al., 2011).

Statistical Analysis

The overall pooled effect was calculated using random effects meta-analysis. Heterogeneity and bias were quantified using the I^2 and T^2 calculations, $I^2 = 100\% \times (Q - df)/Q$, where Q is Cochran's heterogeneity statistic and df the degrees of freedom. Funnel plot methodology and Egger's regression intercept (Egger et al., 1997; Sterne et al., 2011) were calculated. Analyses were performed using Comprehensive Meta-Analysis (Borenstein et al., 2005).

Fig. 4.1 (Moher et al., 2009) Summary of systematic review profile.

Results: Systematic review

The ten clinical trials that met the criteria for systematic review were, in order of publication: 1) The Rose Corn Oil Trial (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965); 2) The Research Committee Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965); 3) The MRC Soyabean Oil Trial (Medical Research Council, 1968); 4) The LA Veterans Study (Dayton and Pearce, 1969; Dayton et al., 1969); 5) The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1968; Leren, 1970); 6) The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978); 7) The Diet and Reinfarction Trial (DART) (Burr et al., 1989); 8) The Minnesota Coronary Survey (Frantz et al., 1989); 9) The St Thomas' Atherosclerosis Regression Study (STARS) (Watts et al., 1992); and 10) The Women's Health Initiative (WHI) (Howard et al., 2006).

The first six trials were reviewed in Chapter Three. The four additional trials, since the time of the introduction of dietary guidelines, are systematically reviewed in the following pages.

7) The Diet And Reinfarction Trial (DART) (Burr et al., 1989)

The study design and participants: The Diet and Reinfarction Trial (DART) was designed to examine the effects of dietary intervention in the secondary prevention of myocardial infarction (MI). 2,033 men under the age of 70 participated in the study. The follow-up took place after two years. The major endpoints were all-cause mortality and ischemic heart deaths (IHD).

The participants were not allocated to one group alone. 2,033 men, who had recovered from an MI, were allocated randomly to receive, or not to receive, advice on each of three dietary factors: 1,018 were given fat advice; 1,015 were given no fat advice. 1,015 were given fish advice; 1,018 were given no fish advice. 1,017 were given fibre advice; 1,016 were given no fibre advice. There were eight different combinations of advice: fat advice alone; fat and fish advice together; fat, fish and fibre advice together; no advice at all; fish advice alone; fish and fibre advice together; fat and fibre advice together; and fibre advice alone. There was no evidence of allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011).

The baseline characteristics were summarised for those receiving fish, fat or fibre advice against those not receiving fish, fat or fibre advice (table I, p.758) (Burr et al., 1989). The characteristics measured were: age; smokers at time of myocardial infarction (MI); history of previous MI; history of angina; history of hypertension; X-ray results

for cardiomegaly, lung congestion and lung oedema; drug treatment for beta-blockers, other anti-hypertensives, anti-angina medications, anti-coagulants, aspirin or anti-arrhythmic tablets. No statistical significance was reported on the data, but visual inspection showed the variables to be similar. The size of study (over 1,000 people allocated to each intervention) would make statistically significant differences at baseline unlikely.

The dietary intervention and comparison: The three dietary interventions were:

- 1) Fat advice – to reduce fat intake to 30% of total energy and to increase the ratio of polyunsaturated to saturated fat to 1.0;
- 2) Fish advice – to increase fatty fish intake to at least two portions weekly (200-400 g) of mackerel, herring, kipper, pilchard, sardine, salmon or trout;
- 3) Fibre advice – to increase intake of cereal fibre to 18 g daily.

Fat advice alone has been included in this systematic review and meta-analysis, as the other two interventions were not dietary fat interventions.

The difference in fat, as a percentage of total energy intake, achieved between the fat advice and no fat advice groups was not large. After six months, the fat advice group averaged 32% fat intake vs. 35% in the no fat advice group. This was maintained at two years. The P/S (polyunsaturated to saturated fat ratio) differed more. This held at 0.78 (the target of 1 was not achieved) at six months and two years for the fat advice group. The P/S ratio was 0.40 for the no fat advice group after six months and 0.44 after two years.

Dieticians visited and telephoned the subjects to ensure adherence to the advice given. At six months and two years the subjects were weighed and a detailed dietary questionnaire was administered. A 25% random sample of participants was asked to weigh and record all food and drink consumed for seven days.

Weight reduction advice was incorporated as required. This had little impact on weight. Overall mean weight rose by 0.6kg during the study (p.760) (Burr et al., 1989).

“All the medical interviews, the decisions regarding diagnosis of reinfarction, and the classifications of death certificates were done by doctors who were unaware of the subjects’ allocation within the trial” (p.758) (Burr et al., 1989).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: Mean cholesterol levels were 6.47 mmol/l at entry for those who went on to receive fat advice and those who didn't. At two years, they were

6.29 mmol/l and 6.55 mmol/l for those receiving fat advice (n = 855) and those not receiving fat advice (n = 860) respectively. High Density Lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol was measured in this study. This was 0.96 and 0.98 mmol/l at entry for those who went on to receive fat advice and those who didn't. After two years, HDL cholesterol was 1.04 mmol/l for those receiving fat advice and 1.05 mmol/l for those not receiving fat advice – higher and equivalent in both groups.

Mean serum cholesterol levels and standard deviations for these were reported at study entry and after two years (table VI, p.760) (Burr et al., 1989). None of the entry or two year data for total cholesterol or HDL for fat advice, compared with no fat advice, was recorded as statistically significant.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: There were 111 deaths (10.9%) from all-causes among those receiving fat advice and 113 deaths (11.1%) from all-causes for those not receiving fat advice. There were 97 deaths (9.5%) from IHD among those receiving fat advice and 97 deaths (9.6%) from IHD for those not receiving fat advice (table III, p.758) (Burr et al., 1989).

The P/S ratio was almost twice as high for the fat advice group as the no fat advice group; deaths were 111 in the fat advice group and 113 in the no fat advice group – not significantly different.

Study design – Flaws: There was a *prima facie* flaw that the fat/fish/fibre groups were not exclusive and thus there were eight possible combinations of these dietary interventions, including a group that received no advice on any of these factors. However, the study reviewed combined interventions and concluded there were no significant interactions between the dietary interventions.

All smokers were strongly advised to stop smoking. However, as Woodhill *et al* noted, this is common to all secondary studies and would have applied to both fat and no fat advice groups (Woodhill et al., 1978).

The study's own conclusion: The study found that there were no significant differences between the groups given advice on fat (p.759) but that "A modest intake of fatty fish (two or three portions per week) may reduce mortality in men who have recovered from MI" (p.757) (Burr et al., 1989).

8) The Minnesota Coronary Survey (Frantz et al., 1989)

The study design and participants: The Minnesota Coronary Survey was a four and a half year open enrolment, single end-time, double-blind, randomised clinical trial,

which was conducted in six Minnesota state mental hospitals and one nursing home. It involved 4,393 institutionalised men and 4,664 institutionalised women. The mean duration of time on the diets was 384 days. There were no age conditions placed and age groups from under 30 to over 70 were well represented.

“The original population was initially stratified into 512 cells on the basis of 8 variables. These were: age, sex, length of stay in hospital, weight, blood pressure, diabetes, cigarette smoking, and evidence by electrocardiogram of a previous myocardial infarction” (p.129). This process ensured that baseline characteristics were not significantly different, but it was judged as unclear for the criteria of allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011).

Despite previous myocardial infarction being documented as a stratification variable, the discussion part of the article reported this as an exclusion criterion: “persons whose initial electrocardiogram showed evidence of a previous myocardial infarction were omitted from the study” (p.134) (Frantz et al., 1989). Hooper *et al* reported the study participants as low risk implying no previous MI (Hooper et al., 2011); Mozaffarian *et al* described the Minnesota subjects as “without CHD” (table 1, p.4) (Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010); Schwingshackl and Hoffman omitted the study in their review of RCTs in the secondary prevention of CHD (Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014); and Truswell described the Minnesota study as a primary study (Truswell, 1994). The study has been judged a primary prevention study on this evidence.

Medications were not detailed, but it would have been likely that participants were taking antipsychotic drugs. The only mention of drugs was in relation to external causes of death (table 7, p.134) (Frantz et al., 1989) where drug reactions were one of many causes of death in this category (fractures, burns, foreign bodies, tooth extraction, freezing, heat stroke, drowning and suicide being the others).

The dietary intervention and comparison: The trial compared the effects of a 39% fat control diet (18% saturated fat, 5% polyunsaturated fat, 16% monounsaturated fat, 446 mg cholesterol per day) with an intervention diet comprising 38% total fat (9% saturated fat, 15% polyunsaturated fat, 14% monounsaturated fat, 166 mg cholesterol per day). The end points captured were the incidence of myocardial infarctions, sudden deaths and all-cause mortality.

Adherence to the diet was facilitated by the participants being institutionalised. Two diets were served in a single queue. As each participant joined the queue, they were given a name label and code and this informed the servers which diet to give them. The

participant did not know which diet had been allocated, “but [it] was easily interpreted by the food servers to determine which diet was to be served” (p.129) (Frantz et al., 1989).

The double-blind was achieved with assessor blinding: “The principal investigator visited each of the institutions at frequent intervals and reviewed under masked conditions the hospital charts, the records kept by the trial technicians, the autopsy reports and the laboratory data on all patients who had died or who had had a suspected cardiovascular event since his last visit” (p.131) (Frantz et al., 1989).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: The mean serum cholesterol level in the pre-admission group was 207 mg/dl. This reduced to 175 mg/dl in the diet group and 203 mg/dl in the control group. There were no standard deviation data for mean serum cholesterol at entry or follow-up.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: There were 2,197 men in the diet group and 2,196 in the control. There were 2,344 women in the diet group and 2,320 in the control.

Within a 2 year period, 158 men in the diet group and 153 men in the control group died from any cause. Within the same period, 111 women in the diet group and 95 women in the control group died from any cause. 62 of these male deaths were from coronary heart disease in the diet group. 54 of these male deaths were from coronary heart disease in the control group. 43 of these female deaths were from coronary heart disease in the diet group. 47 of these female deaths were from coronary heart disease in the control group.

Within a 2 year period, 69 men in the diet group and 74 men in the control group suffered "acute or silent myocardial infarctions and sudden death". Within the same period, 62 women in the diet group and 47 women in the control group suffered "acute or silent myocardial infarctions and sudden death" (table 4, p.132) (Frantz et al., 1989).

The all-cause mortality rate was 7.2% for men in the diet group and 7.0% for men in the control group. The all-cause mortality rate was 4.7% for women in the diet group and 4.1% for women in the control group. The CHD death rate was 2.8% for men in the diet group and 2.5% for men in the control group. The CHD death rate was 1.8% for women in the diet group and 2.0% for women in the control group.

The control group fared better than the diet group for all-cause mortality for men and women and for deaths from CHD for men and CHD incidents for women. The diet

group fared better than the control group for CHD deaths for women and CHD incidents for men. The paper didn't report the significance of the findings in favour of the control group. It reported "this study did not show a statistically significant reduction in cardiovascular events or total deaths from the treatment diet" (p.134) (Frantz et al., 1989).

Study design – Flaws: The study was short – just over one year in length, which is suboptimal for deriving conclusions about a long term condition. The open enrolment was a limitation. The study was also undermined by participants being institutionalised patients with mental illness. The subjects would likely have been taking medications. Psychological distress is associated with increased cardiovascular mortality (Russ et al., 2012) and, while this would have applied to both intervention and control groups, this study also lacked generalisability.

The study's own conclusion: "For the entire study population, no differences between the treatment and control groups were observed for cardiovascular events, cardiovascular deaths or total mortality" (p.129) (Frantz et al., 1989).

9) The St Thomas' Atherosclerosis Regression Study (STARS) (Watts et al., 1992)

The study design and participants: The STARS aimed to assess the effect of dietary reduction of plasma cholesterol concentrations on coronary atherosclerosis. 90 men, below 66 years of age, with coronary heart disease, with a mean plasma cholesterol level of 7.23 mmol/l were randomly assigned to one of three groups: U – usual care; D – dietary intervention; or DC – diet plus cholestyramine. There was no evidence of allocation concealment (Higgins et al., 2011). All participants were tested for tolerance of cholestyramine before allocation.

From the original 90 recruits: 9 withdrew voluntarily for various reasons (3 due to intolerance to cholestyramine, 2 due to neuropsychiatric disturbance, 2 due to emigration and 2 not wanting a second angiogram); 4 died suddenly during the trial; 2 only had 1 angiogram available for analysis and 1 was withdrawn after suffering a minor stroke. This meant that 74 participants completed the study – 24 people in U, 26 people in D and 24 people in DC. The trial duration was 3.25 years. The drug intervention (DC) results have been excluded, from this point onwards, to isolate dietary intervention alone.

There were no significant differences in the participant attributes in the different groups at baseline (table I, p.564 and commentary p.565) (Watts et al., 1992). The

characteristics documented were: age; weight; body mass index; ex-smokers; current smokers; regular alcohol; units of alcohol per week; type A personality; social class I or II; history of hypertension; family history of early CHD; previous myocardial infarction; and angina at entry.

The dietary intervention and comparison: In the diet, total fat intake was reduced to 27% of dietary energy, saturated fat content to 8-10% and dietary cholesterol to 100 mg per 1,000 kcal. Polyunsaturated fat intake was increased to 8% of dietary energy and plant-derived soluble fibre (chiefly pectin) was increased to the equivalent of 3.6 g polygalacturonate per 1,000 kcal.

Patients in the diet group were limited to 1,200 kcal daily until a BMI of 25 was achieved. Further dietetic counselling and suitable foods were given to participants in the diet group who did not achieve or maintain a serum cholesterol reduction of 15%. Hence this was not an intervention with serum cholesterol levels as an outcome.

Patients were assessed at three month intervals to assess and reinforce compliance with treatment. The incident outcome assessment was blinded: “Coding was done by an investigator who was blinded to the therapeutic group” (p.564) (Watts et al., 1992).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: Starting cholesterol levels were 7.07 mmol/l and 7.19 mmol/l in the control and diet groups respectively. During the trial, mean plasma cholesterol levels were 6.93 mmol/l and 6.17 mmol/l in the control and diet groups respectively.

Standard deviations for baseline and in-trial mean serum cholesterol levels were reported (table II, p.565) (Watts et al., 1992). The reduction in mean serum cholesterol level in the control group was not statistically significant ($p = 0.15$). The reduction in mean serum cholesterol level in the diet group was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

The phytosterols in the plant-derived soluble fibre could account for the reduction in cholesterol in the diet group.

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: The baseline patients for each group were reported as 28 (U – control) and 27 (D – diet) (table VI, p.566) (Watts et al., 1992). These baseline numbers have been used in Table 4.1. Of the four deaths, one was in the diet group and three were in the control group. There were two non-fatal myocardial infarctions in the control group and one in the diet group.

Study design – Flaws: The mean age at study entry was 53.9 for the control group and 48.9 for the diet group. The control group started with an age disadvantage. The control

group also had more current smokers: 29.2% vs. 26.9% for the diet group. The control group consumed an average of 15 units of alcohol per week; the diet group consumed an average of 10. These three variations favoured the diet group.

Family history of early CHD varied between the two groups at entry: 45.8% of the control group and 50% of the diet group. Previous MI also differed: 41.7% for the control group and 46.1% for the diet group. These differentials favoured the control group.

There were many dietary interventions and thus the impact of fat, to test the lipid hypothesis, cannot be isolated.

The study was funded by Unilever and Bristol-Myers Ltd.

The study's own conclusion: “These findings support the use of a lipid-lowering diet, and if necessary of appropriate drug treatment, in men with CHD who have even mildly raised serum cholesterol concentrations” (p.563) (Watts et al., 1992).

10) The Women’s Health Initiative (WHI) (Howard et al., 2006)

The study design and participants: The primary study aim was to test the hypothesis that a dietary intervention, intended to be low in fat and high in vegetables, fruits and grains, would reduce breast and colorectal cancer in postmenopausal women, who were consuming 32% or more of their calories as fat at baseline. A secondary aim was to test the hypothesis that the same dietary intervention could reduce cardiovascular risk. 48,835 postmenopausal women aged 50 to 79 years, of diverse backgrounds and ethnicities, were randomly assigned to an intervention (19,541 participants) or control group (29,294) in a free-living setting. Study enrolment occurred between 1993 and 1998 in 40 US clinical centres. The mean follow-up period was 8.1 years.

The allocation process used a “randomized permuted block algorithm with blocks of size 5, 10 or 15 stratified by clinical center site and age group” (p.656) (Howard et al., 2006), judged as meeting requirements for concealment (Higgins et al., 2011).

There were no significant differences in the following baseline characteristics: age group at screening; race/ethnicity; annual family income; body mass index; first-degree relative with premature myocardial infarction; postmenopausal hormone therapy – estrogen alone or estrogen plus progestin; smoking history; hypertension; history of hypercholesterolemia requiring medication; treated for diabetes; history of cardiovascular disease; and the metabolic syndrome (table 1 p.658) (Howard et al., 2006). Significant differences were found in systolic blood pressure (0.4 mm Hg

difference) and a 0.7% difference in use of aspirin (p.659). Taking all characteristics into consideration, there is no evidence that the small and few significant differences impacted the overall outcome.

The dietary intervention and comparison: A food frequency questionnaire confirmed that all women were consuming a baseline diet with fat intake equal to or greater than 32% of total calorie intake. The intervention diet was designed to achieve the goal of reducing total fat to 20% of energy intake by increasing intake of vegetables and fruits to at least five servings daily and grains to at least six servings daily. The intervention did not include total energy reduction or weight loss goals. “Although not a separate focus of the intervention, it was presumed that by reducing total fat intake to 20% kcal, intake of saturated fat would also be reduced (7% energy intake)” (p.656) (Howard et al., 2006).

To ensure dietary adherence for the intervention group, there were 18 group sessions in the first year and quarterly maintenance sessions thereafter led by specially trained and certified nutritionists. Each participant was assigned her own fat-gram goal, calculated on the basis of height. Group activities were supplemented during the trial with individual interviews with targeted messages and personalised advice on fat intake. Women in the control group received a copy of the Dietary Guidelines for Americans, but had no contact with nutritional advisors.

All participants were contacted by clinic staff at six month intervals to provide information on health outcomes. Height; weight; waist circumference and blood pressure were measured at annual visits. Fasting blood samples were collected at baseline and at year 1 from all participants and from a 5.8% (n=2,816) subsample of women at years 3 and 6. All participants completed a food frequency questionnaire (FFQ) at baseline and at 1 year. Thereafter, one third of the participants completed the FFQ each year in a rotating sample. Completion rates were 100% at baseline and 81% thereafter.

The intervention and control group diets were analysed for nutrient intakes at baseline, one year and six years. There were no significant changes in any dietary factor in the control group: energy; total fat saturated fat; monounsaturated fat; polyunsaturated fat; protein; carbohydrate; fibre; dietary cholesterol; fruits and vegetables; or grains. The intervention group reported significant changes in all dietary components, resulting in year 6 in an 8.2% lower mean total fat intake ($p<0.001$) and a 2.9% lower mean saturated fat intake ($p<0.001$), as well as reduced intakes of trans fats, both unsaturated

fats and dietary cholesterol and increased intakes of fibre, fruits and vegetables and grains.

“Outpatient coronary revascularization procedures were reviewed by central physician adjudicators (for CHD death) or trained local adjudicators (for all other coronary end points) all blinded to treatment assignment” (p.657) (Howard et al., 2006).

Outcome – Cholesterol levels: Starting mean cholesterol levels were 224 mg/dl (\pm 36.5) in the diet group and 224.2 mg/dl (\pm 39.2) in the control group. Mean cholesterol levels were measured after 3 years: 214.1 (\pm 35.3) for the diet group and 216.6 (\pm 35.9) for the control group. The mean serum cholesterol values for the diet group reduced by 10.2 (\pm 32.0). The mean serum cholesterol values for the control group reduced by 6.9 (\pm 31.9). The difference between these reductions, 3.26, was reported as significant ($p < 0.05$) from a 2-sample test. This was the only figure reported as significant (table 2 p.659) (Howard et al., 2006).

Outcome – CHD deaths and all-cause mortality: There were 950 deaths from any cause in the diet population (19,541) and 1,454 deaths from any cause in the control group (29,294) (fig. 1, p.656) (Howard et al., 2006) This represented a death rate of 4.86% for the diet group and 4.96% for the control group in the 8.1 year follow-up period.

There were 158 deaths from CHD in the diet population (19,541) and 234 deaths from CHD in the control group (29,294) (table 4, p.661) (Howard et al., 2006). This represented a death rate of 0.8% for both groups in the 8.1 year follow-up period.

Study design – Flaws: The size of the study was a strength. The participants were almost perfectly matched for possible baseline confounders: age; ethnicity; BMI; education smoking and other health history factors. The single gender was a weakness, although this provided balance to data for men provided by other studies. The focus on post menopausal women, and the exclusion of women already consuming dietary fat below 32% of total calorie intake, further reduced the study’s generalisability to the whole population. Participants were additionally invited to receive hormone therapy and participation in a calcium/vitamin D supplement trial was offered after one year. This study was the only RCT that included cholesterol-lowering medication, which was taken by 12% of participants in both the intervention and control groups

The study described its own limitations as: i) the lack of targeting key nutrients relevant to CVD; and ii) the focus on women aged 50 to 79 and the possibility that effects may have been greater on men and/or younger people. Total fat intake and saturated fat

intake were the key nutrient targets introduced with government dietary guidelines and thus this large and long-term study did examine the key nutrients held to be relevant to CVD.

The acknowledged limitations of food frequency questionnaires apply to this study as with other dietary studies (Archer, Pavea and Lavie, 2015; Beaton et al., 1983; Cook, Pryer and Shetty, 2000; Kipnis et al., 2001; Willett WC, 2000).

The study's own conclusion: The intervention achieved an 8.2% energy decrease in total fat intake and a 2.9% energy decrease in saturated fat intake, but did not reduce risk of CHD or stroke.

Fig. 4.2 Methodological quality summary: review authors' judgements about each methodological quality item for each included study (Higgins et al., 2011).

Results: Meta-analysis

Participants and Study Design

The 10 identified RCTs included a total of 3,888 deaths from all-causes and 1,218 deaths from CHD among 62,421 participants (Table 4.1). The most recent trial, the Women's Health Initiative (WHI), dominated the data pool with 78% of the participants, but the results remained non-significant with the exclusion of this study (Howard et al., 2006). Excluding this study leaves 13,586 participants and results in a risk ratio (RR) for all-cause mortality from meta-analysis of 1.005 (95% CI 0.922 to 1.097) and a risk ratio (RR) for CHD mortality from meta-analysis of 0.962 (95% CI 0.850 to 1.089) (both random effects methodology).

The WHI was a primary and secondary trial for women only. The Minnesota Coronary Survey was a primary study, with data for men and women reported separately (Frantz et al., 1989). The LA Veterans Study comprised one fifth secondary subjects and four fifths primary subjects (Dayton et al., 1969). The remaining studies were secondary studies with exclusively male participants.

The mean duration of the ten trials was 4.7 ± 3.3 years. The weighted mean duration (person years by participants) was 6.8 ± 2 years.

All trials were parallel and randomised, avoiding selection bias (Fig. 4.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). Two studies reported allocation concealment (Howard et al., 2006; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965); the remaining eight were unclear for this aspect of selection bias. Eight were blinded for outcome assessment and thus at low risk of detection bias (Burr et al., 1989; Dayton et al., 1969; Frantz et al., 1989; Howard et al., 2006; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Watts et al., 1992). Two were open, with no, or unclear, blinding on either side, at high risk of performance and detection bias (Leren, 1970; Woodhill et al., 1978). The LA Veterans study was reported as double blinded, but the dietary changes were so substantial that this was implausible (egg consumption quantified, vegetable oils added and animal fats restricted) (Dayton et al., 1969). The Minnesota Coronary Survey was reported as double blinded and this was plausible given the dietary intervention (Frantz et al., 1989). The open enrolment and departure in the veterans and Minnesota institutions (Dayton et al., 1969; Frantz et al., 1989) and the early termination of the Rose *et al* study (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965) produced attrition bias. The STARS was judged unclear for attrition bias for the relatively high number of drop-outs in small participant numbers (Watts et al., 1992). All studies were

judged low risk for reporting bias, as there was no evidence of any data being withheld (Fig. 4.2).

The meta-analyses for all-cause mortality (Fig. 4.3) and CHD deaths (Fig. 4.4) were tested for sensitivity analysis of the exclusion of any one study. There were no circumstances in which the exclusion of any one study made the overall effect size significant.

There was little evidence for between study heterogeneity. For all deaths, the Q-value was 7.915 (11 *df*), but this was not statistically significant ($p = 0.721$). I^2 was 0.000 and T^2 was 0.000 indicating no difference in true effects. For CHD deaths, the Q-value was 9.173 (11 *df*), but this was also not statistically significant ($p = 0.606$). I^2 was 0.000 and T^2 was 0.000.

Visual inspection of the funnel plots revealed that one study was touching the outside of the standard error funnel for the meta-analysis of all deaths and CHD deaths (Appendix 5). The two, small, oil interventions (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965) produced asymmetry on the lower right hand side of the funnel, which was countered by The STARS, also small, on the lower left hand side (Watts et al., 1992). The Egger's regression test indicated no statistically significant asymmetry for all-cause mortality and CHD deaths. The Egger's regression intercept was 0.337 (95% CI, two-tailed, -0.489 to 1.163) (one-tailed $p = 0.192$; two-tailed $p = 0.384$) for all-cause mortality and 0.380 (95% CI, two-tailed, -0.756 to 1.517) (one-tailed $p = 0.237$; two-tailed $p = 0.473$) for CHD deaths.

Interventions and Comparisons

Six of the ten RCTs did not examine either of the introduced dietary guidelines: a total fat consumption of 30%, or a saturated fat consumption of 10%, of energy intake (Dayton et al., 1969; Howard et al., 2006; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Four trials examined the administration of vegetable oil (Dayton et al., 1969; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965), to effect reduced intake of animal fat. Two RCTs studied an approximate 20% fat diet (Howard et al., 2006; Research Committee, 1965). Two reviewed the consequence of a 10% saturated fat diet, without the total fat dietary guideline restriction (Frantz et al., 1989; Woodhill et al., 1978). Woodhill *et al* reported higher incidence of all-cause mortality and CHD deaths in the intervention group. Frantz *et al* recorded no difference in all-cause mortality or CHD deaths. The DART tested a 30% total fat diet, although this was not a controlled

variable, as the intervention also tried to achieve a 1:1 polyunsaturated to saturated fat ratio (Burr et al., 1989). The STARS was the first to examine targets approximating to those set by dietary guidelines with a total fat consumption of 27% and an 8-10% saturated fat intake (Watts et al., 1992).

Outcomes: All-cause mortality

Across 10 studies, containing 12 dietary interventions, involving 26,354 participants in the intervention groups and 36,067 participants in the control groups, there were 1,701 deaths in the intervention and 2,187 deaths in the control groups respectively. All-cause mortality was 6.45% in the intervention groups and 6.06% in the control groups.

For all-cause mortality, the WHI carried the greatest weight, 54.35%, (Fig. 4.3 random effects methodology) (Howard et al., 2006). Three studies, comprising four interventions, carried a combined weight of 35% (Dayton et al., 1969; Frantz et al., 1989; Leren, 1970). The Rose *et al* corn and olive oil interventions had negligible impact on the overall effect, with weights of 0.04% and 0.07% respectively (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965), as did The STARS with a weight of 0.07% (Watts et al., 1992). The risk ratio (RR) for all 12 interventions was 0.991 (95% CI, 0.935 to 1.051). The overall effect measurement lies on the line of no effect. There was no statistically significant difference between dietary interventions and all-cause mortality.

CHD mortality

The 12 interventions recorded 568 deaths from CHD among 26,354 participants in the intervention groups and 650 deaths from CHD among 36,067 participants in the control groups. The death rates for CHD mortality were 2.16% and 1.80% in the intervention and control groups respectively. The forest plot for the dietary interventions and deaths from CHD, produced the meta-analysis shown in Fig. 4.4 (random effects methodology).

For CHD mortality, the WHI study carried the greatest weight, 27.59%, (Fig. 4.4 random effects methodology) (Howard et al., 2006). The Oslo study (Leren, 1970) was comparable with a weight of 21.36% and The DART (Burr et al., 1989) contributed 15.56% to the weighting. The Rose *et al* corn and olive oil interventions had negligible impact on the overall effect, with weights of 0.14% and 0.24% respectively (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965), as did The STARS with a weight of 0.23% (Watts et al., 1992). The risk ratio (RR) for all 12 interventions was 0.976 (95% CI, 0.878 to 1.084).

The overall effect measurement lies on the line of no effect. There was no statistically significant difference between the dietary interventions and heart deaths.

Significance reported by the studies

Eight interventions reported no significant differences in all-cause or CHD mortality (Burr et al., 1989; Dayton et al., 1969; Frantz et al., 1989; Howard et al., 2006; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The corn oil deaths, all from CHD, were reported as significantly different, in favour of the control group ($0.1 > p > 0.05$) (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). Woodhill *et al* reported the difference in all-cause mortality as significant, in favour of the control group, but this was not endorsed by statistical analysis (Woodhill et al., 1978). The STARS, with 28 and 27 participants in the control and diet-alone intervention groups respectively, concluded that the outcome supported the administration of a lipid-lowering diet (Watts et al., 1992). However, Fisher's exact test (2 tailed) of deaths vs. survival for the control vs. intervention groups produced a non significant ($p = 0.611$) result.

Serum cholesterol levels

Mean serum cholesterol levels decreased in all groups, control and intervention, except for The DART, where cholesterol levels were 1.2% higher in the control group after two years (Burr et al., 1989). This was unlikely to be clinically relevant; none of the reductions in mean serum cholesterol levels exceeded the critical difference of 19%, calculated by Fraser and Fogarty, as the requirement for significance ($p < 0.05$) (Fraser and Fogarty, 1989).

Three studies alone reported standard deviations and significance for the start and end-of-study mean serum cholesterol levels (Burr et al., 1989; Watts et al., 1992; Woodhill et al., 1978). The one figure reported as statistically significant was the 14% reduction in mean serum cholesterol levels in the intervention group in STARS ($p < 0.001$). (Watts et al., 1992). The eight-year WHI study reported the reductions in mean serum cholesterol levels in the intervention and control groups as 10.2 ± 32.0 mg/dl and 6.9 ± 31.9 mg/dl respectively and reported the difference between the reductions, 3.26 mg/dl, as significant at $p < 0.05$ from a 2-sample test (Howard et al., 2006).

The standardised mean difference in serum cholesterol levels, for the 10 trials (12 interventions) combined, was $-11.4\% \pm 6.5\%$ for the intervention groups and $-4.7\% \pm 4.8\%$ for the control groups (Table 4.1). The effect size was 1.18 (Coe, 2002).

Table 4.1 Outcome data from included trials of diet and events for intervention (Int) and control (Ctrl) groups.

Study	Participants		Intervention		Outcomes		
	Int/Ctrl	Type	Years	Diet	All deaths Int/Ctrl	CHD deaths Int/Ctrl	Change in mean serum cholesterol Int/Ctrl (%)
Corn oil	28/26 * (M under 70)	S	2	64 g corn oil/day + many banned foods	5/1 *	5/1 *	-7.6/-1.2
Olive oil (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965)	26/26 * (M under 70)	S	2	58 g olive oil/day + many banned foods	3/1 *	3/1 *	-0.4/-1.2
Low-fat Diet (Research Committee, 1965)	123/129 (M under 65)	S	3	40 g fat/day	20/24	17/20	-16.9/-12.4
MRC Soybean Oil (Medical Research Council, 1968)	199/194 (M under 60)	S	3.4	85 g soya-bean oil/day + many banned foods	28/31	27/25	-16.9/-5.9
The LA Veterans Study (Dayton et al., 1969)	424/422 (M age 55+)	P/S	8	40% calories from fat, 2/3 fat from veg oils	174/177	41/50	-18.0/-14.1
The Oslo Diet Heart Study (Leren, 1970)	206/206 (M 30-64 yr)	S	11	40% calories from fat, 72% fat from soya-bean oil	101/108	79/94	-17.6/-3.7 (5 yr data)
The Sydney Diet Heart Study (Woodhill et al., 1978)	221/237 (M 30-59 yr)	S	5	10% sat/15% poly vs 14% sat/9% poly	39/28	35/25	-11.0/-7.1
DART Fat advice (Burr et al., 1989)	1,018/1,015 (M under 70)	S	2	Total fat 30% P/S = 1	111/113	97/97	-2.8/+1.2

Study	Participants	Intervention			Outcomes		
	Int/Ctrl	Type	Years	Diet	All deaths Int/Ctrl	CHD deaths Int/Ctrl	Change in mean serum cholesterol Int/Ctrl (%)
Minnesota Coronary Survey: Men Women (Frantz et al., 1989)	(all ages) 2,197/2,196 M 2,344/2,320 W	P	1	Ctrl: 39% calcs fat (18% sat; 5% poly; 16% mono) Int: 38% calcs fat (9% sat; 15% poly; 14% mono)	158/153 111/95	62/54 43/47	Cholesterol not reported separately for men/women -15.5/-1.9
STARS (Watts et al., 1992)	27/28 (M under 66)	S	3.25	27% calcs fat (8-10% sat; 8% poly)	1/3	1/3	-14.0/-1.8
WHI (Howard et al., 2006)	19,541/29,294 (W 50-79 yr)	P/S	8.1	20% calcs fat; 7% calcs sat fat	950/1,454	158/234	-4.4/-3.4 (3 yr data)
TOTAL	26,354/36,067				1,701/2,187	568/650	Mean -11.4%/-4.7% S.D. 6.5/4.8

Table notes:

* Control not double counted

In "Int/Ctrl": M = Men; W = Women.

In "Type": P = Primary prevention study; S = Secondary prevention study

In "Diet": P/S = Polyunsaturated: Saturated fat ratio. Cals = Calories.

Fig. 4.3 Estimates of total mortality (95% confidence intervals) from meta-analysis.

Fig. 4.4 Estimates of CHD mortality (95% confidence intervals) from meta-analysis.

Discussion

The main findings of this systematic review and meta-analysis are that currently available RCT evidence does not support the current dietary fat guidelines. RCT evidence indicates that dietary modification may reduce serum cholesterol to a marginally greater extent in intervention groups, compared with controls. However, this reduction in serum cholesterol does not appear to translate into an improved survival from all-causes or CHD.

Design limitations

One of the most important findings of Chapter Three was that the RCTs available to the dietary committees in 1977 and 1983 lacked generalisability. The totality of RCT evidence available at the time comprised 2,467 male participants enrolled to 6 studies, 5 of which were secondary prevention studies and 1 included secondary and primary prevention subjects. This confinement of RCT studies to men of either advancing age and/or with existing coronary disease restricted the generalisability of RCT study data at the point of introduction of dietary guidelines.

This fundamental design limitation of generalisability has not been rectified with studies currently available. Only one RCT has been undertaken involving men and women without previous heart disease (Frantz et al., 1989). All other RCTs have been single-sex and/or secondary prevention studies. The single primary study of men and women found no significant difference in all-cause or CHD mortality. It also suffered from a number of limitations: open enrolment; short duration (one year); and the participants being institutionalised patients with mental illness. Psychological distress is associated with increased cardiovascular mortality (Russ et al., 2012) and, while this would have applied to both intervention and control groups, this study also lacked generalisability.

With the fundamental caveat of all RCTs lacking generalisability for public health advice, there were some additional design limitations among the secondary/single-sex RCTs, which may confound interpretation. A number of studies impaired assessment of the primary dietary intervention by adding other dietary restrictions (Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Watts et al., 1992). The low-fat diet resulted in the calorie intake in the intervention group ranging between 330 and 780 calories fewer than that of the control group (Research Committee, 1965). At the largest differential, observed after four years of the study, the diet group was consuming 70% of the calorie intake of the control group. This study reported mean weight loss as 7.5% in the intervention group and 4.8% in the control

group. This may have favoured the intervention outcomes. The STARS may also have favoured the diet group by restricting participants to 1,200 kcal daily until a BMI of 25 was achieved (Watts et al., 1992). Further dietetic counseling and suitable foods were given to participants in the intervention group who did not achieve or maintain serum cholesterol reductions of 15%, making serum cholesterol levels a target, not an outcome.

The LA Veterans study provided meals in a contained environment, but was undermined by open enrolment, allowing participants to leave and join (Dayton et al., 1969). The Minnesota Coronary Survey was performed in a controlled environment, enabling diets with the same total fat intake, but different fat compositions, to be administered blind to the participants but not to the servers (Frantz et al., 1989). The other eight RCTs relied upon dietary advice, with meetings and periodical dietary analysis to monitor adherence.

The LA Veterans study recorded the lowest risk ratio for CHD deaths for the diet group: 0.816 (95% CI, 0.552 to 1.206) (Dayton et al., 1969) (Fig. 4.4). However, there were important differences in the groups at study entry, favouring the diet group: 2.8% of the diet group were octogenarians, compared with 5% in the control group; 11% of the diet group were heavy smokers (more than one pack a day) compared with 17% of the control group.

The degree of baseline CHD was not detailed and this would have had significant impact on the risk of CHD during each study. Three studies included men with previous myocardial infarction, or the diagnosis of angina (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Watts et al., 1992; Woodhill et al., 1978). Two studies included primary and secondary subjects (Dayton et al., 1969; Howard et al., 2006) and one was a primary study (Frantz et al., 1989). The remaining four studies described participants as having been hospitalised following a myocardial infarction (Burr et al., 1989; Leren, 1970; Medical Research Council, 1968; Research Committee, 1965). Without knowing the degree of baseline CHD, it cannot be known if risk were equally distributed between diet and control groups. This was a greater limitation for smaller studies and a further limitation for the generalisability of all studies.

Two of the studies were small, although meta-analysis weights this accordingly (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Watts et al., 1992). Leren benefited from trial length, but the study discussion noted that the test groups were too small to be significant for fatal incidences (Leren, 1970). The summary also reported that CHD mortality was

correlated with age, blood pressure, body weight, smoking habits and a combination of these factors, meaning that the association with diet alone could not be isolated.

The WHI study was of substantial size and duration, but with a number of confounding variables (Howard et al., 2006). It was limited in its focus on post menopausal women, aged between 50 and 79, and who were not already consuming dietary fat below 32% of total calorie intake. Participants were additionally invited to receive hormone therapy and participation in a calcium/vitamin D supplement trial was offered after one year. This study alone included cholesterol-lowering medication, which was taken by 12% of participants in both the intervention and control groups.

A limitation of the meta-analysis of the ten studies combined was that all RCTs differed in: duration; number of participants; nature of intervention; other factors held constant and subject age groups, undermining possible conclusions, although the statistical homogeneity helps to mitigate concerns.

Study conclusions

Only one of the ten RCTs presented a case for dietary guidelines. The STARS claimed that its findings supported the use of a lipid-lowering diet in men with CHD (Watts et al., 1992). The five year review of the Oslo Diet Heart Study concluded that the cholesterol-lowering diet reduced the incidence of total CHD relapses (Leren, 1968). The conclusion after 11 years was more reserved: that sudden death in survivors of myocardial infarction was uninfluenced by diet (Leren, 1970).

Four studies were neutral in their findings (Burr et al., 1989; Frantz et al., 1989; Howard et al., 2006; Medical Research Council, 1968). The MRC study found no evidence from the London trial that the relapse-rate in myocardial infarction is materially affected by the unsaturated fat content of the diet (Medical Research Council, 1968). The DART made no claim for dietary fat reductions, but concluded that two to three portions of fatty fish each week may reduce mortality in men who have recovered from a myocardial infarction (Burr et al., 1989). The Minnesota Coronary Survey found no differences between the treatment and control groups for cardiovascular events, cardiovascular deaths or total mortality (Frantz et al., 1989). The WHI intervention reported that an 8.2% energy decrease in total fat intake had been achieved and a 2.9% energy decrease in saturated fat intake, but that this did not reduce risk of CHD (Howard et al., 2006).

The other four studies issued cautions about the safety and/or efficacy of their interventions (Dayton et al., 1969; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Woodhill et al., 1978). Rose *et al* reported that corn oil was most unlikely to be beneficial, and was possibly harmful (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The Research Committee Low-fat Diet concluded that a low-fat diet has no place in the treatment of myocardial infarction (Research Committee, 1965). Dayton *et al* noted the absence of any benefit for longevity and expressed concern about toxicity of the intervention (Dayton et al., 1969). Woodhill *et al* reported that survival was significantly better in the control than the diet group (Woodhill et al., 1978).

This meta-analysis of ten RCTs, in comparison with Harcombe *et al's* review of six RCTs (Harcombe et al., 2015), increased the number of people studied from 2,467 to 62,447. It increased the number of women studied from 0 to 53,499, the majority. It increased the number of primary prevention subjects from 676 (Dayton et al., 1969) to 56,291. However, 83% of the primary prevention subjects were post menopausal women, so the concern about generalisability remains for guidelines introduced for whole populations.

Of 12 interventions, 2 tested the total fat recommendation (Burr et al., 1989; Watts et al., 1992) and 4 tested the saturated fat recommendation (Frantz et al., 1989; Watts et al., 1992; Woodhill et al., 1978). None supported a case for either guideline. Although studies since the introduction of dietary fat recommendations have increased the numbers and diversity of people studied, findings have remained non significant and the proportion of the general population studied remains insignificant.

Other meta-analyses of RCTs

This finding is supported by other meta-analyses of RCTs. Hooper *et al* (Hooper et al., 2011) included RCTs: under one year in duration; with primary outcomes other than heart disease; without CHD/total cholesterol data and/or with confounding interventions (medication (Sondergaard, Moller and Egstrup, 2003), multiple lifestyle changes (Appel et al., 2003)) and reported the risk ratios for all-cause mortality as: 1.02 (95% CI, 0.88 to 1.18) for modified fat intake; 0.97 (95% CI, 0.90 to 1.04) for reduced fat intake; 0.97 (95% CI, 0.76 to 1.23) for reduced or modified fat intake; and 0.98 (95% CI, 0.93 to 1.04) for all included interventions. In the studies where cardiovascular mortality was available, Hooper *et al* similarly found no significant differences as a result of reduced fat and/or modified fat dietary interventions.

Mozaffarian *et al* reported evidence that consuming polyunsaturated fats in place of saturated fats reduced CHD events, not mortality, in RCTs (Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010). This review was criticised (Ravnskov *et al.*, 2014) for excluding two unfavourable trials (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Woodhill *et al.*, 1978) and for including the non-randomised, cross-over trial (Miettinen *et al.*, 1983; Turpeinen *et al.*, 1979) excluded by all other reviews.

Schwingshackl and Hoffmann examined RCTs that reduced or modified dietary fat with regard to all-cause mortality, CVD mortality and CVD events, in participants with established CHD. They concluded that “there was no evidence for the beneficial effects of reduced/modified fat diets in the secondary prevention of coronary heart disease. Recommending higher intakes of polyunsaturated fatty acids in replacement of saturated fatty acids was not associated with risk reduction” (p.1) (Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014).

The results of the present meta-analysis support the hypothesis that the available RCT did not support the introduction of dietary fat recommendations in order to reduce CHD risk or related mortality.

Chapter Five

A systematic review of the epidemiological evidence available at the time of the introduction of dietary fat recommendations

Introduction

Chapters Three and Four respectively reviewed the randomised controlled trial (RCT) evidence available at the time dietary fat guidelines were introduced and currently available. This chapter will report on a systematic review to assess if the published epidemiological evidence available to the dietary committees supported their recommendations on dietary fat.

While the UK nutritional guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) made reference to epidemiological studies, the US committee document (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) did not. The UK guidelines referenced the Seven countries Study (Keys, 1980). The UK document also referenced studies in Framingham, Hawaii/Honolulu, London and Puerto Rico (Gordon et al., 1981; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Yano et al., 1978).

In this chapter, the hypothesis that the epidemiological evidence available to the US and UK committees endorsed their recommendations to reduce dietary fat intake to 30% of total calories and saturated fat intake to 10% of total calories, with the intention of reducing CHD mortality, will be tested.

Methods

Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) is the Cochrane methodology for systematic review and meta-analysis of randomised controlled trials (RCTs) (Moher et al., 2009). The best-practice methodology for systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies is Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology methodology (MOOSE) (Stroup et al., 2000) (Appendix 6). MOOSE is the methodology used in this chapter. MOOSE builds upon the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) methodology and uses parts of PRISMA as appropriate, for example the figure for presenting search methodology (Moher et al., 2009).

Within PRISMA, the advised methodology for extracting data from individual RCTs is PICOS: Participants; Intervention; Comparison; Outcomes and Study information (design, strengths, limitations etc). MOOSE does not offer an equivalent or alternative.

The author of this thesis has developed a PICOS alternative for observational studies: TOPMOS: Type of observational study; Objectives (of the study); Participants/Populations; Methodology; Outcomes and Study information (design, strengths, limitations etc). The systematic review extracts information for each observational study in this format.

Associations established

The review of the literature, Chapter Two, documented where cross-sectional studies had established associations between the component parts of the diet-heart hypothesis. This is summarised below:

Dietary fat and cholesterol

Following observational studies of men in Minnesota (Keys et al., 1950b), Naples (Keys et al., 1954a), Slough (Keys and Keys, 1954) and Madrid (Keys et al., 1954b), Keys concluded that the total fat content of the diet (as a proportion of calories) exerted a powerful influence on the serum cholesterol level in man (Keys et al., 1954a). Age appeared to be a confounder, with cholesterol rising to the age of 50-55 in Minnesotan men, Slough men and rich men in Madrid. Neapolitan men and poor men in Madrid demonstrated stable and falling cholesterol levels respectively between the ages of 40 and 50; rising before these ages.

Cholesterol and CHD

Evidence was found for a relationship between serum cholesterol and CHD (Gertler, Garn and Lerman, 1950; Keys, 1956; Steiner, Kendall and Mathers, 1952) although age was again a confounding variable (Keys et al., 1950b; Morrison, Hall and Chaney, 1948). When middle-aged men were studied, removing age as a confounder, Keys reported that 1) populations with relatively high serum cholesterol averages for middle-aged men (220 mg/dl or more) exhibited a relatively high incidence of CHD and 2) populations with low serum cholesterol averages for middle-aged men (less than 200 mg/dl) exhibited relatively little CHD (p.365) (Keys, 1956). References for (1) were given as men in many parts of the United States (Keys, 1952b), in London (Keys and Keys, 1954), in upper-class men in Madrid (Keys et al., 1954b), Europeans in Cape Town, South Africa (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955), among others. References for (2) were given as southern Italy (Keys et al., 1954a), poor men in Madrid (Keys et al., 1954b), Bantu in Johannesburg and Cape Town (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955; Higginson and Pepler, 1954; Walker and Arvidsson, 1954).

Dietary fat and CHD

The primary cross-sectional analysis undertaken for this part of the diet-heart hypothesis was the graph of men aged 55-59 in six countries presented at the Mount Sinai hospital in New York, which showed a relationship between total fat as a proportion of diet and deaths from heart disease (Keys, 1953a).

The cross-sectional study of three different ethnic groups in Cape Town connected the three elements of the diet-heart hypothesis: dietary fat intake, serum cholesterol levels and CHD (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955). This article established an association with total fat and CHD; saturated fat was not mentioned.

Cross-sectional studies cannot determine cause and effect and the associations derived from these have been documented in the review of the literature. For this reason, and to adhere to best practice evidence available, this chapter is focused on prospective cohort studies (Song and Chung, 2010).

Search strategy

A search was undertaken to identify prospective cohort studies that examined the relationship between dietary fat intake, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD. Exclusion criteria were: clinical trials; cross-sectional studies; case control studies. Inclusion criteria were: prospective cohort studies; participants were human adults; primary study outcome was CHD mortality; data related to dietary fat consumption were available; data on CHD mortality and serum cholesterol measurements were available.

The period searched was up to 5th September 1983, as this was the date of the UK dietary guideline committee publication (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983). In practical terms, the UK publication would have been in preparation, review and print for some weeks or months before this date. However, the search found that no relevant observational studies were published in 1983, giving confidence that available studies could have been considered. The US dietary guidelines were first issued in February 1977 and so publications before and after this date were separated to clarify which evidence was available to each committee (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977).

Searches of the literature were performed using MEDLINE, Embase and the Cochrane Library. AMED and SIGLE (grey literature sources) were not relied upon, as their periods covered were not compatible: from 1985 and 1992 respectively (National

Institute of Clinical Excellence (NICE), 2014; SIGLE System for Information on Grey Literature in Europe, Founded 1992) (Fig. 5.1) The search was undertaken in July 2015.

Selection of studies

Of 285 identified articles, 253 were rejected upon review of the title and abstract. Of these, 52 were rejected for being review articles. 54 were commentaries, editorials or letters. 29 were clinical trials, 11 were not observational studies. 28 related to conditions other than heart disease, primarily cancer, diabetes, hypertension and pregnancy. There were 14 studies where animals or children/adolescents were the primary focus. 26 were articles about pharmacology/blood analysis. 22 were rejected for being related to a particular food or supplement, rather than dietary fat. A further 12 papers were educational material and 5 reviewed dietary compliance in nutritional studies. 32 papers remained. 18 were rejected on closer inspection of the full paper: 9 were reviews, commentaries or expert opinion pieces; 4 were cross sectional/cluster observation studies; 3 were papers on the same study which had no endpoint data; 1 was educational material and the final 1 was a study of blood clotting. 14 met the inclusion criteria. No case control studies or retrospective cohort studies were found, so no data were lost with the inclusion criteria of prospective cohort studies. Where an abstract was unavailable, the publication type, journal name and meta-tags were reviewed to assess if the article should be rejected (for example “letter”, “clinical trial”, “paediatric”). Copies of the remaining articles were obtained from university libraries or the British Library.

Once duplication was removed, the remaining 14 papers produced 4 articles documenting 6 studies (Gordon et al., 1981; Keys, 1970a; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Shekelle et al., 1981). The four articles were hand searched for references to the earliest available publications. The six studies were: The Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963; Shekelle et al., 1981); The Puerto Rico Heart Health Program (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1977; Gordon et al., 1981); The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a); The Framingham Heart Study (Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970); The Honolulu Heart Program (Gordon et al., 1981; Kagan et al., 1974; Yano et al., 1978); and a study conducted in London and the South East (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

To ascertain the validity of eligible observational studies, a pair of reviewers (ZH and BD) worked independently to determine which studies met the inclusion criteria. The same six were agreed upon. Risk of bias was further assessed using the Cochrane Collaboration assessment tool for component parts relevant to observational studies,

defined as follows: selection bias (cohort appropriately reflected wider population characteristics); detection bias (blinding of outcome assessment); attrition bias (incomplete data outcome); and reporting bias (selective reporting) (Higgins et al., 2011) (Fig. 5.2).

Data Extraction

Table 5.2, following the systematic review, details data extraction from that systematic review of: study name; year of key publications; participant characteristics; whether free from CHD at study entry; years of follow-up; outcomes related to mean serum cholesterol, total dietary fat and saturated dietary fat for those who developed/died from CHD and those who didn't.

The process of data extraction revealed some gaps. The Western Electric Study was the only study with complete data for serum cholesterol, total fat and saturated fat in the form in which the development of CHD could be contrasted with those who remained CHD-free (Paul et al., 1963). These data were not available for CHD mortality. The Seven Countries Study reported correlation coefficients for the relationship between serum cholesterol, total fat, saturated fat and CHD for different countries (Keys, 1970a). It did not report dietary fat intake for participants who developed CHD vs. those who didn't and it did not report dietary fat intake in comparable measurements, e.g. grams, or proportion of calorie intake. The London Bus and Bank Study did not report saturated fat data and it reported serum cholesterol and total fat in tertiles, which impaired interpretation (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). The three studies of Framingham, Honolulu and Puerto Rico did not report serum cholesterol data in relation to CHD (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974). These three studies reported total fat and saturated fat in an optimal way: the dietary fat intake in grams for those who died from CHD vs. those who didn't.

No one study satisfied all inclusion criteria. The decision was taken to include all six prospective cohort studies available to the dietary committees, with deficiencies noted. This decision was supported by the fact that the UK dietary guidelines publication referenced: The Seven Countries Study and the studies of Framingham; Hawaii/Honolulu; London and Puerto Rico (Gordon et al., 1981; Keys, 1980; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Yano et al., 1978).

Statistical Analysis

The data available are not conducive to meta-analysis. Three of the studies are presented in a comparable format, but meta-analysis was not possible on these alone, as the information required for dichotomous or continuous analysis was not available (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974). The data presented in the other three studies was in different formats and also lacked the information that would enable meta-analysis to be undertaken (Keys, 1970a; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Paul et al., 1963). Table 5.2 presents the available data in the absence of forest plots being possible. Table 5.2 illustrates the lack of significant findings.

Fig. 5.1 (Moher et al., 2009) Summary of systematic review profile.

Results: Systematic review

The six observational studies systematically reviewed were, in order of first included publication: 1) The Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963); 2) The Puerto Rico Heart Health Program (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969); 3) The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a); 4) The Framingham Heart Study (Gordon and Kannel, 1970); 5) The Honolulu Heart Program (Kagan et al., 1974); and 6) a study conducted in London and the South East (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

All but the Morris *et al* study were available to the US Dietary guidelines committee. However, not all relevant data were available to both committees, as the systematic review reports. Data extracted for each study follows the TOPMOS format: Type of observational study; Objectives (of the study); Participants/Populations; Methodology; Outcomes and Study information (design, strengths, limitations etc).

The method of extracting dietary information was a limitation of all studies. Three of the studies adopted a 24-hour recall methodology (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974). One involved an hour-long interview exploring typical week and weekend intake (Paul et al., 1963). The Seven Countries Study examined a seven-day food record, but with a small proportion of participants examined (Keys, 1970b). Morris *et al* conducted a seven-day food record with items weighed (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). Dietary recall is generally unreliable and 24-hour recall may not be representative of usual diet (Beaton et al., 1983; Willett WC, 2000). Dietary surveys, where food is weighed at the time of being recorded, are also unreliable (Archer, Pavea and Lavie, 2015; Cook, Pryer and Shetty, 2000). This is stated to record, not to criticise, methodology adopted by these studies, as assessments of the reliability of dietary surveys were not available at the time. A further limitation of dietary studies is that they implicitly assume that the baseline diet remains the same as the diet consumed for the duration of the study.

Data for the Cochrane assessment of risk bias have been extracted during the systematic review (Higgins et al., 2011) (Fig. 5.2). All studies exhibited selection bias, as the exclusion of women and men outside a specific age range could not reflect wider population characteristics. This was rationalised as women and younger men rarely experienced CHD and thus more of them would need to be studied. This limitation has not been reiterated in bias analysis for each study: the reporting of selection bias has focused on additional factors that apply to each study. A number of studies reported data in a way that has made review of the diet-heart hypothesis difficult, for example the

grouping of cholesterol data in tertiles. This has not been assessed as reporting bias/selective reporting, where categorisation was logical.

1) The Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963)

Type of observational study: a prospective cohort study.

Objectives: “The study was undertaken in the belief that coronary heart disease was a disease resulting from the interplay of multiple factors and that there was need to delineate these factors further” (p.20) (Paul et al., 1963). The study started in the autumn of 1957 and planned to examine the characteristics of a male population, believed to be free from coronary heart disease, over a period of five years.

Participants/Populations: The study pool involved 5,397 men, aged 40 to 55 years, who had been working at the Western Electric Company in Chicago for 2 or more years. The 5,397 men were assigned an identification number by a randomising process. Members of the randomly selected group were invited to participate in the study, which was voluntary. After exclusions for evidence of pre-existing heart disease and approximately one third of eligible men choosing not to participate, the base population was 1,989 men.

105 men were reported as having withdrawn from the study or having left the company by the 4-year follow-up leaving 1,884 men available for inclusion in the paper. (Tables in the paper totalled to different numbers, from 1,851 to 1,885; the variations were not explained).

Methodology: Family history information was gathered using a form and follow-up interview. Blood cholesterol was measured with the Abell-Kendall method.

Dietary data were obtained by a one hour interview with a trained dietician at the start of the study. The interview asked about: the general pattern of eating on a typical workday and at the weekend; the time, place, and duration of meals; special diets followed at that time and in the past, and changes in eating habits over the previous 20 years. A detailed review of 195 specific foods was conducted to determine the number of times in the past 28 days each food had been eaten and the usual size of the portions. Wax models of common foods and dishes of varying sizes were used as aids. Supplementary information was obtained from forms completed by the wives and interviews with a sample of the wives (p.66) (Shekelle et al., 1981).

Nutritional information was compared for 1,797 non-coronary cases and 88 coronary cases for: total calories; animal protein (grams); vegetable protein (g); animal fat (g);

vegetable fat (g); carbohydrate (g); cholesterol (mg); saturated fat (g); unsaturated fat (g); linoleic acid (g); linolenic acid (g); and several micro nutrients (calcium, phosphorus, iron, vitamin A, thiamine, riboflavin, niacin, vitamin C and vitamin D) (table 10, p.28). “No significant differences are apparent for these nutrients” (p.28) (Paul et al., 1963).

Outcomes – CHD deaths: At the end of 4 years, 38 men had died of any cause. After 4 years and 5 months, 88 men had been classified as having developed coronary heart disease: angina pectoris, 47 men; myocardial infarction, 28 men; deaths from coronary disease, 13 men.

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels were reported as 247 mg/dl for the non-coronary population (1,794 men) and 272 mg/dl for the 88 men who developed coronary disease (p.25). No significance, standard error or standard deviation was given.

Paul *et al* reported that, of the 13 deaths, 3 occurred in people with cholesterol levels below 256 mg/dl and 10 occurred in people with cholesterol levels above 256 mg/dl (table 6, p.26) (Paul et al., 1963). This was presented as 23% of deaths occurred in the lower cholesterol category and 77% of deaths occurred in the higher cholesterol category. This was contrasted with 63% of 1,794 non-coronary cases having cholesterol levels below 256 mg/dl and 37% of 1,794 non-coronary cases having cholesterol levels above 256 mg/dl.

Seasonal variations in serum cholesterol levels were observed over four years: 1958-1961 (fig. 2, p.25) (Paul et al., 1963). All years reported cholesterol levels as highest in the winter. 1958 and 1960 recorded the lowest cholesterol levels in the summer and 1959 and 1961 recorded the lowest cholesterol level in the spring.

Outcomes – Diet: Daily average intake for nutrients (calories, macronutrients, saturated fat, unsaturated fat and some vitamins and minerals) were documented for 1,797 non-coronary cases and 88 coronary cases (table 10, p.28). An association between diet and coronary cases was not established. There were no significant differences between the two groups for: animal protein (90 grams/day in both coronary/non-coronary groups); vegetable protein (26 g/day coronary vs. 28 g/day non-coronary); animal fat (116 g/day coronary vs. 118 g/day non-coronary); vegetable fat (32 g/day coronary vs. 34 g/day non-coronary); carbohydrate (299 g/day coronary vs. 304 g/day non-coronary); saturated fat (identical at 59 g/day in both groups) and unsaturated fat (80 g/day coronary vs. 83 g/day non-coronary). One observable difference was total calorie intake,

which was 3,174 for non-coronary cases and 3,082 for coronary cases. This was not statistically significant. “Table 10 lists the dietary information for the coronary and non-coronary groups. No significant differences are apparent for these nutrients” (p.28) (Paul et al., 1963).

“In an attempt to isolate the high and low fat groups from the point of view of risk, the 296 men comprising the top 15 per cent of the whole population in terms of calories from fat were contrasted with the bottom 15 per cent in terms of fat intake... Worthy of comment is the fact that of the 88 coronary cases, 14 have appeared in the high-fat intake group and 16 in the low-fat group” (p.28) (Paul et al., 1963).

A positive relationship was found between coffee consumption at baseline dietary questionnaire and the subsequent development of CHD. The significance was reported as ($p < 0.025$).

Outcomes – Diet-heart hypothesis: A significant relationship ($p < 0.01$) was found between baseline cholesterol levels and subsequent CHD (table 5, p.25) (Paul et al., 1963). No relationship was found between total fat or saturated fat and CHD.

Outcomes – Other: The study found a highly significant association between cigarette smoking and development of CHD ($p < 0.005$) (p.27): 69% of the deaths occurred among smokers of half a pack or more a day (table 9, p.28) (Paul et al., 1963).

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were the number of participants, the length of follow-up, the rigour of the health information gathered and the number of different variables examined. The limitations were the single gender and the limited age range studied and all subjects drawn from one utility company.

There was evidence of selection bias (Fig. 5.2). The Hawthorne works site was chosen because of its proximity to the medical centre and because the Western Electric company expressed interest in such a project. The group was composed chiefly of second and third generation Americans of Polish and Bohemian ancestry. The pool benefited from the inclusion of different occupations: clerical; light assembly; and vigorous labour activities. The randomising process mitigated selection bias within the study population pool.

Outcome blinding was unclear (Fig. 5.2), as independent parties provided information but this was interpreted by the study team: “the assumption of death from coronary disease was made on the basis of the most reasonable conclusion to be drawn from

information obtained from the family, physicians' and hospital records, death certificates and coroners' reports" (p.21) (Paul et al., 1963).

There was no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 5.2). Over 94% of the survivors of the original group remained in the study.

There was no evidence of selective reporting (Fig. 5.2). The study set out to review many variables and reported on all of them. Associations with the development of coronary heart disease were found with: early age of death of father; history of noncardiac chest discomfort; history of chronic cough; history of shortness of breath; history of peptic ulcer; presence of increased skinfold thickness; elevated blood pressure; elevated blood cholesterol; abnormalities in the electrocardiogram and the use of cigarettes and coffee. No relationship was found between: job type; physical activity off the job; body weight; mean blood sugar levels; lipoprotein lipase levels; or diet (other than coffee), and the development of coronary heart disease (p.30) (Paul et al., 1963).

This study was available to both the US and UK dietary committees. As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, it found support for an association between serum cholesterol and coronary heart deaths or coronary heart disease. It found no support for an association between total fat, saturated fat or any dietary item (other than coffee).

2) The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a)

Type of observational study: a prospective cohort study.

Objectives: The Seven Countries Study started in 1956 in preparation (Keys, 1970a) and in 1958 in practice (Kromhout, Menotti and Blackburn, 1993). The original report of The Seven Countries Study was published in 20 volumes in *Circulation* in April 1970 entitled "Coronary Heart Disease in Seven Countries" (B. S. Djordjević et al., 1970; Christ Aravanis et al., 1970; Flaminio Fidanza et al., 1970; H. L. Taylor et al., 1970; Henry Blackburn, H. L. Taylor and Keys, 1970; Henry L. Taylor et al., 1970; Keys, 1970a; Keys, 1970b; Keys, 1970c; Keys, 1970d; Keys, 1970e; Keys, 1970f; Keys, 1970g; Keys, 1970h; Keys, 1970i; Keys, 1970j; Kimura and Keys, 1970; Martti J. Karvonen et al., 1970; Ratko Buzina et al., 1970; Vanbuchen, 1970).

The opening paragraph of the twenty volumes of The Seven Countries Study described the urgency of finding a means of prevention for CHD, particularly for middle aged men, for whom the social cost of CHD was greatest (p.I-1) (Keys, 1970a). The study aims were strongly influenced by previous Keys' work and focused on diet and its

possible relationship to the etiology of CHD: “Earlier explorations appeared to indicate that substantial differences among populations in the incidence of coronary heart disease are associated with differences in the fat content of the diets of the populations concerned, with serum cholesterol concentration being an intermediate link (Keys 1952, 1953, 1957; Keys, Kimura et al. 1958; Bronte-Stewart et al. 1955; Roine et al. 1958). It was clear that the diet probably was an important part of the reason why middle-aged men had so much higher serum cholesterol levels in Finland than their counterparts in Italy and Japan (Keys, Karvonen, and Fidanza 1958)” (p.I-162) (Keys, 1970i).

This confirmed that i) The Seven Countries Study was a study of the impact of diet on coronary heart disease, ii) Keys and colleagues had undertaken studies that “appeared to indicate” that coronary heart disease and fat in the diet were associated – through cholesterol and iii) that Keys had concluded that diet was an important factor in the difference in heart disease in Finland vs. Italy/Japan. The use of the word fat, not saturated fat, at this time should be noted.

While recommending an epidemiological approach, Keys acknowledged that “Epidemiological studies alone can rarely if ever produce final proof of a causal sequence, particularly in the case of a condition such as coronary heart disease in which there is no single cause but several major influences that promote or retard the development of the disease” (p.I-1) (Keys, 1970a).

Participants/Populations: The Seven Countries Study examined 12,770 men aged 40 to 59 years in Finland, Greece, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, the United States and Yugoslavia (Keys, 1970e). The 12,770 men came from 16 cohorts. There was one cohort in the USA and the Netherlands. There were two cohorts in Finland, Greece and Japan. Three Italian regions were included in the study and the former Yugoslavia contributed five cohorts. The 12,770 men were examined to measure pre-determined risk factors and they were then followed-up for mortality and causes of death for 25 years. Pre-existing heart disease was not an exclusion factor. 129 of the 12,770 men had a diagnosis of definite previous myocardial infarction at study entry (p.I-187) (Keys, 1970e).

The study aimed to include all men aged 40-59 at the time of the start of the study in each discrete cohort. It was decided that women or younger men would yield relatively low incidence rates and would require much larger participation numbers. Younger men were additionally considered less stable in residence and more difficult to secure for follow-up. Men over 60 were not included as they would be more likely to have other

confounding conditions (Keys, 1980). Blackburn explained "we did not consider involving women because of the great rarity of cardiac events among them and the invasiveness of our field examinations" (p.2) (Blackburn, 1995). The exclusion of women negated the possibility of explaining the paradox of women having higher mean serum cholesterol than men and lower CHD.

Two aims of i) keeping self selection of subjects to a minimum and ii) striving for a near-zero loss to follow-up were achieved by concentrating on rural locations. Of the 16 cohorts, 11 were rural, the 5 exceptions being: the USA railroad cohort; the Rome railroad workers; Zutphen in the Netherlands; and Belgrade and Zrenjanin in Yugoslavia. The rural cohorts were characterised by low population density and agriculture, fishing or forestry being the only industry. Rosters of men in the rural locations were compiled from local registers, tax and voting lists and were checked against church, police and other records. Japan and some European cohorts had identity documents (Keys, 1980).

The USA railroad cohort comprised a statistical sample drawn from men representing sedentary occupations (executives, dispatchers and clerks) and switchmen representing physically active men. Self selection was more prevalent in this cohort, as only 75% of invited participants volunteered (Keys, 1980). Subsequent analysis of the railroad men found no significant differences between the occupational classes in either risk factors or incidence of disease. Accordingly the USA railroad men were pooled to establish one cohort.

The Rome railroad cohort provided a comparison to the American railroad cohort. The response of the Italian railroad men was not quantified, but described as better than that of the Americans and not as good as the near total response of rural Italians.

Zutphen was a small market town offering a non-rural discrete region. All men aged 40-59 years were invited to participate and 84.3% presented themselves for examination. Zrenjanin was an agricultural town with some light industry and a measureable population of males aged 40-59 years, of which 98% agreed to participate. Belgrade was defined by members of the faculty of Belgrade University. The response rate for Belgrade was 80%. It was noted at the time that university professors were not representative of the general population (p.6) (Keys, 1980).

Blackburn acknowledged that "The study has been criticized for the method in which populations were selected for the study" (p.2) (Blackburn, 1995). Japan and the USA had already been documented as defining the end points of the observed relationship

between dietary fat and deaths from CHD in men aged 55-59 (Keys, 1953a). Italy was another of the six countries, positioned on the relationship line in the Mount Sinai presentation. A book written in tribute to Keys for his 90th birthday documented that many of the countries were chosen because researchers were known to be examining similar issues to Keys: Martti Karvonen in Finland; Flaminio Fidanza and Vittorio Puddu in Italy; Ratko Buzina and Bozidar Djordjevic in what was known as Yugoslavia; Christos Aravanis and Anastasios (Andy) Dontas in Greece; Noboru Kimura and Hironori (Hiro) Toshima in Japan; and Frans Van Buchem and Louise Dalderup in The Netherlands (p.11) (Kromhout, Menotti and Blackburn, 1993). As documented in Chapter Two, Keys had collaborated with Buzina, Fidanza, Karvonen and Kimura prior to the start of The Seven Countries Study.

Zutphen was chosen by the Dutch researchers “because it offered practical advantages of local hospitals and physicians and had been the site of earlier health surveys” (p.5) (Keys, 1980). The USA railroad industry was selected “because the pensions, death and disability benefits of the Railroad Retirement Board provide powerful incentives to maintain contact with the board” (p.4) (Keys, 1980). The Rome railroad men were chosen “to provide a European sample to compare with the American railroad men” (p.5) (Keys, 1980). For the selection of Crevalcore and Montegiorgio, “it was enough to have the assurance of our colleague Flaminio Fidanza that we would have good cooperation in those rural areas and that the cost of the work would be within our resources” (p.6) (Keys, 1980). Similarly, “friendship with our colleague Ratko Buzina led to selection of areas of Dalmatia and Slavonia where he had friends to help and where, again, we could expect low cost and high cooperation” (p.6) (Keys, 1980). In Japan “Noburu Kimura, who had once worked with us in Minnesota, offered enthusiastic help at little cost” (p.7) (Keys, 1980). “Similarly, collaboration with Martti J. Karvonen, led to the choice of Finland.” “In Greece, friends A.S. Dontas and Christ Aravanis led us to Crete” (p.7) (Keys, 1980).

The context of The Seven Countries Study was important, as the men were war survivors. Men aged 40-59 years in 1956 were aged between 23-42 years when World War II started and aged between 29-48 years when World War II ended. This context was important for each of the seven countries in the study and cohort differences. Italy joined the war in June 1940, with Mussolini politically aligned to Hitler through fascism. Italian men fought in conflicts from east Africa through Greece to southern France, but Italy was not invaded or occupied. Greece was invaded by Italy and Crete

was occupied by Germany. Yugoslavia signed a tripartite treaty in March 1941 to allow Germany through its territory to Greece. Germany reneged on the treaty and took control of Yugoslavia on the return from Greece (Gilbert, 2004). The Netherlands was occupied from May 1940 until the end of the war. Anne Frank's diary gives some insight into life in this small territory (Frank, 1947).

The American people were brought into the war with the attack on Pearl Harbour in December 1941, but were not invaded or occupied. Japan's most devastating involvement in World War II was the allied atomic bombing of Hiroshima and Nagasaki in August 1945. The greatest suffering directly involving a cohort was experienced in east Finland. The Finns fought the Winter War alone against the Soviet Union, the Continuation War with Germany against the Soviet Union and the Lapland War against Germany. Most of Finnish Karelia was lost to the Soviet Union with The Moscow Peace Treaty of 1940. Approximately 400,000 people, virtually the entire population of Karelia (the cohort of east Finland), required relocation within Finland. The Winter War and Continuation War, particularly, and the resulting Soviet expansion caused considerable bitterness in Finland. The territory taken from Finland by the Soviet Union included: Viipuri, Finland's second largest city; the industrial heartland; a key canal (Saimaa) and it made an eighth of Finland's citizens refugees, without chance of return (Gilbert, 2004). As shown in Table 5.1, Column F, this displaced region of east Finland experienced the highest rate of CHD deaths among all 16 cohorts.

Keys was aware of the impact of war on countries studied, Finland especially. Keys excluded Finland from the Mount Sinai presentation with the explanation: "The omissions are Western Germany and Finland, because of major population shifts and other effects from the war" (p.120) (Keys, 1953a). In the 1954 symposium on atherosclerosis, Keys described the impact of war on the four Scandinavian countries (p.190) (Keys and Anderson, 1954). In a 1952 paper, Keys narrated: "Besides the dubious point of attributing war-time changes in vital statistics to actual changes in atherosclerosis..." (p.115-116) (Keys, 1952b).

Methodology: The methodology for the examination of participants was documented in a Scandinavian medical journal (Keys A et al., 1967) and in Volume II of The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970b).

At the initial meeting, a nurse, medical technician or physician undertook a comprehensive examination and documented medical history and lifestyle information. The London School of Hygiene Cardiovascular questionnaire was completed by the

examiner (Rose and Blackburn, 1968) (annex 6). Men were assessed in underwear and socks to record height, weight and skin fold thickness over the triceps and the tip of the scapula. Blood pressure was recorded at least twice. A 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) was recorded in supine rest on multichannel machines, with routine control of calibration and paper speed (25 mm/sec). Except where there was manifest heart disease or other contraindication, a three-minute exercise test was made with repetition of the ECG immediately after the end of the exercise. The final classification of the ECG was made and independently checked in the coordinating center for The Seven Countries Study at the University of Minnesota. A urinary sample for qualitative urinalysis and a blood sample for serum cholesterol analysis completed the examination. Serum cholesterol was also analysed at the Minnesota center (Keys, 1970b). Information was gathered on smoking rates and levels of inactivity.

Complete re-examinations were given every five years for those who had survived and cause of death was recorded for those who had died. At the first re-examination, five years later, the same tests were administered and the same examiners were used as far as was possible. The majority of examinations were made in the mornings, before the men had performed strenuous work; most of them had eaten their usual breakfast before the appointment (Keys, 1970b).

Complete five-year re-examinations covered 94.2% of all survivors, and at least some information about health status was obtained for almost all of the other men; fewer than 0.5 of 1% were lost to follow-up (p.I-186) (Keys, 1970e).

Dietary information was documented in Volume XVII of The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970i) and in a non-mainstream Dutch booklet (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). The opening volume of the study reported that 7-day dietary surveys were carried out on random samples of the cohorts, except in the United States where dietary data were obtained by 24-hour recall interview of all men at the time of entry examination and among the Rome railroad men, where a sample of employees were queried with the sole purpose of detecting whose diets differed from the norm for the region. For Japan, it was noted that a more carefully controlled survey was carried out at Tanushimaru, but not at the fishing village of Ushibuka (p.I-6) (Keys, 1970a). Aside from the complete US survey, the highest sample taken was 8.1% in Yugoslavia – Zrenjanin and the lowest sample taken was 2.8% in Italy – Crevalcore (Appendix 7).

Outcomes – CHD deaths: At the first five year review, 588 of the 12,770 men had died – 158 from coronary heart disease (CHD). Of the 129 with a diagnosis of definite

previous myocardial infarction (MI) at study entry, 27 died within five years. Of the 12,641 men not diagnosed with definite previous MI at study entry, 131 died within five years (p.I-187) (Keys, 1970e). The death rate from CHD for those with pre-existing MI was 20.9%. The death rate from CHD for those without previous MI was 1.0%. This was a major finding of The Seven Countries Study, but not reported as such.

The data for pre-existing CHD were inconsistent. Volume XV of The Seven Countries Study reported that 241 men were not free of CHD (p.I-148) (Keys, 1970h). The 1980 publication detailed men who were CHD free at entry by cohort; these totalled 261 men (p.9) (Keys, 1980). The data for men with pre-existing CHD and subsequent deaths from CHD were available for USA, Finland and “other areas”, making analysis excluding pre-existing CHD not possible by country or cohort (p.I-149) (Keys, 1970h).

The following analysis thus includes men with pre-existing heart disease.

Table 5.1 Data extracted from The Seven Countries Study for: start date; number of men; all deaths; CHD deaths; baseline median cholesterol levels; percentage of calorie intake from total fat and percentage of calorie intake from saturated fat.

	Col A	Col B	Col C	Col D	Col E	Col F	Col G	Col H	Col J
Country – Cohort	Start	Men	All Deaths	Deaths/ 100,000	CHD Deaths	CHD deaths/ 100,000	Median chol. mg/dl	% Calories total fat	% Calories sat fat
Japan – Tanushimaru	1958	509	23	4,519	4	786	170	9%	3%
Yugoslavia – Dalmatia	1958	672	24	3,571	3	446	186	32%	9%
Yugoslavia – Slavonia	1958	699	55	7,868	7	1,001	198	33%	14%
USA – Railroad workers	1958-60	2,571	124	4,823	62	2,412	237	40%	17.5%
Finland – east (north Karelia)	1959	817	61	7,466	29	3,550	265	39%	22%
Finland – west	1959	860	50	5,814	9	1,047	237	35%	19%
Italy – Crevalcore	1960	993	60	6,042	11	1,108	200	27%	10%
Italy – Montegiorgio	1960	719	29	4,033	5	695	200	25%	9%
The Netherlands – Zutphen	1960	878	50	5,695	16	1,822	230 (mean)	40%	19%
Japan – Ushibuka	1960	504	24	4,762	1	198	140	N/A	N/A
Greece – Crete	1960	686	10	1,458	1	146	202	40%	8%
Greece – Corfu	1961	529	11	2,079	4	756	198	33%	7%

Italy – Rome Railroad workers	1962	768	24	3,125	2	260	207	N/A	N/A
Yugoslavia – Velika Krsna	1962	511	23	4,501	1	196	156	24%	9%
Yugoslavia – Zrenjanin	1963	516	15	2,907	1	194	167	N/A	N/A
Yugoslavia – Belgrade	1964	538	5	929	2	372	208	N/A	N/A
TOTAL		12,770	588		158				

Table notes:

Data in columns A, B, C and E were extracted from Volume I of the *Circulation* report (table I.2, p.I-7) (Keys, 1970a).

Columns D and F, for all deaths and CHD deaths per 100,000 people, were calculated to facilitate comparison between large and small cohorts.

Cholesterol data for Column G were extracted from the 20 Volume *Circulation* report as follows. All measurements are medians unless otherwise stated: Japan – Tanushimaru (p.I-111 “about”) (Kimura and Keys, 1970); Yugoslavia – Dalmatia (p.I-41) (Ratko Buzina et al., 1970); Yugoslavia – Slavonia (p.I-41) (Ratko Buzina et al., 1970); USA – Railroad workers (p.I-54) (Martti J. Karvonen et al., 1970) ; Finland – east (p.I-54) (Martti J. Karvonen et al., 1970); Finland – west (p.I-54) (Martti J. Karvonen et al., 1970); Italy – Crevalcore (p.I-65 approximation of 200 given) (Flaminio Fidanza et al., 1970); Italy – Montegiorgio (p.I-65 approximation of 200 given) (Flaminio Fidanza et al., 1970); The Netherlands – Zutphen (no average given. 230 was estimated from table VIII.2 (p.I-78) – taking the mean of the 50th percentile score of 4 age groups given) (Vanbuchem, 1970); Japan – Ushibuka (p.I-111 “about”) (Kimura and Keys, 1970); Greece – Crete (p.I-90) (Christ Aravanis et al., 1970); Greece – Corfu (p.I-90) (Christ Aravanis et al., 1970); Italy – Rome Railroad workers (p.I-118) (Henry L. Taylor et al., 1970); Yugoslavia – Velika Krsna (p.I-125) (B. S. Djordjević et al., 1970); Yugoslavia – Zrenjanin (p.I-125) (B. S. Djordjević et al., 1970); Yugoslavia – Belgrade (p.I-127) (B. S. Djordjević et al., 1970).

Data for Column H and J were extracted from Volume XVII of the *Circulation* report (fig. XVII.1, p.I-168) (Keys, 1970i). Data were not available for four cohorts as shown with N/A – Not Available. Tanushimaru was abbreviated to Kyushu.

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels:

In a commentary following the introduced dietary guidelines in the US, Reiser noted that “The natives of six of the 13 places studied have exactly the same serum cholesterol concentrations. That alone should make any conclusion relating serum cholesterol values to coronary events questionable. Additionally, the incidence of CHD in the six places varies from about 0.5 to 6 persons per 100 over a 5-year period” (p.870) (Reiser, 1978). Reiser was commenting on data for 13 cohorts, excluding Japan and Rome (fig. XVII.4, p.I-172) (Keys, 1970i). As shown in Table 5.1, Column G, the six cohorts with essentially the same cholesterol concentrations were Slavonia, Crevalcore, Montegiorgio, Crete, Corfu and Belgrade.

Outcomes – Diet: The dietary information available from The Seven Countries Study was not comprehensive. Most of the volumes in *Circulation* made no mention of dietary fat: total, saturated or any other kind (B. S. Djordjević et al., 1970; H. L. Taylor et al., 1970; Henry Blackburn, H. L. Taylor and Keys, 1970; Henry L. Taylor et al., 1970; Keys, 1970b; Keys, 1970c; Keys, 1970d; Keys, 1970f; Keys, 1970g; Keys, 1970h; Keys, 1970j). The other reference given by Keys for dietary detail was the Dutch publication (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). Between these two sources, the dietary information for each cohort was as follows:

- There was no dietary information in either The Seven Countries Study or Den Hartog for the USA railroad cohort (H. L. Taylor et al., 1970) or the Rome railroad cohort (Henry L. Taylor et al., 1970).
- Japan was not covered by the Den Hartog publication. Volume I of The Seven Countries Study reported that a carefully controlled dietary survey was carried out at Tanushimaru, but not at Ushibuka (p.I-6) (Keys, 1970a). The only mention of the diet in Tanushimaru was in Volume X of The Seven Countries Study: “The diet of Tanushimaru is dominated by rice, soybean products, vegetables in great variety, fish and seafood, very little fat, and very little dairy produce” (p.I-102) (Kimura and Keys, 1970).
- The three Yugoslavian cohorts of Velika Krsna, Zrenjanin and Belgrade were reported in Volume XII of The Seven Countries Study (B. S. Djordjević et al., 1970), but there were no references to diet or dietary fat. The Den Hartog booklet reported percentage of calories from each macronutrient for the three cohorts, but with no food intake detail underpinning this.

- The other two Yugoslavian cohorts, Dalmatia and Slavonia, were reported in Volume V of The Seven Countries Study (Ratko Buzina et al., 1970). The sole reference to the Dalmatian diet described the Dalmatian coast as “olive country, and the diet is characterized by the use of olive oil to the exclusion of almost all other fat” (p.I-40). The only reference to the diet in Slavonia reported: “In Slavonia, animal fat, especially pork fat, takes the place of oil in the diet, and meats and poultry are used in greater abundance than in Dalmatia” (p.I-40) (Ratko Buzina et al., 1970). The Den Hartog document reported more detail for these two cohorts. One of the most striking differences was the alcohol intake, which accounted for 7.8% of calorie intake in Slavonia and 20.6% of calorie intake in Dalmatia (table 7, p.116) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). As shown in Table 5.1, Dalmatia had less than half the CHD deaths per 100,000 of Slavonia, despite similar cholesterol levels.

- The Dutch cohort of Zutphen was reported in Volume VIII of The Seven Countries Study with one dietary reference, which was not primarily about Zutphen: “...the data on the U.S. railroad men are not very precise, but the Americans seemed to be more like the Zutphen men than any other cohort in respect to total fats, kinds of fatty acids, etc” (p.I-81) (Vanbuchem, 1970). The Den Hartog booklet reported percentage of calories from each macronutrient for Zutphen, and contained some food intake detail for dairy fat, margarine, fish fat, meat fat, bread, potato and pulse intake, which accounted for approximately 45% of daily calories (table 7, p.98) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968).

Consistent with other cohort observations (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977), the Zutphen study reported that “the men who had had a myocardial infarction, angina pectoris or intermittent claudication had a significantly lower consumption of calories than the others ($p < 0.05$)” (p.99) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968).

- Both Finnish cohorts were reported in Volume VI of The Seven Countries Study with one dietary reference alone: “...by 1959 it was clear that the diets of the men in both rural areas were somewhat lower in fat than the average diet in the United States but that butterfat was a prominent item” (p.I-52) (Martti J. Karvonen et al., 1970). The Den Hartog data for Finland was more comprehensive with a detailed breakdown of calorie intake for cereals, sugar, margarine, butter, milk, meat, fish, eggs, alcohol, potatoes, other vegetables and fruit. In contrast with Dalmatia and Slavonia, alcohol intake for west Finland and east Finland was 0.6% and 0.4% respectively. The differences in the

west and east Finland diets were not dramatic. Butter intake at 12.4% of total calories for west Finland and 16.7% for east Finland was one of the biggest differences. Cereal, sugar, margarine, milk, meat and potato intakes were similar. Fish intake was higher in east Finland; egg, vegetable and fruit intake were higher in west Finland (table 2, p.33) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968).

- Rural Italy, Crevalcore and Montegiorgio, were documented in Volume VII of The Seven Countries Study, again with sparse dietary detail.”...repeated dietary surveys on subsamples of the cohort of Crevalcore showed an average of only 27% of calories from total fats and only 15% of calories from fats of animal origin (p.I-64) (Fidanza et al. 1964).” “The average of surveys in three different seasons in Montegiorgio showed 25% of total calories from total fats and 16% of calories from fats of animal origin (p.I-64) (Fidanza et al. 1964).” Den Hartog provided more detail with a breakdown of food intake for: cereals; sugar and sweets; fats and oils; milk and cheese; meat/fish/eggs; alcohol; potatoes and vegetables; and fruits. The alcohol intake for both rural Italian cohorts was 10% of total calories. The largest differences in diet were milk and cheese providing 8% of Crevalcore calories and 1% of those in Montegiorgio. Sugar and sweets accounted for 5.2% of the Crevalcore diet and 1.8% of the Montegiorgio calorie intake. The Montegiorgio diet was higher in cereals (52.6% vs. 46.4%) and fats and oils (16.8% vs. 13.3%) (table 3, p.72) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). These two cohorts were interesting because their mean serum cholesterol level was identical at 200 mg/dl at baseline, while CHD deaths per 100,000 were almost twice as high in Crevalcore as Montegiorgio (1,108 vs. 695).

- There was one mention of diet in Volume IX of The Seven Countries Study, which documented the Greek islands of Crete and Corfu: “In regard to the diet, the only obvious difference between the two populations [Crete and Corfu] is a somewhat higher intake of fat in Crete, a difference entirely accounted for by olive oil” (p.I-99) (Christ Aravanis et al., 1970). Den Hartog contained more detail. Three samples, of an average of 32 men, were taken for Crete in September 1960, May/June 1962 and February 1965. Two samples, of an average of 37 men, were taken for Corfu in September 1961 and March/April 1963.

The Greek Orthodox Easter Sunday in 1963 fell on April 14th (Harry J. Smith, 1963), which meant that the seven consecutive day sampling period for Corfu in March-April fell within the 40 days of Lent. The intake was reported as: 26.5% bread; 31.4% olive oil; 3.1% animal protein; 6.0% animal fat; 4.3% alcohol and 28.6% other sources for the

average of the three Crete samples. The intake was reported as: 39.5% bread; 23.9% olive oil; 3.3% animal protein; 3.9% animal fat; 7.8% alcohol and 21.7% other sources for the average of the two Corfu samples (table 3, p.60) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). The lent Corfu sample differed little from the non-lent period. Bread consumption was slightly higher and olive oil and alcohol consumption slightly lower during the lent period, but animal fat and animal protein intake were virtually identical. Crete and Corfu had virtually identical serum cholesterol levels (202 mg/dl vs. 198 mg/dl) and significantly different CHD death rates (146 per 100,000 for Crete vs. 756 per 100,000 for Corfu).

Outcomes – Diet-heart hypothesis: The summary of The Seven Countries Study presented the three parts of the diet-heart hypothesis as study conclusions:

- 1) "The incidence rate of CHD tends to be directly related to the distributions of serum cholesterol values" (p.I-191 to I-194) (Keys, 1970e);
- 2) "The average serum cholesterol values of the cohorts tended to be directly related to the average proportion of calories provided by saturated fats in the diet" (p.I-194) (Keys, 1970e);
- 3) "The CHD incidence rates of the cohorts are just as closely related to the dietary saturated fatty acids as to the serum cholesterol level" (p.I-194) (Keys, 1970e).

Keys did not claim that saturated fat consumption or serum cholesterol levels were causal factors in heart disease. The conclusions made were that CHD, serum cholesterol levels and dietary saturated fat tended to be related. Total fat was rejected as a factor related to either cholesterol or CHD: "Serum cholesterol averages and CHD incidence rates were not found to be related to the percentage of calories provided by protein or polyunsaturated fatty acids in the diet and were only slightly related to total fat calories" (p.I-194) (Keys, 1970e).

Keys reported correlation coefficients with 13 or 14 cohorts as follows, but the source figure excluded 4 cohorts (Ushibuka, Rome railroad, Zrenjanin and Belgrade) (fig. XVII.1, p.I-168) (Keys, 1970i):

Median serum cholesterol and saturated fat as a percentage of calories: $r = 0.89$ (p.I-170) ($p < 0.05$). This was based on 14 cohorts, with Ushibuka and Rome Railroad missing.

Median serum cholesterol and CHD deaths and infarctions (data for CHD deaths alone were not presented) per 100 people: $r = 0.76$ (p.I-172) ($p < 0.05$). This was based on 13 cohorts, with both Japanese cohorts and Rome Railroad missing.

CHD deaths and infarctions (data for CHD deaths alone were not presented) and total fat as a percentage of calories: $r = 0.40$ (p.I-173) (not significant) ($p > 0.05$). This was based on 13 cohorts, with both Japanese cohorts and Rome Railroad missing.

CHD deaths and infarctions (data for CHD deaths alone were not presented) and saturated fat as a percentage of calories: $r = 0.84$ (p.I-174) ($p < 0.05$). This was based on 13 cohorts, with both Japanese cohorts and Rome Railroad missing.

These correlation coefficients established strong relationships between the component parts of the diet-heart hypothesis, using saturated, not total, dietary fat and using CHD deaths and infarctions. The data are available to calculate correlation coefficients for CHD deaths alone. These were not substantially different to the correlation coefficients for CHD deaths and infarctions (Appendix 8).

Outcomes – Other: The summary volume of The Seven Countries Study presented additional findings about non-significant relationships between CHD incidence and smoking, sedentary behaviour, weight, protein and polyunsaturated fat :

- “Cigarette smoking cannot be involved as an explanation” (p.I-189 to I-191).
- “Differences between the cohorts in the proportion of the men who are sedentary or physically inactive do not explain the difference between the cohorts in the incidence of CHD” (p.I-191).
- “Consideration of neither obesity nor relative weight helps to explain the population differences in CHD incidence” (p.I-191).
- “CHD incidence rates were not found to be related to the percentage of calories provided by protein or polyunsaturated fatty acids” (p.I-194) (Keys, 1970e).

One other relationship was noted: “There is some tendency for the incidence of CHD to be related to the prevalence of hypertension in the cohorts” (p.I-191) (Keys, 1970e).

In the summary of The Seven Countries Study, those were the statements of conclusions. There was no mention in this summary of monounsaturated fat. The only mention of polyunsaturated fat was that it was unrelated. Keys asserted that smoking, activity levels/exercise and weight played no part in CHD; blood pressure had some

observed pattern and CHD tended to be related to total cholesterol and the average proportion of calories provided by saturated fats in the diet.

By 1960, The Framingham Heart Study had found that smoking increased the risk of heart disease (Dawber, 1960). By 1967 the same study had found that exercise had a positive impact on heart disease and weight had an adverse impact (Kannel, 1967). In 1953, Morris *et al* demonstrated the benefit of vigorous physical activity to cardiovascular health (Morris and Crawford, 1958). Published in 1970, the conclusions of The Seven Countries Study were contrary to evidence of the time. Importance was assigned to a study for its cholesterol and saturated fat findings, which contradicted contemporary evidence about smoking, activity and weight.

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were: the scale and ambition of the project; the rigour of clinical examination; the reporting of the methodology for the physical examination of participants; and the expertise collated to work on the project. The limitations were: the single gender; the limited age range studied; the method of selecting cohorts and countries; the limited sampling of participants for dietary information; the inclusion of men with pre-existing heart disease and not presenting data so that these could be excluded.

The most significant limitation of the study was that it was an inter-country comparison rather than a CHD/CHD-free comparison. Men who developed CHD in Japan were compared with men who developed CHD in the US, as opposed to men who developed CHD in Japan being compared with men who did not develop CHD in Japan. This introduced substantially more confounding factors, including, but not limited to: geography; lifestyle; Gross Domestic Product; climate; politics; other aspects of national diet; national health provision etc. When asked about the value of Keys' work, a contemporary of the time, Professor Peter Elwood, described inter country studies as "the lowest form of evidence" (Personal communication, 2015).

There was evidence of selection bias in the selection of locations, with friendship playing a substantial part and with a number of countries chosen known to adhere to the hypothesis being examined: Italy; Japan; and the US (Keys, 1953a) (Fig. 5.2). The considerations of expected local co-operation and affordability of the location were practical rather than scientific factors. There was no evidence of selection bias in the selection of participants within chosen locations, as all men meeting the age requirement were invited to take part. Overall response rate was 90.4% (p.9) (Keys, 1980) and would have been higher but for the 75% and 80.6% response rate in the US

and Rome railroad organisations respectively where men were concerned about employment and benefits should heart disease be diagnosed.

Outcome blinding was unclear in Europe and Japan, as cohort staff were involved in the process: “After the entry examinations local physicians and health workers recorded deaths and serious illnesses; those reports of mortality and major changes in health status were periodically (two to four times yearly) checked by physicians of the research teams responsible for each of the cohorts in Europe and in Japan” (p.I-5-I-6) (Keys, 1970a). In the US railroad cohort, the Railroad Retirement Board provided information on illness, hospitalisation, retirement, and deaths effectively blinding outcomes from the study team (Fig. 5.2).

There was no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 5.2). The study aims of minimising self selection of subjects and striving for a near-zero loss to follow-up were achieved by concentrating on rural locations.

There was some evidence of selective reporting (Fig. 5.2). Data were not presented as absolute numbers; demarcations were introduced to classify participants as the percentage of men: smoking more than 10 cigarettes a day; being sedentary (as opposed to being moderately active for much of the day or occupied in hard physical labour); with relative weight more than 110%; with mean skin folds more than 28mm; with systolic blood pressure more than or equal to 160 mmHg; with diastolic blood pressure more than or equal to 95 mmHg; and cholesterol greater than 250 mg/dl. Keys commented on the substantial difference between CHD deaths and incidents among those with pre-existing heart disease, but the data were not available to evaluate healthy men alone.

This study was available to both the US and UK dietary committees. As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, it found strong correlations between serum cholesterol, the percentage of calories from saturated fat and coronary heart deaths across countries. It found no support for an association between total fat and CHD.

3) The London Bus and Bank Study (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977)

Type of observational study: a (pilot) prospective cohort study.

Objectives: This study was undertaken “as part of a search for a practicable way of assessing individual diet that could be used in a large-scale prospective study of diet and coronary heart disease (CHD)” (p.1307) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). The authors reported that they failed to find a valid and simple enough method suitable for large-

scale study and thus abandoned the project. This small scale study did produce some interesting findings worthy of inclusion in this systematic review.

The study noted that the leading hypothesis of the time related “the incidence of CHD, through serum cholesterol concentrations, to the fat in the diet, and more particularly to the saturated fatty-acid content, or the ratio of polyunsaturated to saturated fatty acids (P:S ratio)” (p.1311) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Participants/Populations: The study involved 337 healthy men, aged 30-67 years, working as bank staff (151 men), bus conductors (84 men) or bus drivers (102 men) in London and south-east England. The men were recruited by the Medical Research Council (MRC) social medicine unit. The men were representative of London and country staff from four major banks and of London transport drivers and conductors. They represented 83% of the men approached and eligible to participate in the study. Men were deemed ineligible if they had a history or clinical evidence of CHD and/or were on a prescribed diet. Of the remaining 17%, 10% refused to participate and 7% produced incomplete documentation.

Methodology: Between 1956 and 1966, all 337 men participated in a 7-day individual weighed dietary survey. Personnel records were accessed for all 337 men, providing baseline data for age, occupation, height and weight. The bank employees in 3 areas and all the busmen, totalling approximately 280 of the men, were examined clinically at the time of the dietary survey. Complete data were extracted on 270 men in total. The additional clinical examinations provided data for smoking, serum cholesterol, systolic blood pressure and skin fold thickness. Cholesterol methodology was not reported, but readings were described as “casual” and “non-fasting” (p.1312) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). The diet information provided data for intake of: calories; saturated fat; polyunsaturated fat; sugar; animal protein and cereal fibre. Unfortunately, dietary intakes were presented in low third, middle third and high third groups in comparison tables with other variables and thus absolute data were not available for analysis.

Outcomes – CHD deaths: By the end of 1976, 45 of the 337 men had developed coronary heart disease; 26 had died from CHD and 51 had died from any cause. Clinical examinations had been performed on 36 of the 45 men who developed CHD and thus information related to smoking, serum cholesterol and other examination measures were available for this number.

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels: Consistent with all observations reported in Chapter Two, the review of the literature, the article reported that “Analysis of dietary

cholesterol against coronary events showed no association at all” (p.1312) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Plasma cholesterol was presented in tertiles: the low third fell into the 3.0-5.6 mmol/l group; the middle third were between 5.6-6.5 mmol/l and the high third had plasma cholesterol levels in the range 6.5-8.6 mmol/l. As noted in the methodology, only 270 of the men were fully examined providing cholesterol data. Of these, 36 developed CHD: 7 in the low third group, 13 in the middle third and 16 in the high third. The incident rates were 7.8%, 14.4% and 17.8% respectively. The statistical significance of this was not reported.

The study reported that a “massive correlation exercise” was carried out on plasma cholesterol data collated for 270 of the men. “Correlation coefficients were calculated between individual lipid values and all the dietary variables, firstly, for all the men, then standardised by occupation. The results throughout were, as expected, little or nothing” (p.1312) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). The words “as expected” were interesting, but not expanded upon.

Outcomes – Diet: The study found two relationships with diet: “men with a high energy intake had a lower rate of CHD than the rest” (p.1307) and “fewer cases of CHD developed among men with a relatively high ratio of polyunsaturated to saturated fatty acids in their diet, but the difference was not statistically significant” (p.1307) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Consistent with other data presentation in the paper, total fat was presented in tertiles. The low third of total fat intake derived 30-39% of calories from fat; the middle third derived 38-43% of calories from fat; and the high third derived 41-56% of calories from fat. The overlaps were not explained. There were 18 cases of CHD in the low third, 10 in the middle third and 17 in the high third, giving incident rates of 16%, 9% and 15% respectively (table XIV, p.1311) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Saturated fat was not presented similarly. Saturated fat was presented as a percentage of energy intake by low, middle and high energy intake groups: “There was little qualitative difference in the patterns of diet between the three energy-intake groups (Fig 1). Thus in the thirds of the men, saturated fats, for example, constituted 21.5%, 21.2% and 21.4% of total energy intake” (p1309). This negated possible analysis of the association between saturated fat and development of CHD.

The authors concluded that, in the data, “the association between energy intake or cereal-fibre intake or the ratio of P:S in the diet and CHD is not mediated or explained in any simple way through plasma cholesterol concentrations” (p.1312) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Outcomes – Other: The study recorded smoking details for 270 of the men and found a strong relationship between smoking and incidence of CHD. 6.7% of non-smokers developed CHD; 20.8% of those smoking 11-20 cigarettes a day developed CHD and 28.6% of those smoking more than 20 cigarettes a day developed CHD. The statistical significance of this was not provided.

The wider age range for this study enabled the observation of an association between age and cases of CHD. Among 77 men aged 30-44, 7 developed CHD; among 118 men aged 45-49, 16 developed CHD; among 114 men aged 50-59, 17 developed CHD; and among 28 men aged 60-67, 5 developed CHD. The incident rates were 9.1%, 13.6%, 14.9% and 17.9% respectively (table III, p.1308) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were the length of follow-up, the inclusion of different occupations and the dietary survey being 7-day, not 24-hour. The limitations were the single gender, the small participant numbers, fewer still having clinical data extracted and the presentation of data in tertiles, restricting secondary analysis. The wider age range studied had the advantage of including men outside the ages of 40 to 64 and thus being more representative of the male population. However, it had the disadvantage of age then being a confounding factor not adjusted for. The report noted that there were no cases of CHD under the age of 40 and only two over the age of 70.

There was some evidence of selection bias (Fig. 5.2). The pool benefited from the inclusion of different occupations and the high participation rate among those eligible. No rationale was given for the chosen location (London and the south-east) or for the chosen sources of participants: banks and London transport.

There was evidence of blinding, as the men were “tagged” at the Registrar General’s Office and notifications of death were sent to the researchers from this external source (Fig. 5.2). The authors reported that “to avoid importing bias” the diagnoses given on death certificates were accepted without question (p.1308) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

There was no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 5.2). The original group was fully accounted for, as a death or survival, at follow-up.

There was no evidence of selective reporting (Fig. 5.2). The study set out to review many variables and reported on all of them. Associations with the development of coronary heart disease were found with: age; smoking; height; energy intake and intake of cereal fibre. No relationship was found between: physique; skin fold thickness; sucrose consumption; dietary cholesterol; total fat; or saturated fat and the development of coronary heart disease. The presentation of data in low, middle and high groups compromised interpretation of that data; but there was no evidence that tertiles were used to bias the presentation of results.

The primary conclusion of the study was that men with a high energy intake had a lower rate of CHD than men with a low energy intake. Weight did not correlate with energy intake. Morris became renowned for the study of activity in bus drivers compared with bus conductors and the lower incidence of CHD in the more active occupation (Heady et al., 1961; Morris and Crawford, 1958). The energy finding could be confounded by more active men consuming more calories. However, the energy intakes of the bank staff, bus drivers and bus conductors were a mean of 2,645, 2,651 and 2,646 respectively – not sufficiently different for this to provide an explanation.

As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, the study found some support for an association between plasma cholesterol and coronary heart disease (CHD deaths not reported). It found no support for an association between total fat, saturated fat or any dietary item, other than cereal fibre and total calorie intake.

4) The Framingham Heart Study (Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970)

Type of observational study: a prospective cohort study.

Objectives: The Framingham Heart Study started at the end of 1948 as a long-term epidemiological investigation into cardiovascular disease (CVD). In a review of Framingham, twenty years on, Tavia Gordon and William Kannel documented that The Framingham Heart Study derived from the hypothesis that the age of onset of CVD was a function of three variables: 1) constitutional factors (including hereditary); 2) conditioning factors (the external environment) and 3) the length of time the conditioning factors act on or interact with constitutionally determined factors to result in clinical CVD (Gordon and Kannel, 1970).

The general epidemiological purpose of the study was “the determination of factors influencing the development of heart disease” (p.125) (Gordon and Kannel, 1970).

Participants/Populations: Framingham, a town in Massachusetts, 21 miles west of Boston, met a number of criteria deemed important as a location for a successful long-term health study: the town was of sufficient size to provide participants, but not so large that selection could be exclusive; it contained a variety of socioeconomic and ethnic subgroups to be representative of a wider population; the population was relatively stable, facilitating follow-up; the town was located near a suitable medical centre and the staff therein were highly supportive of the study; an annual list of residents was well maintained and death certificate information and other vital statistics were thoroughly documented. Framingham had also been the site for a community study of tuberculosis, 30 years earlier, and thus had previous study performance and experience.

The original participants recruited into The Framingham Heart Study were 5,209 men and women between the ages of 30 and 59. “It was not until Exam 4 that a diet history was introduced” (p.131) (Gordon and Kannel, 1970). Exam 4 covered the period 1954 to 1958 (National Heart Institute, 1968).

The Framingham Heart Study was the model for the Honolulu and Puerto Rico studies. For the purpose of comparison between the three cohorts, a 24-hour recall diet survey, similar to that conducted in Honolulu and Puerto Rico in 1965, was conducted between 1966 and 1969 for 859 men from The Framingham Heart Study, then aged 45-64 and with no history of heart disease. This explained the four year follow-up period for the Framingham dietary subgroup, compared to the six-year follow-up for the comparator cohorts of Honolulu and Puerto Rico.

Methodology: Participants in The Framingham Heart Study were examined at study entry and every two years thereafter. An extensive medical history was recorded at baseline including: family history of cardiovascular disease in parents, siblings, and children; and disease suffered by the participant in the past such as diphtheria, scarlet fever, sore throat, rheumatic fever, or other chronic diseases. Previous operations were recorded. Evidence of hypertension or heart disease was investigated through questioning (and subsequently in the physical examination looking for signs of oedema/varicose veins). Lifestyle factors, such as hours of sleep, alcohol and cigarette consumption were documented. Average weight at 5-year intervals from the age of 25 was recorded. Evidence of anxiety or emotional upset was sought with questions about

ulcers, headaches and stress symptoms and historical and current use of drugs or medicines was ascertained (Dawber, Meadors and Moore, 1951).

A physical examination was performed independently by at least two physicians, aimed at detecting evidence of previous heart disease. A 12-lead electrocardiogram was performed and chest x rays were taken. Height, weight, chest and waist circumference, and estimate of body build were recorded at this medical. Blood pressure was measured. A blood sample was tested for: haemoglobin; serum cholesterol; uric acid; glucose and syphilis. Urine was tested for protein (Dawber, Meadors and Moore, 1951; Dawber, Moore and Mann, 1957).

Outcomes – CHD deaths: Four year follow-up incidence of CHD was presented in 1981, too late for the deliberations of the US committee (Gordon et al., 1981). After 4 years of follow-up: 780 men remained CHD-free (table 2, p.502); 47 had died from any cause; 14 had died from CHD (table 9, p.507); 37 had suffered a myocardial infarction (MI) and 28 had incurred other forms of CHD, mainly angina pectoris (table 2, p.502) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels were not reported in such a way that the diet-heart hypothesis could be examined. Mean serum cholesterol levels were reported by grams of starch intake (table 13, p.510), as it was reported that “there was an inverse relation between starch intake and serum cholesterol, but it was too weak to explain fully the inverse starch-CHD association” (p.500) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Diet: The association of CHD deaths with dietary information was presented in 1981 (Gordon et al., 1981). There was no evidence that total fat, saturated fat, monounsaturated or polyunsaturated fat were associated with CHD incidence or deaths.

The total fat intake of men CHD-free was a mean of 114 g per day. The total fat intake of men who suffered some CHD was 112 g per day. The total fat intake of men who died from CHD or suffered an MI was 106 g/day (table 2, p.502). The total fat intake of men who died from CHD was 112 g/day; the total fat intake of men who survived was 114 g/day (table 9, p.507). The corresponding figures for saturated fat were 44 g/day CHD-free; 43 g/day some CHD; 39 g/day death/MI (table 2, p.502); 46 g/day death from CHD; 44 g/day alive (table 9, p.507) (Gordon et al., 1981). None of these findings was significant.

The significant finding ($p<0.05$) was that the calorie intake was higher in those who remained CHD-free – a mean of 2,622 calories per day compared with a mean of 2,369 calories per day for those who died or had an MI (table 2, p.502) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Diet-heart hypothesis: No evidence was found for any association between deaths from CHD or incidence of CHD with total dietary fat or dietary saturated fat. No data were presented for any association between serum cholesterol and CHD.

Outcomes – Other: There was a significant ($p<0.01$) inverse association between alcohol intake and development of CHD. Men who were CHD-free after 4 years consumed an average of 25 g of alcohol per day; those who developed any form of CHD (death, MI, angina) consumed an average of 12 g of alcohol per day. Those who died of CHD or suffered an MI consumed an average of 10 g of alcohol per day; this was also statistically significant ($p<0.01$) (table 2, p.502) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were the rigour of The Framingham Heart Study design and execution and the dietary fat data being reported by CHD and CHD-free outcomes. The limitations were the single gender and the limited age range studied and all subjects drawn from one location.

There was no evidence of selection bias (Fig. 5.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). Framingham was chosen for its attributes relevant to achieving successful outcomes: participant numbers, retention, medical facilities etc. The comprehensive census and other actions taken to ensure participation ensured that the study was highly inclusive of available men.

There was evidence of blinding (Fig. 5.2). “The death data arose from the files of medical examiners, state and local health departments, and the clinical or autopsy reports of hospital deaths” (p.5) (Dawber, Moore and Mann, 1957).

There was little evidence of attrition bias for this sub group of Framingham. 859 men were enrolled into this dietary comparison study and all were accounted for as CHD-free, deceased or having suffered MI or other CHD, at the 4-year follow-up (Fig. 5.2).

There was no evidence of selective reporting for this sub group dietary study (Fig. 5.2). The presentation of cholesterol data by starch intake (Gordon et al., 1981) was unhelpful for analysis of the impact of serum cholesterol on CHD, but did not suggest bias.

This study was available to both the US and UK dietary committees, but the dietary data were available to the UK committee only. As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, this

study did not examine the association between serum cholesterol and coronary heart deaths or disease. It did examine the association between total and saturated dietary fat and CHD and found no evidence of an association. The two main conclusions of the study were 1) that there was a significant association between higher calorie intake and lower CHD and 2) that there was a significant association between higher alcohol intake and lower CHD.

5) The Honolulu Heart Program (Gordon et al., 1981; Kagan et al., 1974)

Type of observational study: a prospective cohort study.

Objectives: The Honolulu Heart Program had a dual purpose. It was part of a three cohort study to examine the incidence and mortality from CHD of Japanese men in three different locations – Japan (Hiroshima and Nagasaki); California and Honolulu – to ascertain if the study of the same ethnic group, in different locations, could yield insights into CHD and risk factors. The Honolulu Heart Program was also designed to serve as a comparator cohort to Framingham and Puerto Rico in the study of CHD in males aged 45-64 with no previous evidence of CHD (Gordon et al., 1981). 7,272 men from Honolulu were recruited to compare and contrast with 859 men, a sub group of The Framingham Heart Study and 8,218 men from Puerto Rico in an attempt to examine “Diet and its relation to coronary heart disease and death in three populations” (Gordon et al., 1981). The three cohorts were in defined locations, with minimal loss to follow-up likely over up to six years.

Participants/Populations: The Honolulu Heart Program involved 7,272 men, aged 45 to 64 years and free from CHD at baseline. All men of Japanese ancestry, born between 1900 and 1919 and listed on the Honolulu selective service records for World War II and still resident on the island formed the eligible pool. Attempts to locate the men were made through searches of telephone, business and state agency records. Of the estimated 14,426 men meeting initial criteria, 11,148 were located (excluding residents of chronic care institutions) and 9,878 returned a completed questionnaire in early 1965 (Kagan et al., 1974). 7,272 of these men were free from previous heart disease and willing to participate in the study and they were first examined between 1965 and 1968.

Methodology: The methodology was documented in the 1974 publication (Kagan et al., 1974). Self-administered questionnaires were completed by each participant to gather basic demographic and socio-economic information. The questionnaire also covered general health status, usual physical activity, smoking history and dietary habits. At the baseline meeting, detailed information was obtained by a nurse on the family and

medical history of close family members, especially incidence of cardiovascular disease. The physical examination included: height, weight, skinfold measurements; blood pressure; timed vital capacity and a 12-lead electrocardiogram. A glucose tolerance test was undertaken for men free from diabetes. Uric acid levels were tested. Blood cholesterol was measured with the Auto-Analyzer N-24 A method. Dietary data were obtained by a one hour interview with a trained dietician at first attendance at the clinic. The 24-hour recall of the previous day's diet was the chosen method.

Outcomes – CHD deaths: Six year follow-up incidence of CHD was presented in 1981 (Gordon et al., 1981), too late for the deliberations of the US committee. After 6 years of follow-up: 7,008 men remained CHD-free (table 4, p.504); 395 had died from any cause; 78 had died from CHD (table 11, p.509); 86 had suffered a myocardial infarction (MI) and 100 had incurred other forms of CHD, mainly angina pectoris (table 4, p.504) (Gordon et al., 1981)

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels: As with the Framingham sub group, mean serum cholesterol levels were not reported in such a way that the diet-heart hypothesis could be examined. Mean serum cholesterol levels were reported by grams of starch intake (table 13, p.510), as it was reported that “there was an inverse relation between starch intake and serum cholesterol, but it was too weak to explain fully the inverse starch-CHD association” (p.500) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Diet: The association of CHD deaths with dietary information was presented in 1981 (Gordon et al., 1981). There was no evidence that total fat, saturated fat, monounsaturated or polyunsaturated fat was associated with CHD incidence or deaths.

The total fat intake of men CHD-free was a mean of 87 g per day. The total fat intake of men who suffered some CHD was 86 g per day. The total fat intake of men who died from CHD or suffered an MI was 86 g/day (table 4, p.504). The total fat intake of men who died from CHD was 86 g/day; the total fat intake of men who survived was 87 g/day (table 11, p.509). The corresponding figures for saturated fat were 32 g/day CHD-free; 32 g/day some CHD; 31 g/day death/MI (table 4, p.504); 32 g/day death from CHD; 32 g/day alive (table 11, p.509) (Gordon et al., 1981). None of these findings was significant.

The significant finding ($p < 0.01$) was that the calorie intake was higher in those who remained CHD-free – a mean of 2,319 calories per day compared with a mean of 2,210

calories per day for those who suffered any form of CHD and 2,149 for those who died or had an MI (table 4, p.504) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Diet-heart hypothesis: No evidence was found for any association between deaths from CHD or incidence of CHD with total dietary fat or dietary saturated fat. No data were presented for any association between serum cholesterol and CHD.

Outcomes – Other: There was a significant ($p<0.05$) association between starch intake and remaining free from CHD. Those who were free from CHD after 6 years consumed an average of 165 g of starch per day; those who experienced any form of CHD consumed an average of 155 g of starch per day (table 4, p.504). Those who died of CHD consumed an average of 144 g of starch per day. This was statistically significant ($p<0.01$) (table 11, p.509) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Men who consumed more alcohol were less likely to develop CHD ($p<0.01$), but more likely to die of causes other than CHD ($p<0.01$).

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were the number of participants, the length of follow-up, the rigour of the examination process and the dietary fat data being reported by CHD and CHD-free outcomes. The limitations were the single gender and the limited age range studied and all subjects located on one island. The study of Japanese men alone was a limitation for generalisability, but a strength for homogeneity of participants. This attribute was necessary for the secondary cohort comparison of Japanese men in three different locations.

There was no evidence of selection bias (Fig. 5.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). Having defined the subject pool as Japanese men, aged 45-64 years, living in Honolulu, systematic efforts were made to include all eligible participants.

There was evidence of blinding (Fig. 5.2). The end points used for CHD incidence were definite MI by ECG and CHD death. Death was attributed to CHD if it was sudden (within one hour of onset of illness), and without another disease to account for it, or if it was not-sudden, but with course and evidence consistent with CHD. Special efforts were made to evaluate deaths that occurred both in the hospital and out-of-hospital. Autopsy information was obtained in all cases where an autopsy was performed. Autopsies were undertaken in the majority of deaths in hospital (Gordon et al., 1974).

There was no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 5.2). 7,272 men were enrolled into the study and all were accounted for as CHD-free, deceased or having suffered MI or other CHD, at the 6-year follow-up.

There was no evidence of selective reporting for this sub group dietary study (Fig. 5.2). The presentation of cholesterol data by starch intake (Gordon et al., 1981) was unhelpful for analysis of the impact of serum cholesterol on CHD, but did not suggest bias.

This study was available to both the US and UK dietary committees, but the dietary data (Gordon et al., 1981) were available to the UK committee only. As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, this study did not examine the association between serum cholesterol and coronary heart deaths or disease. It did examine the association between total and saturated dietary fat and CHD and found no evidence of an association. The main conclusions of the study were 1) there was a significant association between higher calorie intake and lower CHD and 2) there was a significant association between higher starch intake and remaining free from CHD and 3) there was a significant association between higher alcohol intake and remaining free from CHD but there was a concomitant significant association between higher alcohol intake and dying from causes other than CHD.

6) The Puerto Rico Heart Health Program (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1978; Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1980; Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1977; Gordon et al., 1981)

Type of observational study: a prospective cohort study.

Objectives: “The Puerto Rico Heart Health Program, was begun for the purpose of investigating the relationship of risk factors to prevalence and incidence of CHD in 10,000 rural and urban Puerto Rican men ages 45 to 65” (p.2092) (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1977). The study started in 1965 and planned to examine the characteristics of a male population, without evidence of coronary heart disease, over a number of years. The final follow-up was conducted in 1980.

Participants/Populations: The study involved 8,218 men, aged 45 to 64 years and free from coronary heart disease at baseline: 2,420 men living in rural communities and 5,798 men in urban environments. The men resided within a geographic radius of 25 miles of urban San Juan (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1980) enabling the study to evaluate heart disease among men in a similar location, but with urban-rural contrast.

A pool of 10,000 men was identified as sufficient to yield significant numbers of CHD cases during years of follow-up. A house-to-house census of the region was conducted between October 1964 and June 1965 and publicity campaigns were undertaken using

mediums of posters, newspapers, television and civic organisations (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969). Appointment letters inviting men to attend a clinic on a specified date were sent to subjects from the census list in numerical order. Where subjects owned a telephone, a call was made the day before the appointment to improve attendance. Subjects failing to keep appointments were approached by neighbourhood committees. Rural participation was aided by study staff taking equipment to establish temporary clinics at local town halls, churches, restaurants and even cockfight rings. Men were recruited upon attendance at a clinic between 1965 and 1968. The aim of securing at least 80% participation was achieved (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969).

Methodology: The methodology was documented in the 1969 publication (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969). A social interview recorded: education and occupation of participant and his father; income; cause and age of death of parents; smoking habits; and physical activity. Full medical history was taken at this baseline interview including past history of heart disease or other illnesses, operations, hospitalisations and medications. A physical examination was undertaken which included: height, weight, skinfold measurements; thyroid abnormalities; evidence of pulmonary disease; full cardio evaluation – rhythms, murmurs etc; blood pressure; liver analysis; evidence of ankle edema, varicose veins, or other signs of peripheral vascular disease; neurological examination; physiological assessment of anxiety; vital capacity; 12-lead electrocardiogram; urine test for sugar and albumin; blood sample for syphilis, glucose and serum cholesterol. Blood cholesterol was measured with a modified Huang method (Huang et al., 1961). Dietary data were obtained by a one hour interview with a trained dietician at first attendance at the clinic. The 24-hour recall of the previous day's diet was the chosen method.

Outcomes – CHD deaths: Six year follow-up incidence of CHD was presented in 1981 (Gordon et al., 1981), too late for the deliberations of the US committee. After 6 years of follow-up: 7,932 men remained CHD-free (table 3, p.503); 402 had died from any cause; 71 had died from CHD (table 10, p.508); 92 had suffered a myocardial infarction (MI) and 123 had incurred other forms of CHD, mainly angina pectoris (table 3, p.503) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels were not reported in such a way that the diet-heart hypothesis could be examined. Mean serum cholesterol levels were reported by grams of starch intake (table 13, p.510), as it was reported that “there

was an inverse relation between starch intake and serum cholesterol, but it was too weak to explain fully the inverse starch-CHD association” (p.500) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Other publications relating to the study focused on the rural-urban aspect of the population. Baseline mean serum cholesterol levels were reported as 195 mg/dl for rural men and 205 mg/dl for urban men (table 1, p.1820) (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1980). The 1978 two and a half year follow-up compared CHD incidence between the rural and urban men, rather than comparing cholesterol and diet risk factors between those who went on to develop CHD and those who didn't. This paper concluded: “The age-adjusted CHD incidence rate for urban men was 1.5 times that of rural men” (p.206) (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1978). Rural men, on average, had lower blood pressure, serum cholesterol and blood sugar, but more of them smoked. It was reported that factors seen as risk characteristics did not fully explain the differences in CHD incidence, inferring that living in an urban environment was a risk factor *per se*: “More rural areas had a lower incidence than less rural without any distinct differences in risk factor levels, and persons who had moved into urban areas or from one urban area to another had a higher incidence than men who had always lived in the same urban area, despite the fact that there was no distinct difference among them in CHD risk factors” (p.214) (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1978).

Outcomes – Diet: The association of CHD deaths with dietary information was presented in 1981 (Gordon et al., 1981). There was no evidence that total fat, saturated fat, monounsaturated or polyunsaturated fat was associated with CHD incidence or deaths.

The total fat intake of men CHD-free was a mean of 95 grams per day. The total fat intake of men who suffered some CHD was 94 grams per day. The total fat intake of men who died from CHD or suffered an MI was 92 g/day (table 3, p.503). The total fat intake of men who died from CHD was 94 g/day; the total fat intake of men who survived was 96 g/day (table 10, p.508). The corresponding figures for saturated fat were 36 g/day CHD-free; 35 g/day some CHD; 33 g/day death/MI (table 3, p.503); 34 g/day death from CHD; 36 g/day alive (table 10, p.508) (Gordon et al., 1981). None of these findings was significant.

The significant finding ($p<0.05$) was that the calorie intake was higher in those who remained CHD-free – a mean of 2,395 calories per day compared with a mean of 2,289 calories per day for those who suffered any form of CHD and 2,223 for those who died or had an MI (table 3, p.503) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Outcomes – Diet-heart hypothesis: No evidence was found for any association between deaths from CHD or incidence of CHD with total dietary fat or dietary saturated fat. No data were presented for any association between serum cholesterol and CHD.

Outcomes – Other: There was a significant ($p < 0.01$) inverse association between starch intake and all-cause mortality. Those who were alive after 6 years consumed an average of 180 grams of starch per day; those who died from any cause consumed an average of 161 grams of starch per day. Those who died of CHD consumed an average of 171 grams of starch per day; this was not statistically significant (table 10, p.508) (Gordon et al., 1981).

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were the number of participants, the length of follow-up, the rigour of the examination process and the dietary fat data being reported by CHD and CHD-free outcomes. The limitations were the single gender and the limited age range studied and all subjects drawn from one 25 mile radius location.

There was no evidence of selection bias (Fig. 5.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). The region was chosen to be able to contrast an urban and rural population in a proximate location. The comprehensive census and other actions taken to ensure participation ensured that the study was highly inclusive of available men.

There was evidence of blinding, as reported for The Honolulu Heart Program (Fig. 5.2). The end points used for CHD incidence were definite MI by ECG and CHD death. Death was attributed to CHD if it was sudden (within one hour of onset of illness), and without another disease to account for it, or if it was not-sudden, but with course and evidence consistent with CHD. Special efforts were made to evaluate deaths that occurred both in the hospital and out-of-hospital. Autopsy information was obtained in all cases where an autopsy was performed. Autopsies were undertaken in the majority of deaths in hospital (Gordon et al., 1974).

There was no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 5.2). 8,218 men were enrolled into the study and all were accounted for as CHD-free, deceased or having suffered MI or other CHD, at the 6-year follow-up.

There was no evidence of selective reporting (Fig. 5.2). The presentation of cholesterol data for urban vs. rural populations (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1978) or by starch intake (Gordon et al., 1981) was unhelpful for analysis of the impact of serum cholesterol on CHD, but did not suggest bias.

This study was available to both the US and UK dietary committees, but the dietary data (Gordon et al., 1981) were available to the UK committee only. As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, this study did not examine the association between serum cholesterol and coronary heart deaths or disease. It did examine the association between total and saturated dietary fat and CHD and found no evidence of an association. The two main conclusions of the study were 1) that there was a significant association between higher calorie intake and lower CHD and 2) that there was a significant difference between living in a rural environment and lower CHD.

Framingham – an extended search

Five of the six cohort studies have been fully captured in this systematic review. For The Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963), The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a), The London Bus and Bank Study (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977), The Honolulu Heart Program (Gordon et al., 1981; Kagan et al., 1974) and the Puerto Rico Heart Health Program (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981), the original participant base was quantified and accounted for in this systematic review. The exception was The Framingham Heart Study, which originally recruited 5,209 men and women between the ages of 30 and 59 in 1948, and from which a sub group of 859 men, aged between 45-64, was extracted to study risk factors for CHD (Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970). This sub group undertook a dietary interview, so that diet could be assessed as a possible risk factor for CHD, and the methodology was consistent with The Honolulu Heart Program and the Puerto Rico Heart Health Program to facilitate findings emerging from each individual study and from comparison between similar studies.

Framingham literature has been extensively searched to ascertain if any other epidemiological evidence for associations between serum cholesterol levels, dietary fat (total and/or saturated) and CHD was available before dietary fat guidelines were first set in 1977 (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977).

The systematic review above noted that dietary evaluation was not introduced until Exam 4 of the Framingham examination cycle (Gordon and Kannel, 1970). Exam 4 covered the period 1954 to 1958 (National Heart Institute, 1968). The six year review of The Framingham Heart Study, published in 1961, made no mention of diet or dietary fat as a possible risk factor (Kannel et al., 1961).

The methodology for, and objectives of, dietary evaluation was comprehensively documented in 1962 (Mann et al., 1962). The six dietary hypotheses were documented

as: the calorie balance; level of animal fat intake; level of vegetable fat intake; level of protein intake; level of cholesterol intake; and iron intake as related to hematologic values (table I, p.201). This confirmed that assessment of total fat would be possible, with the addition of animal and vegetable fat, but that assessment of saturated fat would not be possible, as this is present in all food containing fat, whether of animal or vegetable origin (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013). Mann reported: “No systematic attempt was made to compute fatty acid content of the diets because no reasonably reliable tables of fatty acid composition of foods as consumed were available” (p.201) (Mann et al., 1962). Not all Framingham participants completed a dietary assessment. 1,049 subjects were drawn from the pool of original recruits, who had attended at least the third or the fourth cycle of examinations (p.211). 912 successful interviews were completed: 437 men and 475 women. This represented an 87% successful interview rate for both sexes, with some participants refusing to undertake a dietary assessment, some interviews being of insufficient quality and some people moving or dying before the dietary assessment took place (table IX, p.212) (Mann et al., 1962).

One of the last Framingham review articles, to precede the February 1977 US dietary guidelines, was published in July 1976 (Kannel, McGee and Gordon, 1976). There was no mention of diet, or dietary fat. This paper documented standardised regression coefficients for the incidence of cardiovascular disease (CVD) for specific risk factors for Framingham men and women observed over 18 years (table II, p.49). No significance levels were reported. The data showed high variation, for men and women, and different types of CVD (coronary disease, brain infarction, intermittent claudication, and hypertensive heart failure) between the five risk factors examined: systolic blood pressure; smoking; electrocardiogram of left ventricular hypertrophy; glucose intolerance; and serum cholesterol level at the age of 45 (the age constraint for cholesterol was noted as necessary “since its role varies with age, being greatest for young adults and decreasing with age” (p.49)). The highest correlation coefficient was 0.602 for smoking and intermittent claudication in men. The lowest correlation coefficient was -0.005 for smoking and brain infarction in women. Systolic blood pressure correlation coefficients were high for men and women with brain infarction and hypertensive heart failure: 0.587 (men/brain infarction); 0.542 (men/hypertensive heart failure); 0.478 (women/brain infarction); 0.504 (women/hypertensive heart failure). Serum cholesterol at age 45 had a correlation coefficient of 0.441 for men and coronary disease and 0.391 for women and coronary disease. Serum cholesterol at age

45 had a correlation coefficient of 0.403 for men and total CVD and 0.301 for women and total CVD.

The Kannel *et al* article collated all data gathered over 18 years on risk factors and incidence of CVD for men and women to establish coefficients for calculating the risk of developing CVD in the next eight years for a man or woman initially free from CVD. The highest coefficients were glucose intolerance (0.602) and smoking (0.558) for men and glucose tolerance (0.682) for women. Smoking did not emerge as a major risk factor for women. Serum cholesterol had a very small coefficient: 0.026 for men and 0.016 for women (table IV, p.50) (Kannel, McGee and Gordon, 1976). The probability by age and sex of developing CVD in 8 years (incidence per 1,000 people) was reported (table VI, p.50). This showed the scale of age as an overriding risk factor for CVD. Per 1,000 people, 18 men and 5 women, aged 35, would probably develop CVD within 8 years; compared with 229 men and 199 women aged 70: rates 13 times higher for men and 40 times higher for women in the older age group.

The complete Framingham Heart Study bibliography has been published (Framingham Heart Study, 2015). There were 15 publications emanating from the study in the 1950s, none of which contained any dietary references in the title (“diet”, “dietary” or “fat”). In the 1960s there were 80 Framingham publications. Three mentioned diet/dietary in the title; all three documented the methodology for diet assessment in the study (one was a magazine article preceding the journal article) (Dawber et al., 1962; Mann et al., 1962). In the 1970s, 181 publications derived from The Framingham Heart Study. None of these contained dietary references in the title. The Framingham Heart Study provided no data relating to dietary fat for the US guidelines committee to consider. The information available to the UK committee was reported in the above systematic review: no difference in total fat or saturated fat intake between men who subsequently developed CHD and those who did not.

Table 5.2 Outcome data from included prospective cohort studies for: study name; participant number and age range; years of follow-up; serum cholesterol, total fat and saturated fat for CHD-free vs. CHD deaths (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974) or CHD-free vs. development of CHD (Keys, 1970a; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Paul et al., 1963); and other significant associations found.

Study	Men/Age	CHD-free?	Follow-up yrs	Cholesterol CHD/Non	Total fat CHD/Non	Sat fat CHD/Non	Other Significant associations with CHD
Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963)	1,989 (40-55)	Y	4	CHD/Non 272/247 mean mg/dl	CHD/Non 148/152 g/day (*)	CHD/Non 59/59 g/day (*)	Age of death of father, smoking, coffee, elevated blood pressure
Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a) Note 1	12,770 (40-59)	98%	5	r = 0.76	r = 0.40 (*)	r = 0.84	Previous MI. NO association found with CHD & activity, smoking or weight

The following data were available to the UK Committee only:

London bank and bus study (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977)	337 (30-67)	Y	20	Note 2 3-5.6 7 5.6-6.5 13 6.5-8.6 16	Note 3 (*) 30-39% 18 38-43% 10 41-56% 17	N/A	Age of participant. Smoking. Higher calorie intake/cereal fibre & lower CHD
Framingham (Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970)	859 (45-64)	Y	4	N/A	CHD death/alive 112/114 g/day (*)	CHD death/alive 46/44 g/day (*)	Higher calorie intake & lower CHD. Higher alcohol intake & lower CHD

Study	Men/Age	CHD-free?	Follow-up yrs	Cholesterol CHD/Non	Total fat CHD/Non	Sat fat CHD/Non	Other Significant associations with CHD
Honolulu (Gordon et al., 1981; Kagan et al., 1974)	7,272 (45-64)	Y	6	N/A	CHD death/alive 86/87 g/day (*)	CHD death/alive 32/32 g/day (*)	Higher calorie intake & lower CHD. Higher starch intake & lower CHD. Higher alcohol intake & lower CHD
Puerto Rico (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981)	8,218 (45-64)	Y	6	N/A	CHD death/alive 94/96 g/day (*)	CHD death/alive 34/36 g/day (*)	Higher calorie intake & lower CHD. Rural living & lower CHD

Table notes: N/A = data not available; MI = Myocardial Infarction

(*) Not statistically significant

Note 1: The Pearson correlation coefficients presented in this row represent 13 cohorts (both Japanese and the Rome railroad cohorts were missing). The coefficients represent the relationship between serum cholesterol, total dietary fat and saturated fat intake for the 13 cohorts and CHD deaths and infarctions. Data for CHD deaths alone were not presented. Data for men without heart disease on entry were not available. The data did not compare fat/cholesterol of those with CHD vs. those without. The correlations apply to fat/cholesterol data for cohorts relative to each other.

Note 2: Tertiles of cholesterol in mmol/l and number of CHD cases, not deaths, in each tertile.

Note 3: % of dietary intake accounted for by total fat and number of CHD cases, not deaths, in each tertile.

Fig. 5.2 Methodological quality summary: review authors' judgements about each methodological quality item for each included study (Higgins et al., 2011).

	Cohort appropriately reflected wider population (selection bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)
Key				
Low risk of bias				
High risk of bias				
Unclear risk of bias				
Western Electric/Paul (1963)				
Seven Countries Study/Keys (1970)				
London bank & bus men/Morris (1977)				
Framingham/Gordon (1970 & 1981)				
Honolulu/Kagan (1974 & 1981)				
Puerto Rico/Garcia-Palmieri (1969 & 1981)				

Results

Participants and Study Design

The six identified prospective cohort studies included 31,445 male participants. All but 337 participants (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977) were over the age of 40 at baseline and were followed for a minimum of 4 years and a maximum of 20 years.

The mean duration of the six cohorts was 7.5 ± 6.2 years. The weighted mean duration (person years by participants) was 5.6 ± 0.8 years.

Five cohort studies excluded men with previous heart disease. The one study that included men with previous heart disease enabled examination of men healthy at baseline in some circumstances (Keys, 1970a).

All studies had complete outcome data, showing no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 5.2). Two studies were unclear in the assessment of blinding of outcome (Keys, 1970a; Paul et al., 1963). The three comparator population studies showed no evidence of selection bias (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974). The London Bus and Bank Study (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977) and The Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963) were assessed as having some selection bias for drawing from limited occupations and/or corporations. The selection bias in The Seven Countries Study was stronger, having initially been informed by Keys' analysis of country data (Keys, 1953a) and having subsequently relied greatly upon friendship for cohort selection. Five studies were judged low risk for reporting bias, as there was no evidence of any data being withheld. The Seven Countries Study was judged as unclear for reporting bias, as the presentation of data according to thresholds introduced subjectivity (Fig. 5.2) (Higgins et al., 2011).

In the absence of meta-analysis, statistical review of study heterogeneity is not possible. The studies were homogenous in their focus on men; largely free from previous heart disease and in their study aims to review the impact of dietary fat on CHD mortality for a follow-up period of at least four years. The age of participants was an area of homogeneity: three of the studies included men aged 45-64 (52% of participants) (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974); two of the studies included men between 40 and 55 or 59 (47% of participants) (Keys, 1970a; Paul et al., 1963); only one study, accounting for 1% of participants, included a wider age range of 30-67 (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Areas of heterogeneity were related to the populations chosen. London bankers, Japanese fishermen, American railroad workers and Puerto Rican farmers, like all the cohorts studied, differed by location, climate, politics, income, ethnicity, genetics, traditional diet, soil quality, and other confounding factors.

Examination of the dietary guidelines

None of the six cohorts examined either of the introduced dietary guidelines: a total fat consumption of 30%, or a saturated fat consumption of 10%, of energy intake. Three studies examined the total fat intake and the saturated fat intake, as a percentage of calorie intake, for men who died from CHD compared to men who remained alive (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974). One study examined the total fat intake and the saturated fat intake, as a percentage of calorie intake, for men who developed CHD compared to those who

didn't (the comparison was not available for CHD deaths) (Paul et al., 1963). One study reviewed total dietary fat in tertiles and noted no difference in the saturated fat intake of men in different calorie intake tertiles (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). One study compared total and saturated fat intake by 7 countries and 16 cohorts, as opposed to by men who developed CHD compared with those who didn't in each region (Keys, 1970a).

Outcomes: All-cause mortality

Across 6 studies, involving 31,445 participants, there were 1,521 deaths from all-causes during the period of follow-up. The death rate from all-causes was 4.84%, during the mean follow-up of 7.5 ± 6.2 years.

CHD mortality

Across 6 studies, involving 31,445 participants, there were 360 deaths from CHD during the period of follow-up. The death rate from CHD was 1.14%, during the mean follow-up of 7.5 ± 6.2 years.

The death rates contrast with the 30% death rate for the six RCTs reviewed in Chapter Three and reinforce the high death rate in secondary studies. The one study that included men with previous heart disease found that the death rate from CHD for those with pre-existing MI was 20.9%. The death rate from CHD for those without previous MI was 1.0% (Keys, 1970a).

Significance reported by the studies

None of the six studies found any significant relationship between CHD deaths and total dietary fat intake. One of the six studies found a statistically significant relationship between CHD deaths and saturated dietary fat intake (Keys, 1970a).

Serum cholesterol levels

One of the studies found a statistically significant association between CHD incidence and mean serum cholesterol (Paul et al., 1963) and another of the studies found a statistically significant association between CHD deaths and infarctions and median serum cholesterol (Keys, 1970a).

Discussion

The main findings of this systematic review are that the epidemiological evidence available to the dietary committees did not support the introduction of dietary fat guidelines. There were two prospective cohort studies available to the US committee

(Keys, 1970a; Paul et al., 1963) and an additional four available to the UK committee (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Four of the studies found a significant relationship between higher calorie intake and lower incidence of CHD (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). The Framingham and Honolulu studies found a significant relationship between higher alcohol intake and lower incidence of CHD (Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974). The London and Honolulu studies found a significant relationship between higher starch/cereal intake and lower incidence of CHD (Kagan et al., 1974; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977).

Design limitations

As was reported with the review of RCT evidence in Chapter Three, the fundamental design limitation of epidemiological evidence available to inform the dietary committees of 1977 and 1983 was that all studies included men only. The epidemiological evidence available at the time of dietary guidelines being introduced, largely evaluated healthy men, while the RCTs available at the time had studied secondary males.

One study alone provided support for the diet-heart hypothesis (Keys, 1970a). This study had the most serious limitations: first of selection bias and second of not comparing the development of CHD against non development of CHD in each cohort. Rather it was an inter country comparison, comparing the development of CHD in one cohort/country with the development of CHD in another cohort/country, which therefore introduced many other confounders. This study also contradicted evidence found by contemporary studies on the association of smoking, weight and sedentary behaviour with CHD.

Study conclusions

Five of the studies made no mention of dietary fat in their conclusions. The Western Electric Study concluded: “No relation was encountered between body weight, mean blood sugar levels, lipoprotein lipase levels, or diet (other than coffee), and the development of coronary heart disease” (p30) (Paul et al., 1963). Morris *et al* identified healthy and unhealthy patterns of behaviour: “Meanwhile, a pattern of healthy living may have been identified: high energy intake and expenditure, high intake of cereal

fibre, no cigarettes, with relatively little proneness to heart attack; and another behaviour pattern, of low energy intake and physical inactivity, low intake of cereal fibre, smoking cigarettes-carrying a relatively high risk” (p.1313) (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). The 1981 publication combining the Framingham, Honolulu and Puerto Rico cohorts summarised the findings of the three studies together: “In conclusion, men who developed MI or died of CHD consumed significantly fewer calories (but weighed more) and consumed less alcohol than average” (p.514) (Gordon et al., 1981).

As noted in the review of the literature, the verbatim findings of The Seven Countries Study set out the tripartite relationship between CHD, serum cholesterol and saturated dietary fat:

- “The incidence rate of CHD tends to be directly related to the distributions of serum cholesterol values.”
- “The average serum cholesterol values of the cohorts tended to be directly related to the average proportion of calories provided by saturated fats in the diet.”
- “The CHD incidence rates of the cohorts are just as closely related to the dietary saturated fatty acids as to the serum cholesterol level”(p.I-194) (Keys, 1970e).

The Seven Countries Study was available to both dietary committees. While the UK nutritional guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) made reference to The Seven Countries Study, the US committee document (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) did not. However, the US committee document reported that: “The basic research is strongly corroborated by epidemiological studies of populations throughout the world who live quite well on a diet containing as little as 10 percent calories from fat” (p.XL) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) and the only study of populations throughout the world at that time was The Seven Countries Study.

Other associations

The correlation coefficients established by The Seven Countries Study were strong. However, as shown in the review of the literature, other strong correlations were found with factors from animal protein to television sets (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957; Yudkin, 1957).

The 25 year follow-up to The Seven Countries Study (Menotti et al., 1993) calculated Pearson correlation coefficients for mean serum cholesterol levels at baseline and CHD deaths at 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25 years of follow-up. The Pearson correlation coefficient

was calculated as 0.72 for baseline cholesterol and CHD deaths at 25 years. The author of this thesis used the data in the 1993 Menotti article to repeat the correlations found with CHD death rates and mean serum cholesterol to understand the data and methodology used. The same methodology was then used to explore alternative correlations. The strongest relationship found was for CHD death rates and the latitude of the country or cohort in The Seven Countries Study. The correlation coefficient for CHD deaths and latitude of the cohort was 0.93. The correlation coefficient for CHD deaths and latitude of the country was 0.96 (Appendix 9). While Keys did find a strong association with median serum cholesterol and CHD deaths, there were stronger associations that were discoverable.

The latitude finding offers an alternative explanation for the observed relationship with cholesterol and CHD. Vitamin D is made when sunshine synthesises cholesterol in skin membranes (Gillie, 2010). In cohorts further away from the equator, cholesterol is less able to be turned into vitamin D. Population mean serum cholesterol levels are higher and concomitantly population mean vitamin D levels are lower. Higher CHD could be associated with lower vitamin D, with cholesterol a marker, not a maker, of heart disease (Scragg, 1981).

Chapter Three (Harcombe et al., 2015), reported that the dietary fat guidelines were not supported by RCT evidence available at the time of their introduction. This chapter finds that the epidemiological evidence available at the time did not support the introduced dietary guidelines. Both chapters recorded serious limitations with the availability of primary prevention, both-sex, studies, which are the ones most likely to have generalisability for whole populations.

Chapter Six

A systematic review and meta-analysis of the epidemiological evidence currently available to evaluate if the introduced dietary fat guidelines have been supported in retrospect

Introduction

The systematic review in Chapter Five was the first to examine the epidemiological evidence available at the time of the introduction of national dietary guidelines (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983; Select committee on nutrition and human needs, 1977).

This chapter reports on a systematic review and meta-analysis to assess if the published epidemiological studies available to the dietary committees and those published afterwards, supported the recommendations on dietary fat. With this in mind, the hypothesis is that epidemiological evidence currently available does not support the contention that reducing dietary fat intake, to 30% of total calories and saturated fat intake to 10% of total calories, would contribute to a reduction in CHD risk and/or related mortality. The guidelines have not been changed since they were announced; correspondingly, the validity of their evidence base remains relevant.

Methods

A systematic review was conducted in accordance with the Meta-analysis Of Observational Studies in Epidemiology methodology (MOOSE) (Stroup et al., 2000) (Appendix 10). MOOSE builds upon the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) methodology and uses parts of PRISMA as appropriate, for example the figure for presenting search methodology (Moher et al., 2009). This chapter uses the TOPMOS methodology for extracting data from observational studies, as used in Chapter Five.

Search strategy

A search was undertaken to identify prospective cohort studies that examined the relationship between dietary fat intake, serum cholesterol and mortality from CHD. Exclusion criteria were: clinical trials, randomised or non-randomised; cross-sectional studies; case control studies. Inclusion criteria were: prospective cohort studies; participants were human adults; primary study outcome was CHD mortality; data related to dietary fat consumption were available; data on CHD mortality and serum cholesterol measurements were available.

The search was undertaken on 30 September 2015. Searches of the literature were performed using MEDLINE, Embase and the Cochrane Library (Fig. 6.1). The search was undertaken in August 2015.

Selection of studies

Of 669 identified articles, 607 were rejected upon review of the title and abstract. Of these, 55 were rejected for being review articles. 55 were commentaries, editorials or letters. 39 were clinical trials, 9 were cross sectional or case control studies observational studies. 75 related to conditions other than heart disease, primarily cancer, diabetes, hypertension and obesity. There were 53 studies where animals or children/adolescents were the primary focus. 98 were articles about pharmacology/blood analysis. 123 were rejected for being related to a particular food, nutrient or supplement, rather than dietary fat. A further 40 papers were educational material and 36 reviewed dietary compliance in nutritional studies. 24 articles were mathematical modelling exercises, including meta-analysis. 62 papers remained. 13 were rejected on closer inspection of the full paper: 6 were reviews, 6 were commentaries or expert opinion pieces 1 was educational material. Where an abstract was unavailable, the publication type, journal name and meta-tags were reviewed to assess if the article should be rejected (for example “letter”, “clinical trial”, “paediatric”). Copies of the remaining articles were obtained from university libraries or the British Library. 49 papers, *prima facie*, met the inclusion criteria.

Of the 49 papers, 6 were the studies included in Chapter Five: The Western Electric study (Paul et al., 1963; Shekelle et al., 1981); The Puerto Rico Heart Health Program (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1977; Gordon et al., 1981); The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a); The Framingham Heart Study (Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970); The Honolulu Heart Program (Gordon et al., 1981; Kagan et al., 1974; Yano et al., 1978); and a study conducted in London and the South East (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977). 24 papers were additional publications related to these 6 studies; the majority of these were about The Seven Countries Study. The additional publications were examined for data published after the introduction of the dietary fat guidelines to assess if any Chapter Five studies could be updated. A 1984 paper about The Honolulu Heart Program (McGee et al., 1984) and a 1991 paper about The Framingham Heart Study (Posner et al., 1991) were reviewed, but neither reported CHD mortality.

12 new studies were found (Ascherio et al., 1996; Boniface and Tefft, 2002; Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996; Fehily et al., 1993; Goldbourt, Yaari and Medalie, 1993; Jakobsen et al., 2004; Kushi et al., 1985; Mann et al., 1997; Nagata et al., 2012; Oh et al., 2005; Pietinen et al., 1997; Xu et al., 2006). Seven papers were additional publications related to these studies. Four studies were excluded on closer inspection for not reporting CHD mortality data (Fehily et al., 1993; Goldbourt, Yaari and Medalie, 1993; Jakobsen et al., 2004; Mann et al., 1997) and another one contained CHD mortality data that was not separable from CHD events (Oh et al., 2005). These five studies also failed to meet inclusion criteria for other reasons: no saturated fat data (Fehily et al., 1993; Mann et al., 1997); no total fat data (Goldbourt, Yaari and Medalie, 1993; Mann et al., 1997); no serum cholesterol data (Fehily et al., 1993; Jakobsen et al., 2004; Mann et al., 1997; Oh et al., 2005). Mann *et al* was the only study to review animal fat, not all dietary fat. This study, examining the benefits of a vegetarian diet, reported consumption of total animal fat and saturated animal fat, thus excluding the fat and saturated fat in many non-animal foods (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013).

Six studies were excluded for having no serum cholesterol data (Ascherio et al., 1996; Boniface and Tefft, 2002; Kushi et al., 1985; Nagata et al., 2012; Pietinen et al., 1997; Xu et al., 2006), which left one study meeting the inclusion criteria (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). This study has been systematically reviewed. This study included 4,546 men and women, aged 30-79 and followed them for an average of 12 years, so it had generalisability for the wider population.

To ascertain the validity of eligible observational studies, a pair of reviewers (ZH and BD) worked independently to determine which studies met the inclusion criteria. The same one additional study was agreed upon. Risk of bias was assessed using the Cochrane Collaboration assessment tool (Higgins et al., 2011) for component parts relevant to observational studies, defined as follows: selection bias (cohort appropriately reflected wider population characteristics); detection bias (blinding of outcome assessment); attrition bias (incomplete data outcome); and reporting bias (selective reporting) (Higgins et al., 2011) (Fig. 6.2).

Data Extraction

Table 6.1, following the systematic review, details data extraction from that systematic review of: study name; year of key publications; participant characteristics; whether free from CHD at study entry; years of follow-up; outcomes relating to mean serum

cholesterol, total dietary fat and saturated dietary fat for those who developed/died from CHD and those who didn't.

Table 6.2 sets aside the serum cholesterol component part of the diet-heart hypothesis and the requirement for studies to report serum cholesterol data. This enabled data for dietary fat (total and saturated) and CHD mortality to be examined for seven studies (Ascherio et al., 1996; Boniface and Tefft, 2002; Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996; Kushi et al., 1985; Nagata et al., 2012; Pietinen et al., 1997; Xu et al., 2006). Table 6.2 presents the results for total and saturated dietary fat and CHD deaths for these seven studies.

Statistical Analysis

The data available for the full diet-heart hypothesis evaluation criteria (Table 6.1), including serum cholesterol data, are not conducive to meta-analysis. Three of the studies are presented in a comparable format (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974), but meta-analysis was not possible on these alone as the information required for dichotomous or continuous analysis was not available. The data presented in the other three studies (Keys, 1970a; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Paul et al., 1963) was in different formats and also lacked the information that would enable meta-analysis to be undertaken. The new study identified reported standard deviation data, but meta-analysis is not possible on one study alone (table 2, p.213) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). Table 6.1 presents the available data and illustrates the lack of significant findings.

Meta-analysis was possible for all but one study in Table 6.2 (Kushi et al., 1985). Forest plots for the associations between CHD deaths and total fat and saturated fat are presented in Fig. 6.3 and Fig. 6.4 respectively.

Fig. 6.1 (Moher et al., 2009) Summary of systematic review profile.

Results: Systematic review

The one additional prospective cohort study that met the criteria for systematic review was published in 1996 (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). Data extracted for this study follows the TOPMOS format: Type of observational study; Objectives (of the study); Participants/Populations; Methodology; Outcomes and Study information (design, strengths, limitations etc).

Data for the Cochrane assessment of risk bias have been extracted during the systematic review (Higgins et al., 2011) (Fig. 6.2).

1) The Lipid Research Clinic follow-up Study (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

Type of observational study: a prospective cohort study.

Objectives: The study was designed to examine the relationship between total fat, saturated fat and coronary heart disease mortality, in Canadian men and women, free from CHD, over a 12 year follow-up period. Recruitment for the study took place between 1972 and 1976 and the participants were followed for an average of 12.4 years until June 1987.

Participants/Populations: The study pool involved 4,546 men and women, at least 30 years old, who represented a cross-sectional survey of various North American populations. 2,353 subjects were male; 2,193 were female. The data were analysed in two age groups, not by gender. The age groups chosen were 30 to 59 and 60 to 79 years of age. The rationale was given as “this arbitrary division was chosen to maximise the coronary deaths for analysis in each group” (p.212) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

Methodology: The baseline meeting involved an extensive examination to record the medical and family history of each subject, including use of medication, blood pressure and blood lipid measurements, resting and active electrocardiograms and anthropometric variables.

Dietary data were obtained by a 24-hour dietary recall, administered by a trained nutritionist. Dietary data were coded using the most recent National Heart, Lung and Blood Institute food codebook; coded data were then converted into nutrient values using food tables (p.212) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

Nutritional information was compared for CHD deaths and no CHD deaths for the age groups 30 to 59 and 60 to 79 separately for total energy intake (calories) and dietary cholesterol (mg) and for the following nutrients, which were reported in grams and as a

percentage of total energy intake: total fat; saturated fat; monounsaturated fat; polyunsaturated fat; carbohydrate; protein; and alcohol (table 2, p.213).

Outcomes – CHD deaths: At the end of 12 years, 92 people had died of CHD. 52 of these deaths occurred among 3,925 men and women aged 30-59; 40 of these deaths occurred among 621 men and women aged 60 to 79. Of the 52 deaths in the younger age group, 38 were males and 14 were females, giving death rates of 1.83% and 0.76% for men and women respectively. Of the 40 deaths in the older age group, 27 were males and 13 were females, giving death rates of 9.57% and 3.83% for men and women respectively (table 1, p.213) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

Outcomes – Cholesterol levels: Mean serum cholesterol levels were reported as 6.01 ± 0.96 mmol/l for the 52 men and women, aged 30 to 59, who died from CHD and 5.25 ± 0.98 mmol/l for the 3,873 men and women, aged 30 to 59, who did not die from CHD (table 1, p.213). The significance of the no CHD death was reported as $p < 0.001$. The cholesterol measurements were not significant for the older age group. Mean serum cholesterol levels were reported as 5.91 ± 0.87 mmol/l for the 40 men and women, aged 60 to 79, who died from CHD and 5.75 ± 1.05 mmol/l for the 581 men and women, aged 60 to 79, who did not die from CHD (table 1, p.213).

Outcomes – Diet: Dietary intake, as measured by the 24-hour recall, was reported for calories, macronutrients, saturated fat and unsaturated fat for 52 CHD deaths and 3,873 no CHD deaths in the age group 30 to 59 and for 40 CHD deaths and 581 no CHD deaths in the age group 60 to 79 (table 2, p.213).

There was no significant relationship between any nutrient measured in absolute intake and CHD deaths for either age group i.e. there was no significant difference related to CHD deaths in either age group for total calorie intake or grams of total fat, saturated fat, unsaturated fat, carbohydrate, protein or alcohol. As a percentage of energy, there was a significant difference for total fat ($p < 0.05$) and saturated fat ($p < 0.01$) for the age group 30 to 59, with men and women grouped together. There was no significant difference for any nutrient as a percentage of energy in the 60 to 79 age group.

Outcomes – Diet-heart hypothesis: A significant relationship ($p < 0.001$) was found between baseline cholesterol levels and not dying from CHD for men and women together in the 30 to 59 age group (table 1, p.213). No relationship was found with cholesterol and CHD deaths in the 60 to 79 age group.

No relationships were found between absolute dietary intakes and CHD deaths. Significant relationships were found with total and saturated fat intake, as a percentage of energy, and not dying from CHD for men and women together in the 30 to 59 age group (table 2, p.213). No relationships were found with total or saturated fat, as a percentage of energy, and CHD deaths in the 60 to 79 age group.

Outcomes – Other: The study found no association with polyunsaturated fat, as an intake in grams or as a percentage of total energy, in either age group. A significant relationship was found with smoking and CHD deaths and having a higher BMI and CHD deaths in the younger age group, but not the higher age group. Death rates for men were approximately 2.5 times death rates for women in both age groups.

Study information (designs, strengths, limitations): The study strengths were the number of participants, the length of follow-up, the participants having been drawn from the general population and being reflective of the adult population in both the gender mix and the wide age range included.

The method of extracting dietary information was a limitation. Dietary recall is generally unreliable and 24-hour recall may not be representative of usual diet (Beaton et al., 1983; Willett WC, 2000).

There was no evidence of selection bias (Fig. 6.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). The pool benefited from the inclusion of both men and women, from a wide age range, taken from the general population.

There was evidence of outcome blinding (Fig. 6.2). If cardiovascular disease was mentioned on the death certificate as either a primary or secondary cause of death, further information was sought from hospital records and from available informants. The deaths were classified by a nosologist using the International Classification of Diseases.

There was no evidence of attrition bias (Fig. 6.2). All 4,546 participants were accounted for as having died or still living.

There was no evidence of selective reporting (Fig. 6.2). The study set out to review predominantly dietary variables and reported on all of them.

This study was the only one, from the search undertaken, to measure all components of the diet-heart hypothesis – serum cholesterol, total fat and saturated fat – against CHD mortality. As regards the diet-heart hypothesis, it found support for an association between serum cholesterol and coronary heart deaths in people aged 30 to 59, but not

older. It found support for an association between total fat and coronary heart deaths, and saturated fat and coronary heart deaths as percentages of total energy intake, in people aged 30 to 59, but not older.

Table 6.1 Outcome data from included prospective cohort studies for: study name; participant number, gender and age range; years of follow-up; serum cholesterol, total fat and saturated fat for CHD-free vs. CHD deaths (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996; Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Gordon and Kannel, 1970; Kagan et al., 1974) or CHD-free vs. development of CHD (Keys, 1970a; Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977; Paul et al., 1963); and other significant associations found.

Study	Sex/Age	CHD-free?	Follow-up yrs	Cholesterol CHD/Non	Total fat CHD/Non	Sat fat CHD/Non	Other Significant associations with CHD
Western Electric Study (Paul et al., 1963)	1,989 M (40-55)	Y	4	CHD/Non 272/247 mean mg/dl	CHD/Non 148/152 g/day (*)	CHD/Non 59/59 g/day (*)	Age of death of father, smoking, coffee, elevated blood pressure
Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970a) Note 1	12,770 M (40-59)	98%	5	r = 0.76	r = 0.40 (*)	r = 0.84	Previous MI. NO association found with CHD & activity, smoking or weight
London bank and bus study (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977)	337 M (30-67)	Y	20	Note 2 3-5.6 7 5.6-6.5 13 6.5-8.6 16	Note 3 (*) 30-39% 18 38-43% 10 41-56% 17	N/A	Age of participant. Smoking. Higher calorie intake/cereal fibre & lower CHD
Framingham (Gordon et al., 1981)	859 M (45-64)	Y	4	N/A	Note 4 Death/alive 112/114 g/day (*)	Note 4 Death/alive 46/44 g/day (*)	Higher calorie intake & lower CHD. Higher alcohol intake & lower CHD

Study	Sex/Age	CHD-free?	Follow-up yrs	Cholesterol CHD/Non	Total fat CHD/Non	Sat fat CHD/Non	Other Significant associations with CHD
Honolulu (Gordon et al., 1981)	7,272 M (45-64)	Y	6	N/A	Note 4 Death/alive 86/87 g/day (*)	Note 4 Death/alive 32/32 g/day (*)	Higher calorie intake & lower CHD. Higher starch intake & lower CHD. Higher alcohol intake & lower CHD
Puerto Rico (Gordon et al., 1981)	8,218 M (45-64)	Y	6	N/A	Note 4 Death/alive 94/96 g/day (*)	Note 4 Death/alive 34/36 g/day (*)	Higher calorie intake & lower CHD. Rural living & lower CHD
Lipid Research (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996)	2,071 M 1,854 W (30-59)	Y	12	Death/alive 6.01/5.25 mmol/l (<i>p</i> <0.001)	Death/alive 42.5/39.8 % energy (<i>p</i> <0.05)	Death/alive 16.8/15.1 % energy (<i>p</i> <0.01)	Age. Being male. Weight. Smoking.
Lipid Research (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996)	282 M 339 W (60-79)	Y	12	Death/alive 5.91/5.75 mmol/l (*)	Death/alive 38.0/38.0 % energy (*)	Death/alive 13.8/14.3 % energy (*)	Age. Being male.

Table notes: N/A = data not available; MI = Myocardial Infarction

(*) Not statistically significant

Note 1: The Pearson correlation coefficients presented in this row represent 13 cohorts (both Japanese and the Rome railroad cohorts were missing). The coefficients represent the relationship between serum cholesterol, total dietary fat and saturated fat intake for the 13 cohorts and CHD deaths and infarctions. Data for CHD deaths alone were not presented. Data for men without heart disease on entry were not available. The data did not compare fat/cholesterol of those with CHD vs. those without. The correlations apply to fat/cholesterol data for cohorts relative to each other.

Note 2: Tertiles of cholesterol in mmol/l and number of CHD cases, not deaths, in each tertile.

Note 3: % of dietary intake accounted for by total fat and number of CHD cases, not deaths, in each tertile.

Note 4: Deaths are from CHD only.

Only one study reported standard deviations for any of the data in the table, rendering meta-analysis not possible (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

Table 6.2 Outcome data from prospective cohort studies without serum cholesterol data (with the exception in Table 6.1 (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996)) for: study name; participant number, gender and age range; years of follow-up; total fat and saturated fat for CHD deaths vs. CHD-free.

Study	Men/Women/Age	CHD-free?	Follow-up yrs	Total fat CHD death/Non	Sat fat CHD death/Non
Ireland Boston study (Kushi et al., 1985)	1,001 M (30-69)	N	20	39.4/38.5 % energy (*)	17.4/16.9 % energy (*)
US Health Professionals (Ascherio et al., 1996)	43,757 M (40-75)	Y	6	Note 1 1.59 (1.01 – 2.51) (<i>p</i> = 0.02)	Note 1 2.21 (1.38 – 3.54) (<i>p</i> = 0.0016)
Lipid Research (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996)	2,353 M 2,193 W (30-79)	Y	12	Note 2a 1.04 (1.01 – 1.08) (<i>p</i> <0.01)	Note 2a 1.11 (1.04 – 1.18) (<i>p</i> <0.01)
The Finnish Cancer Study (Pietinen et al., 1997)	21,930 M (50-69)	Y (all smokers)	6.1	Note 1 0.85 (0.65 – 1.12) (*)	Note 1 0.73 (0.56 – 0.95) (<i>p</i> = 0.044)
UK Health Survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002)	1,225 M (40-75)	Y	16	Note 2b 1.01 (0.93 – 1.10) (*)	Note 2b 1.00 (0.86 – 1.18) (*)
UK Health Survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002)	1,451 W (40-75)	Y	16	Note 2b 1.19 (1.03 – 1.37) (<i>p</i> = 0.0181)	Note 2b 1.40 (1.09 – 1.79) (<i>p</i> = 0.0074)

Study	Men/Women/Age	CHD-free?	Follow-up yrs	Total fat CHD death/Non	Sat fat CHD death/Non
Strong Heart Study (Xu et al., 2006)	646 M 1,013 W (47-59)	Y	7.2	Note 3 3.57 (1.21 – 10.49) (<i>p</i> = 0.01)	Note 3 5.17 (1.64 – 16.36) (<i>p</i> = 0.01)
Strong Heart Study (Xu et al., 2006)	405 M 874 W (60-79)	Y	7.2	Note 3 0.77 (0.41 – 1.45) (*)	Note 3 0.80 (0.41 – 1.54) (*)
Japanese Study (Nagata et al., 2012)	12,953 M (≥35)	Y	16	Notes 1 & 4 1.12 (0.80 – 1.57) (*)	Notes 1 & 4 0.96 (0.67 – 1.39) (*)

Table notes: (*) Not statistically significant

95% confidence intervals in parentheses.

Note 1: Data were presented in quintiles. The lowest quintile fat intake was given a risk ratio (RR) for CHD mortality of 1.0. The RR for the highest fat intake, quintile 5, was presented.

Note 2: 2a) This presented the RR for a one unit increase in the percentage of energy intake provided by the nutrient (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996)

2b) This was defined as an additional 100 g per week (Boniface and Tefft, 2002).

Note 3: Data were presented in quartiles. The lowest quartile fat intake was given a risk ratio (RR) for CHD mortality of 1.0. The RR for the highest fat intake, quartile 4, was presented.

Note 4: Data are for CVD, not CHD. Nagata *et al* included 15,403 women, but did not report on CVD, or CHD mortality by fat intake for women (table 4, p.1718 for men).

Fig. 6.2 Methodological quality summary: review authors' judgements about each methodological quality item for each included study (Higgins et al., 2011).

	Key Unclear risk of bias			
	Cohort appropriately reflected wider population (selection bias)	Blinding of outcome assessment (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)
Ireland Boston/ <u>Kushi</u> (1985)				
US Health Professionals/ <u>Ascherio</u> (1996)				
Lipid Research/ <u>Esrey</u> (1996)				
Finnish Cancer Study/ <u>Pietinen</u> (1997)				
UK Health Survey/ <u>Boniface</u> (2002)				
Strong Heart Study/ <u>Xu</u> (2006)				
Japanese Study/ <u>Nagata</u> (2012)				

Results: Meta-analysis

Participants and Study Design

The one additional study that met all inclusion criteria added 2,193 women and 2,353 men to the 31,445 men examined in Chapter Five (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). This study had complete outcome data, showing no evidence of attrition bias. There was evidence of blinding and the study was evaluated as low risk for reporting bias and selection bias (Fig. 6.2). The risk of bias of the other six studies was evaluated in Chapter Five (Fig. 5.2). Other than the inclusion of some women, Esrey *et al* did not materially change the profile of the pooled studies in Table 6.1.

The remainder of this results section is focused on Table 6.2, which included Esrey *et al* and six further prospective cohort studies. These six studies did not report serum cholesterol data and thus full examination of the diet-heart hypothesis was not possible.

However, the reporting of CHD mortality for total dietary fat and saturated fat intake was worthy of examination.

The seven prospective cohort studies in Table 6.2 included 89,801 participants. 84,270 of the participants were male (94%). All but one study excluded people with previous heart disease (Kushi et al., 1985). This study could not be included in the meta-analysis, as it did not contain suitable data. The age ranges varied from 30 to 79 years old at baseline. One of the studies grouped subjects from 47 to 59 years old and from 60 to 79 years old (Xu et al., 2006).

Participants were followed for a minimum of 6 years and a maximum of 20 years. The mean duration of the seven cohorts was 11.9 ± 5.6 years. The weighted mean duration (person years by participants) was 8.3 ± 1.1 years.

All trials had complete outcome data, avoiding attrition bias (Fig. 6.2) (Higgins et al., 2011). One study was judged unclear for selection bias, as participants excluded non-smokers (Pietinen et al., 1997). Four studies were judged unclear for detection bias, as blinding of outcome assessment was unclear (Kushi et al., 1985; Nagata et al., 2012; Pietinen et al., 1997; Xu et al., 2006). Risk of reporting bias was judged low for all but two of the studies: it was judged unclear for the Strong Heart Study, as the rationale for the age group division was not provided (Xu et al., 2006); and it was judged high risk for the Japanese Study as CVD by fat intake wasn't reported for women (Nagata et al., 2012) (Fig. 6.2).

For total fat and CHD deaths, Esrey *et al* carried the greatest weight, 34.72%, (Fig. 6.3 random effects methodology) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). The two Boniface and Tefft observations, for men and women, carried a combined weight of 45.62% (Boniface and Tefft, 2002). The two Xu *et al* observations carried a weight of 2.49% between them (Xu et al., 2006). The risk ratio for the meta-analysis of the eight data sets available for total fat and CHD deaths was 1.06 (95% CI 0.97 to 1.16). The overall effect measurement lies on the line of no effect. There was no statistically significant difference between total fat and CHD deaths.

The meta-analysis for total fat and CHD deaths was tested for sensitivity analysis of the exclusion of any one study. There were no circumstances in which the exclusion of any one study made the overall effect size significant.

There was evidence for between study heterogeneity. The Q-value was 15.395 (7 *df*) and this was statistically significant ($p = 0.031$). I^2 was 54.531 and T^2 was 0.006 indicating difference in true effects.

Visual inspection of the funnel plot revealed that one study was outside the standard error funnel for the meta-analysis of total fat and CHD deaths (Appendix 11). This was the Xu *et al* study for people aged 47-59 (Xu et al., 2006), which was substantially different to other risk ratios. The Egger's regression test indicated no statistically significant asymmetry for total fat and CHD deaths. The Egger's regression intercept was 0.602 (95% CI, two-tailed, -1.037 to 2.241), but this was not statistically significant (one-tailed $p = 0.202$; two-tailed $p = 0.403$).

For saturated fat and CHD deaths, Esrey *et al* carried the greatest weight, 20.91%, (Fig. 6.4 random effects methodology) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). The two Boniface and Tefft observations, for men and women, carried a combined weight of 34.34% (Boniface and Tefft, 2002). The two Xu *et al* observations carried a weight of 8.38% between them (Xu et al., 2006). The risk ratio for the meta-analysis of the eight data sets available for saturated fat and CHD deaths was 1.13 (95% CI 0.93 to 1.37). The overall effect measurement lies on the line of no effect. There was no statistically significant difference between saturated fat and CHD deaths.

The meta-analysis for saturated fat and CHD deaths was tested for sensitivity analysis of the exclusion of any one study. There were no circumstances in which the exclusion of any one study made the overall effect size significant.

There was evidence for between study heterogeneity. The Q-value was 31.152 (7 *df*) and this was statistically significant ($p = 0.000$). I^2 was 77.530 and T^2 was 0.044 indicating difference in true effects.

Visual inspection of the funnel plot revealed that three studies were outside the standard error funnel for the meta-analysis of total fat and CHD deaths (Ascherio et al., 1996; Pietinen et al., 1997) and the Xu study for people aged 47-59 (Xu et al., 2006). The Egger's regression test indicated no statistically significant asymmetry for total fat and CHD deaths. The Egger's regression intercept was 0.523 (95% CI, two-tailed, -2.258 to 3.304), but this was not statistically significant (one-tailed $p = 0.331$; two-tailed $p = 0.661$).

Fig. 6.3 Estimates of CHD mortality and total fat risk ratios (95% confidence intervals) from meta-analysis.

Fig. 6.4 Estimates of CHD mortality and saturated fat risk ratios (95% confidence intervals) from meta-analysis.

Examination of the dietary guidelines

None of the seven cohort studies examined either of the introduced dietary guidelines: a total fat consumption of 30%, or a saturated fat consumption of 10%, of energy intake. Two studies examined the total fat intake and the saturated fat intake, as a percentage of calorie intake, for participants who died from CHD compared to those who did not (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996; Kushi et al., 1985). Esrey *et al* also reported the risk ratio for an additional one unit of total or saturated fat as a percentage of energy intake. Three studies measured total and saturated fat intake in quintiles and reported data for CHD mortality as risk ratios comparing the lowest and highest quintiles of intake (Ascherio et al., 1996; Nagata et al., 2012; Pietinen et al., 1997). The Strong Heart Study followed this method, but for quartiles, not quintiles (Xu et al., 2006). The remaining study reported the risk ratio for an additional 100 g of total or saturated fat per week for men and women separately (Boniface and Tefft, 2002).

CHD mortality

Across 7 studies, involving 89,801 participants, there were 2,024 deaths from CHD during the period of follow-up: 110 (Kushi et al., 1985); 229 (Ascherio et al., 1996); 92 (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996); 635 (Pietinen et al., 1997); 98 men and 57 women died in the UK health and lifestyle survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002); 138 (Xu et al., 2006); and 665 men died in The Japanese Study (Nagata et al., 2012). The death rate from CHD was 2.25%, during the mean follow-up of 11.9 ± 5.6 years. The death rate was impacted by the large Finnish study, which included only participants who smoked. The death rate for this study was 2.9%.

The death rate contrasts with the 30% death rate for the six RCTs reviewed in Chapter Three and reinforces the high death rate in secondary studies. The one study that included men with previous heart disease reported a death rate of 11% (Kushi et al., 1985).

Significance reported by the studies

Two of the seven studies reported some participants separately: one by age group (Xu et al., 2006) and one by gender (Boniface and Tefft, 2002). This enabled nine sets of data to be examined (Table 6.2). Five found no significant relationship between total fat and CHD mortality (Kushi et al., 1985; Nagata et al., 2012; Pietinen et al., 1997), men in the UK health and lifestyle survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002) and the 60 to 79 year old participants from The Strong Heart Study of American Indians (Xu et al., 2006). The

remaining four found a significant relationship between total fat and CHD mortality (Ascherio et al., 1996; Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996); women in the UK health and lifestyle survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002); and the under 60 year old participants from The Strong Heart Study of American Indians (Xu et al., 2006).

Four found no significant relationship between saturated fat and CHD mortality (Kushi et al., 1985; Nagata et al., 2012), men in the UK health and lifestyle survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002) and the 60 to 79 year old participants from The Strong Heart Study of American Indians (Xu et al., 2006). The remaining five found a significant relationship between saturated fat and CHD mortality (Ascherio et al., 1996; Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996; Pietinen et al., 1997); women in the UK health and lifestyle survey (Boniface and Tefft, 2002); and the under 60 year old participants The Strong Heart Study of American Indians (Xu et al., 2006).

Meta-analysis confirmed that the pooled data were not significant for CHD mortality and total fat intake or CHD mortality and saturated fat intake.

Serum cholesterol levels

The only study to meet the full systematic review inclusion criteria was reported in Table 6.1 (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). This study found a significant relationship between baseline serum cholesterol and subsequent mortality from CHD in the age group 30 to 59 years, but not in the age group 60-79 years old.

Discussion

The main findings of this systematic review and meta-analysis are that the epidemiological evidence currently available to dietary committees provides no statistically significant retrospective support for the introduction of dietary fat guidelines.

Most studies reported other significant findings: Kushi *et al* found a significant association with higher intake of carbohydrate and fiber and lower CHD mortality. Esrey *et al* found significant positive associations with age, male gender, Body Mass Index (BMI), smoking and CHD deaths. Two studies reported significant associations with trans fat intake and CHD mortality (Ascherio et al., 1996; Pietinen et al., 1997). Ascherio *et al* additionally reported significant associations with the number of cigarettes smoked per day, the number of years of smoking, blood pressure, BMI and CHD mortality. Ascherio *et al* found that High Density Lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, education and physical activity were inversely related to the risk of CHD. Boniface and

Tefft reported that smoking, not exercising and being socially disadvantaged were related to higher saturated fat intake and CHD death, which meant that confounding variables could have played a part in findings. Xu *et al* found that age, being male, having diabetes and smoking were all significantly associated with CHD deaths.

Design limitations

As was found with the review of RCT evidence in Chapters Three, Four and Five, the fundamental design limitation of epidemiological evidence currently available is that it lacks generalisability. RCT evidence available to the dietary guideline committees had studied secondary males (Chapter Three); epidemiological evidence available to the dietary guideline committees had studied largely primary males (Chapter Five). One RCT currently available included men and women, without previous heart disease, and contained all component parts of the diet-heart hypothesis for examination (Frantz et al., 1989). One prospective cohort study currently available included primary men and women and contained all component parts of the diet-heart hypothesis for examination (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

The method of extracting dietary information was a limitation. Dietary recall is generally unreliable and 24-hour recall may not be representative of usual diet (Beaton et al., 1983; Willett WC, 2000). Dietary surveys, where food is weighed at the time of being recorded, are also unreliable (Archer, Pavea and Lavie, 2015; Cook, Pryer and Shetty, 2000).

Study conclusions

Two studies concluded that evidence was strong for an association between dietary fat and death from CHD. Boniface and Tefft reported: “Strong evidence was found for the within cohort relationship of dietary fat and CHD death in women while no evidence was found for a relationship in men” (p.786) (Boniface and Tefft, 2002). Xu *et al* found that: “Total fat, saturated fatty acid, and monounsaturated fatty acid intake were strong predictors of CHD mortality in American Indians aged 47-59 y” (p.894) (Xu et al., 2006).

The Japanese Study found: “Total fat intake is associated with decreased mortality in Japanese men but not in women” (p.1713) (Nagata et al., 2012).

Two studies reported weak or no associations between dietary fat and CHD mortality. Ascherio *et al* appeared to reference The Seven Countries Study with their comment, “These data do not support the strong association between intake of saturated fat and

risk of coronary heart disease suggested by international comparisons” (p.84) (Ascherio et al., 1996). Pietinen *et al* reported that “There was a significant positive association between the intake of trans fatty acids and the risk of coronary death. There was no association between intakes of saturated or cis-monounsaturated fatty acids or linoleic or linolenic acid or dietary cholesterol and the risk of coronary death” (p.876) (Pietinen et al., 1997).

The final two studies described the relationship as unclear. Kushi *et al* concluded: “The nature of the association in this study between dietary lipids and the risk of mortality from coronary heart disease remains unclear” (p.816) (Kushi et al., 1985). The one study meeting all systematic review inclusion criteria reported: “We conclude that future research must be directed toward better understanding the pathway between dietary intake and coronary disease as the current diet-lipid-heart hypothesis may be overly simplistic” (p.211) (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996).

Other meta-analyses of prospective cohort studies

A meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies evaluating the association between saturated fat and cardiovascular disease was published in 2010 (Siri-Tarino et al., 2010). This meta-analysis included prospective cohort studies: with data related to the consumption of saturated fat; with fatal or non fatal CVD data; where the association of saturated fat with CVD was specifically evaluated; and where participants were healthy adults at baseline. The review identified 21 studies for inclusion. Five contained stroke, not CHD, data and were thus outside the remit of this thesis. 16 contained CHD data (Ascherio et al., 1996; Boniface and Tefft, 2002; Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996; Fehily et al., 1993; Goldbourt, Yaari and Medalie, 1993; Jakobsen et al., 2004; Kushi et al., 1985; Leosdottir et al., 2007; Mann et al., 1997; McGee et al., 1984; Oh et al., 2005; Pietinen et al., 1997; Posner et al., 1991; Shekelle et al., 1981; Tucker et al., 2005; Xu et al., 2006).

The 16 included The Western Electric Study (Shekelle et al., 1981); The Honolulu Heart Program (McGee et al., 1984) and The Framingham Heart Study (Posner et al., 1991) included in Chapter Five of this thesis. The three other studies included in Chapter Five of this thesis were rejected for the absence of saturated fat data (Morris, Marr and Clayton, 1977); and the absence of CVD data (Garcia-Palmieri et al., 1969; Gordon et al., 1981; Keys, 1970a). The Seven Countries Study was also excluded by Siri-Tarino *et al* “because it evaluated the association of SFAs with CVD across cohorts/countries” and because “many countries were left out of this analysis, and if

they were all plotted, the relationship between SFAs and CVD would not exist (DiNicolantonio, 2014)” (Personal correspondence with Siri-Tarino, 2015).

The two studies found by Siri-Tarino *et al*, but not the search in this chapter, did not meet CHD mortality inclusion criteria (Leosdottir et al., 2007; Tucker et al., 2005). Leosdottir *et al* examined CVD events and found “In relation to risks of cardiovascular events, our results do not suggest any benefit from a limited total or saturated fat intake, nor from relatively high intake of unsaturated fat” (p.701) (Leosdottir et al., 2007). Tucker *et al* was a study of combined increased fruit and vegetable intake and decreased saturated fat intake and thus the impact of saturated fat modification could not be isolated. Additionally, this study did not examine total fat intake.

The conclusion of Siri-Tarino *et al*'s review was “meta-analysis of prospective epidemiologic studies showed that there is no significant evidence for concluding that dietary saturated fat is associated with an increased risk of CHD or CVD” (p.535) (Siri-Tarino et al., 2010).

Chapters Three and Five found that the dietary fat guidelines were not supported by RCT or epidemiological evidence available at the time of their introduction. Chapter Four found that the RCT evidence currently available does not support the introduced dietary guidelines in retrospect. This chapter finds that the epidemiological evidence currently available does not support the introduced dietary guidelines in retrospect. All chapters found serious limitations with the availability of primary prevention, both-sex, studies, which are the ones most likely to have generalisability for whole populations.

Chapter Seven

An examination of the randomised controlled trial and epidemiological evidence for the introduction of dietary fat recommendations in 1977 and 1983: A systematic review and meta-analysis

Discussion

“The urgency of finding means of prevention is sharpest for men in middle age for it is in that group that the social cost of CHD is greatest... Starting with men aged 40 through 59, the follow-up would show CHD causing close to 40% of all deaths in five years. It is understandable, then, that most work on the epidemiology of CHD begins with men of those ages” (p.I-1) (Keys, 1970a).

Introduction

The first part of the diet-heart hypothesis, that serum cholesterol was related to coronary heart disease (CHD), originated from the work of Russian pathologists in the early twentieth century. Having observed fatty deposits in arteries during post mortems, a number of researchers sought to understand if dietary cholesterol determined serum cholesterol (Anitschkow, 1913; Chalатов, 1912; Knack, 1915; Kon, 1913; Kon, 1914; Stuckey, 1910; Stuckey, 1911; Stuckey, 1912; Wesselkin, 1913). The summary of findings from the original animal studies was that: rabbits (herbivores) fed animal foods developed fatty deposits/changes in the aortas; rats (omnivores) fed animal foods produced no observable changes in the aortas; and rabbits fed cholesterol in plant food showed no arterial damage.

In the 1950s, Keys undertook several experiments with human subjects and concluded “that the cholesterol content, *per se*, of all natural diets has *no* significant effect on either the serum cholesterol level or the development of atherosclerosis in man” (p.182) (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

The logic that only animal foods contain cholesterol and thus, if animal foods consumed to administer dietary cholesterol had no impact on serum cholesterol then animal foods *per se* had no impact on serum cholesterol, was overlooked. Attention turned to dietary fat in food when non-animal foods would have been more logical to examine.

In the early 1950s, literature referred to animal and vegetable fat and not the degree of saturation of fat (Keys, 1952a; Keys, 1952b; Keys et al., 1950c). Interventions with vegetable fat were extrapolated to conclusions about animal fat, without animal fat having been tested (Keys, 1952a; Keys, 1952b).

The first references to saturated and unsaturated fats occurred later in the decade (Keys, 1956). Keys' earliest findings were that there was no relationship between the saturation of fats and their effects in producing hypercoagulability of the blood after they were eaten (Keys, 1956).

The second part of the diet-heart hypothesis, that dietary fat and serum cholesterol were related, followed observational studies of men in Minnesota, Naples, Slough and Madrid. Keys concluded that the total fat content of the diet (as a proportion of calories) exerted a powerful influence on the serum cholesterol level in man (Keys et al., 1954a). Age appeared to be a confounder, with cholesterol rising to the age of 50-55 in Minnesotan and Slough men and rich men in Madrid. Neapolitan men and poor men in Madrid demonstrated stable and falling cholesterol levels respectively between the ages of 40 and 50; rising before these ages.

The third part of the diet-heart hypothesis, that dietary fat and CHD were related, was first presented with the graph of deaths from heart disease and calories from total fat in men aged 55-59, for six countries, from the Mount Sinai presentation of 1953 (Keys, 1953a). The response of Yerushalmy and Hilleboe demonstrated that data were available for 22 countries (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957).

Keys concluded that no other variable, besides the fat calories in the diet, showed anything like such a consistent relationship to the mortality rate from CHD (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

The first statement of the diet-heart hypothesis, with the three component parts, appears to have been made in a 1955 publication, which explored the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol and CHD in different ethnic groups in Cape Town (Bronte-Stewart, Keys and Brock, 1955). This paper confirmed that total fat intake and animal fat intake were the subjects of examination. Saturated fat was not mentioned.

In 1957, Keys published another summary paper on "Diet and the epidemiology of coronary heart disease" (Keys, 1957a). Keys' position on fat, cholesterol and heart disease became more certain. He described the American diet as dominated by "innumerable fat-loading meals", the results of which were "hypercholesteremia, which promotes atherosclerosis". Keys differentiated that food fats were not identical in promoting hypercholesteremia, but those most prevalent in fatty diets were more powerful in this direction than food oils that had an opposing effect. As a final complication, Keys noted that different fats had differing effects on serum cholesterol and blood coagulation (p.1912) (Keys, 1957a).

This was the context for the start of The Seven Countries Study in 1956-1958. The Seven Countries Study concluded that there was no relationship with total fat and CHD, but that there was a strong correlation between saturated fat intake and CHD in one of seven countries when compared with saturated fat intake and CHD in others of seven countries (Keys, 1970a).

In ideal research circumstances, epidemiological evidence would have established clear and consistent associations and then well designed randomised controlled trials (RCTs) would have followed epidemiological findings and set out to test associations found. This did not happen with the development of the diet-heart hypothesis. Possibly the sense of urgency took over. The epidemiology and RCTs were running in parallel from the 1950s onwards.

The focus on men, and men who had already had a heart attack in the case of the RCTs, was understandable in the context of the Keys' quotation opening this chapter. This focus, however, lacked generalisability for the population as a whole.

Results

The findings

Public health advice for all citizens should be informed by conclusive, consistent, evidence from numerous robust studies, of an appropriate representative group of such citizens (large enough, long enough, studies of healthy men and women of all ages). This did not happen before the guidelines were set. It has not happened since and it is unlikely to happen in the future, not least with cost, ethical and confounding variable complications, such as the prevalence of medication. There are two issues with the evidence examined in this thesis:

1) The conclusions of the evidence:

The evidence available to the dietary committees at the time the guidelines were introduced did not support the recommendations made. The four null hypotheses, set out in Chapter One, cannot be rejected. A systematic review and meta-analysis of RCTs available in 1977/1983, where a dietary fat intervention had been made, revealed identical all-cause mortality (30% in intervention and control groups) and no statistically significant difference in deaths from CHD. A systematic review of prospective cohort studies available in 1977/1983 found one study offering support for saturated, but not total fat, to be a subject for further examination and five studies with no significant findings in relation to total, or saturated, dietary fat.

The evidence currently available offers no additional support. A systematic review and meta-analysis of dietary fat RCTs currently available, where a dietary fat intervention had been made, found no statistically significant difference in all-cause mortality or deaths from CHD. A systematic review and meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies currently available found no statistically significant results to implicate total or saturated fat in CHD mortality.

With one exception, the specific guidelines of 30% total fat and 10% saturated fat have not been tested. The STARS (Watts et al., 1992) was the only study to examine targets approximating to those set by dietary guidelines, with a total fat consumption of 27% and an 8-10% saturated fat intake. The DART (Burr et al., 1989) tested a 30% total fat diet, although this was not a controlled variable, as the intervention also tried to achieve a 1:1 polyunsaturated to saturated fat ratio. Two RCTs studied an approximate 20% fat diet (Howard et al., 2006; Research Committee, 1965). Two reviewed the consequence of a 10% saturated fat diet, without the total fat dietary guideline restriction (Frantz et al., 1989; Woodhill et al., 1978). The prospective cohort studies examined grams of fat intake for those who died from CHD vs. those who didn't, or fat intake as a percentage of calories, sometimes in absolute amounts, sometimes comparing lowest and highest tertiles, quartiles or quintiles. They did not examine populations for outcomes related to the two dietary fat guidelines. This is not a criticism of the studies. Public health policy should follow evidence, not the other way round.

One RCT claimed that its findings supported the use of a lipid-lowering diet in men with CHD (Watts et al., 1992). Three prospective cohort studies reported strong evidence for an association between dietary fat and CHD: The Seven Countries Study found an association with saturated fat (Keys, 1970e); Boniface and Tefft (Boniface and Tefft, 2002) found an association with both total and saturated fat, but for men only, not women; Xu *et al* found associations for total fat, saturated fatty acid and monounsaturated fatty acid intake in American Indians aged 47-59 years, but not older (Xu et al., 2006).

All other RCTs and prospective cohort studies reported no significant findings for total or saturated dietary fat. Four RCTs issued cautions about the safety and/or efficacy of their interventions (Dayton et al., 1969; Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Woodhill et al., 1978). Rose *et al* reported that corn oil was most unlikely to be beneficial, and was possibly harmful (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965). The Research Committee Low-fat Diet concluded that a low-fat diet has no place

in the treatment of myocardial infarction (Research Committee, 1965). Dayton *et al* noted the absence of any benefit for longevity and expressed concern about toxicity of the intervention (Dayton et al., 1969). Woodhill *et al* reported that survival was significantly better in the control than the diet group (Woodhill et al., 1978).

Regarding the serum cholesterol part of the diet-heart hypothesis, the RCTs at the time and currently available collectively reported greater reductions in mean serum cholesterol levels in the intervention groups, but this did not result in a reduction in deaths, from CHD or all-causes. These findings raise questions about the mechanism of cholesterol lowering medications, such as statins. It has been assumed that statins lower cholesterol and lowering cholesterol lowers death rates. There may be another mechanism by which statins have an effect, independent of cholesterol. Caution should be adopted in using cholesterol as a surrogate end-point: the new Proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 9 inhibitors (PCSK9) are being launched with surrogate end-point evidence alone, without evidence for CHD mortality (European Medicines Agency, 2015).

Plant sterols offer a plausible explanation for dietary interventions lowering cholesterol, but not mortality. Plant sterols is the collective term for free and esterified phytosterols and phytostanols, regardless of biological source. Phytosterols are cholesterol-like molecules found in all plant foods, with the highest concentrations occurring in vegetable oils. They are absorbed only in trace amounts, but inhibit the absorption of intestinal cholesterol (Ostlund, 2002). The most commonly occurring phytosterols in the human diet are β -sitosterol, campesterol and stigmasterol, which account for approximately 65%, 30% and 3% of diet contents respectively (Weihrauch and Gardner, 1978). The ability of phytosterols to inhibit the absorption of cholesterol was first established in 1953 (Pollak, 1953). However, there is no evidence that plant sterols reduce the risk of CHD and much evidence that they are detrimental (Harcombe and Baker, 2014).

2) The quality of the evidence:

Even if the evidence from prospective cohort studies and RCTs had been overwhelming, the limitations of the studies were so great that the evidence could not be relied upon. Only one RCT was a primary study of both men and women (Frantz et al., 1989). Only one prospective cohort study, with evidence for CHD mortality, examined both men and women, free from CHD at the baseline (Esrey, Joseph and Grover, 1996). All prospective cohort studies suffered the limitations of dietary questionnaires (Archer,

Pavela and Lavie, 2015; Beaton et al., 1983; Cook, Pryer and Shetty, 2000; Freedman, Schatzkin and Wax, 1990; Kipnis et al., 2001; Willett WC, 2000). Other limitations of each study have been documented in Chapters Three to Six.

The Seven Countries Study

The strongest evidence presented, among 10 RCTs and 13 prospective cohort studies, came from The Seven Countries Study (Keys, 1970e). Keys noted in the introduction to The Seven Countries Study publication that association did not mean causation, but the strength of conclusions did not adopt this caution. The conclusions of this study defined the diet-heart hypothesis as the tripartite association of saturated fat, serum cholesterol levels and CHD; the impact of dietary cholesterol and total dietary fat having been rejected (Keys, 1970e).

The correlations established by The Seven Countries Study were strong. The correlation between median serum cholesterol level and CHD deaths and infarctions (data for CHD deaths alone were not presented) per 100 people was $r = 0.76$ ($p < 0.05$). The correlation between CHD deaths and infarctions and saturated fat as a percentage of calories was $r = 0.84$ ($p < 0.05$) (Keys, 1970i). However, these correlations were for countries vs. each other, not for people in one country who died from CHD vs. those in the same country who didn't.

The confounders were significant, including, but not limited to: geography; lifestyle; Gross Domestic Product; climate; politics; other aspects of national diet; national health provision etc. When asked about the value of Keys' work, a contemporary of the time, Professor Peter Elwood, described inter country studies as "the lowest form of evidence" (Personal communication, 2015).

The Seven Countries Study suffered from further limitations with the pre-selection of countries known to be associated; an average of 3.4% of men sampled for dietary information; and the inclusion of men with pre-existing CHD, with the finding that the CHD death rate within 5 years was 20.9% for secondary males and 1.0% for primary males.

Without these limitations, the strong correlations established by The Seven Countries Study were not unique. Equally strong correlations had been established with animal protein, with Gross Domestic Product suggested as the confounder (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957); television sets and vehicle licenses (Yudkin, 1957); and the strongest correlation of all was established with latitude in this thesis (Appendix 9).

A definitive assessment of the strength of associations found in research was proposed by Bradford Hill with his nine criteria (Bradford Hill, 1965). In 2009, Mente *et al* reviewed RCTs and prospective cohort studies against these criteria for numerous foods and nutrients. They concluded: “Insufficient evidence of association is present for intake of ... saturated and polyunsaturated fatty acids; total fat; linolenic acid; meat; eggs and milk” (p.659) (Mente et al., 2009).

Although The Seven Countries Study was not referenced by the US committee February publication (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977), it was referenced by the UK committee (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) and Keys and his research was referenced 40 times in the 869 supplemental pages to the dietary guidelines (Select committee on nutrition and human needs, 1977). The fact that Keys had appeared on the front cover of Time Magazine attested to the regard with which he was held (Ancel Keys Time Magazine, 1961). There can be little doubt that The Seven Countries Study had a significant impact on the introduction of dietary fat guidelines.

Other meta-analyses

The discussion section of Chapter Four reported a number of meta-analyses of RCTs that had been undertaken by other authors (Hooper et al., 2011; Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010; Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014). The discussion section of Chapter Six reported one meta-analysis of prospective cohort studies that had been undertaken by other authors (Siri-Tarino et al., 2010).

Two additional meta-analyses reviewed both RCTs and prospective cohort studies (Chowdhury et al., 2014; Skeaff and Miller, 2009). Skeaff and Miller sought to summarise the evidence from cohort studies and RCTs of the relation between dietary fat and risk of CHD. Their conclusion was “Intake of total fat was not significantly associated with CHD mortality. Intake of total fat was also unrelated to CHD events” (p.175) (Skeaff and Miller, 2009). Chowdhury *et al* set out to summarise evidence between fatty acids and coronary disease. Their review examined saturated, monounsaturated, polyunsaturated and trans fats, while also reviewing individual chain length fatty acids, palmitic (C16:0) and margaric (C17:0) as examples. The conclusion was “Current evidence does not clearly support cardiovascular guidelines that encourage high consumption of polyunsaturated fatty acids and low consumption of total saturated fats” (p.398) (Chowdhury et al., 2014).

Table 7.1 summarises the findings from other meta-analyses of RCTs and/or prospective cohort studies. Table 7.2 reports their objectives and inclusion criteria. There were 39 reports of risk ratios from meta-analysis with 95% confidence intervals. Of these, 4 reported significant findings; 35 reported no significant findings. One of the significant findings related to trans fats, not total or saturated fat. It found that trans fat intake was positively associated with coronary disease (Chowdhury et al., 2014). Another of the significant findings came from the study of the impact of replacing saturated fat with polyunsaturated fat (Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010), which was criticised (Ravnskov et al., 2014) for excluding two studies that would have moderated this conclusion (Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Woodhill et al., 1978) and including a favourable, but non-randomised cross-over, trial excluded by all other meta-analyses (Miettinen et al., 1983; Turpeinen et al., 1979).

The other two significant findings were related to CVD events and not mortality (Hooper et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2011). In 2011, including RCTs with a minimum of 6 months duration, Hooper *et al* found 1 significant result and 11 non-significant results. The one significant result was that, when all RCTs were examined together, the risk ratio (RR) for CVD events from meta-analysis was 0.86 (95% CI 0.77 to 0.96). In 2015, including RCTs with a minimum of 24 months duration, Hooper *et al* found one significant result and seven non-significant results. The one significant result was, when a reduction in saturated fat was examined, the risk ratio (RR) for CVD events from meta-analysis was 0.83 (95% CI 0.72 to 0.96).

As a result of this 2015 review, Hooper *et al* suggested that there may be a small reduction in cardiovascular risk with reduction of saturated fat intake (Hooper et al., 2015). It was further suggested that replacing the energy from saturated fat with polyunsaturated fat “appears to be a useful strategy, and replacement with carbohydrate appears less useful” (p.2) (Hooper et al., 2015) and replacement with monounsaturated fat unclear. Of the 11 interventions contributing to this conclusion, only 1 documented both saturated fat reduction and reported that this was mainly replaced with polyunsaturated fat (Dayton et al., 1969).

The Hooper meta-analyses of 2011 and 2015 included four small studies (646 people in total), not included in any other meta-analysis, which were primarily studies of: diabetes (Houtsmuller, Zahn and Henkes, 1979); skin cancer (Black et al., 1994); hypercholesterolemia (Moy et al., 2001); and glucose intolerance (Ley et al., 2004), but for which Hooper *et al* obtained CVD event information. The most recent review

(Hooper et al., 2015) included no study of healthy people of both genders. The one primary, both-sex RCT available was excluded by Hooper *et al*, for not meeting the 24 month duration criteria (Frantz et al., 1989). The one significant finding of small benefit for CVD events, among numerous insignificant findings, thus also lacked generalisability.

Dietary fat guidelines were introduced with the ambition of reducing deaths from CHD. No meta-analysis of RCTs and/or prospective cohort studies has found any significant difference for dietary fat interventions and all-cause mortality or deaths from CHD, or associations with dietary fat and CHD mortality (Chowdhury et al., 2014; Harcombe et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2015; Hooper et al., 2011; Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010; Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014; Siri-Tarino et al., 2010; Skeaff and Miller, 2009).

Discussion

Have there been consequences?

Both the US and UK documents acknowledged that the evidence was not conclusive. The UK publication referred to "a strong consensus of opinion" (p.24) (National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983). Hegsted's introduction to the Dietary Goals for The United States noted "there will undoubtedly be many people who will say we have not proven our point" (p.3) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977).

Hegsted continued by asking "What are the risks associated with eating less meat, less fat, less saturated fat, less cholesterol, less sugar, less salt, and more fruits, vegetables, unsaturated fat and cereal products – especially whole grain cereals. There are none that can be identified" (p.8) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977).

Senators Percy, Schweiker and Zorinsky wrote a foreword for the second edition of the guidelines noting the "lack of consensus among nutritional scientists and other health professionals" (p.vii). They recommended that it be stated in bold print on the Goals and Food Selection pages "that the value of dietary change remains controversial and that science cannot at this time insure (sic) that an altered diet will improve protection from certain killer diseases such as heart disease and cancer" (p.ix) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, December 1977).

The second edition of the US dietary goals was published at the end of 1977 (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, December 1977). In between the first edition (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977) and the second, many witnesses appeared before the committee. Deliberations were reflected in a number of comments from the second edition of the guidelines: “Some witnesses have claimed that physical harm could result from the diet modifications recommended in this report... However, after further review, the Select Committee still finds that no physical or mental harm could result from the dietary guidelines recommended for the general public”(p.xxxiii) (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, December 1977). The view was, therefore, that even if benefit were unproven, no harm could be done.

There are three macronutrients: carbohydrate; protein and fat. Protein is found in all foods except pure fats (oils and lard) and sucrose (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013). The proportion of protein in a natural diet thus tends to remain constant at approximately 15-20% of energy intake. If fat intake is reduced, as a proportion of energy intake, carbohydrate concomitantly rises. The consequences of increasing carbohydrate content in human diets had not been investigated before the dietary fat guidelines were introduced.

Until the introduction of dietary guidelines in 1977, the view of Tanner, from *The Practice of Medicine*, prevailed “Farinaceous and vegetable foods are fattening, and saccharine matters are especially so” (p.213) (Tanner, 1869). In 1960, 13.3% of United States (US) adults were obese; 44.8% were overweight. By 2007, 34.7% of US adults were obese; 67.7% were overweight (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2010). In the UK, in 1972, 2.7% of men and 2.7% of women were obese and 23.0% of men and 13.9% of women were overweight. By 1999, obesity rates had risen to 22.6% of men and 25.8% of women, while 49.2% of men and 36.3% of women were overweight (Michael Wadsworth et al., 2006). (Health was devolved in the UK in 1999 to the regions of England, Northern Ireland, Scotland and Wales and thus UK statistics terminated).

The diabetes rate was 2.4% in 1976 in the US (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, October 2014). The introduction to the 2010 Dietary Guidelines for Americans reported that 24 million Americans, almost 11% of the adult population, were diabetic and 78 million Americans, 35% of adults were pre-diabetic (Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), 2010). This has recently been updated to 29

million diabetics and 86 million pre-diabetics (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2014). A recent review in *The Lancet*, estimated that the lifetime risk for developing diabetes was 40.2% for American men and 39.6% for women (Gregg et al., 2014). There were 800,000 people with diabetes in the UK in 1980, from a population of 56 million – an incident rate of 1.42% (Diabetes UK, 2004). The diabetes rate in the UK in 2015 was 6.1% (Diabetes UK, 2015). The incident rate of diabetes, in both the US and the UK, has increased more than four fold since the dietary fat guidelines were introduced.

The association between the introduction of the dietary fat guidelines and concomitant increases in obesity and diabetes deserves examination. A number of recent reviews have suggested a causal connection: “The replacement of saturated fats in the diet with carbohydrates, especially sugars, has resulted in increased obesity and its associated health complications” (p.294) (Lawrence, 2013). In a BMJ Editorial, cardiologist, Dr. Aseem Malhotra closed with the statement: “It is time to bust the myth of the role of saturated fat in heart disease and wind back the harms of dietary advice that has contributed to obesity” (p.1) (Malhotra, 2013). In 2014, Dr. James DiNicolantino questioned current dietary guidelines. Having reviewed data trends for dietary fat and obesity in the US, he concluded: “These data provide a strong argument that the increase in the consumption of refined carbohydrates was the causative dietary factor for the diabetes and obesity epidemic in the USA” (p.1) (DiNicolantonio, 2014). Following a Swedish systematic review of literature, an article was published in the BMJ entitled “Swedish health advisory body says too much carbohydrate, not fat, leads to obesity” (Hansen, 2013). Feinman *et al* analysed US dietary intake for the period 1974-2000 and concluded: “During the epidemics of obesity and type 2 diabetes, caloric increases have been due almost entirely to increased carbohydrate” (p.6) (Feinman et al., 2014).

Dietary guidelines set to change?

The US dietary guidelines, originally issued in 1980, are re-issued every five years; 2015 being a dietary guidelines year of issue. The draft report for 2015, from the US dietary guidelines advisory committee (DGAC), was published in February 2015 (Dietary Guidelines Advisory Committee, 2015). The recommendation to limit dietary cholesterol intake to 300 milligrams a day has prevailed in the US since 1977 (Select Committee on Nutrition and Human Needs, February 1977). The DGAC stated that they will not bring forward this recommendation because available evidence shows no

appreciable relationship between consumption of dietary cholesterol and serum cholesterol: “Cholesterol is not a nutrient of concern for over consumption” (p.90) (Dietary Guidelines Advisory Committee, 2015). The UK did not introduce dietary cholesterol targets in the original guidelines (Committee on Medical Aspects of Food Policy (COMA), 1984; National Advisory Committee on Nutritional Education (NACNE), 1983) and they have not been introduced since (Department of Health, 1991). The Keys’ research from the 1950s, documented in Chapter Two, concluded that dietary cholesterol should never have been a nutrient of concern (Keys and Anderson, 1954).

The DGAC advice demonstrated further movement away from the original dietary fat guidelines by containing no total fat recommendation and a change in the position on dietary fat and cardiovascular disease (CVD). The advisory report documented the findings of the meta-analyses by Skeaff (Skeaff and Miller, 2009) (RCTs and prospective cohorts), Siri-Tarino (Siri-Tarino et al., 2010) (prospective cohorts), Hooper (Hooper et al., 2011) (RCTs) and Chowdhury (Chowdhury et al., 2014) (RCTs and prospective cohorts) and concluded that reducing total fat does not lower CVD risk (Dietary Guidelines Advisory Committee, 2015). The saturated fat guideline was reiterated, however, with the recommendation to consume fewer than 10% of total calories from saturated fat per day (Dietary Guidelines Advisory Committee, 2015).

There are consequences of maintaining the saturated fat guideline and not the total fat guideline. Consumption of one, or both, of the other natural fats, monounsaturated and polyunsaturated, may increase. The fat that is being promoted for higher intake is polyunsaturated fat (Hooper et al., 2015; Jakobsen et al., 2009; Li et al., 2015; Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010; Schwab and Uusitupa, 2015). Many authors have expressed concern about this recommendation (Baum et al., 2012; de Souza et al., 2015; DiNicolantonio, 2014; Lamarche and Couture, 2014; Ramsden et al., 2010; Ramsden et al., 2013; Ravnskov et al., 2014).

It is important to differentiate between polyunsaturated fats. The DART provided early evidence for the benefit of omega-3 polyunsaturated fat, naturally abundant in fish (Burr et al., 1989). The only significant finding from this RCT was that all-cause mortality was lower for those following the fish advice, which was to increase fatty fish intake to at least two portions (200-400 g) weekly. The relative risk for fish advice vs. no fish advice was 0.71 (0.54-0.92) ($p<0.05$) (table IV, p.759) (Burr et al., 1989). This significant finding was explored further by the research team, but not found to be

replicated (Burr et al., 2003). Omega-6 polyunsaturated fats have pro-inflammatory properties, which can be mitigated by omega-3 intake (Schmitz and Ecker, 2008), but any dietary advice on polyunsaturated fats needs to be specific and evidence based.

The UK does not review dietary guidelines at regular intervals. The target for total fat remains 30% of daily total energy intake and 10% for saturated fat (Department of Health, 1991).

A way forward?

The 2010 Dietary Guidelines for Americans documented the sources of saturated fat in the American diet (fig. 3-4, p.26) (Department of Health and Human Services (HHS), 2010). Pizza, desserts, candy, potato chips, pasta, tortillas, burritos and tacos accounted for 32.6% of saturated fat consumed in the diets of US citizens aged 2 years and older. 9.3% of dietary saturated fat came from sausages, frankfurters, bacon, ribs and burgers. 12.8% came from chicken and mixed chicken dishes, beef and mixed beef dishes, and eggs and mixed egg dishes. A further 24.5% was unaccounted for and collated as “All other food categories”; likely including, if not predominantly being, processed foods. The natural foods listed were cheese, milk, butter, nuts and seeds which collectively accounted for 20.8% of saturated fat intake. It would have been ideal for unprocessed chicken, beef and eggs to have been separated from processed meals containing these ingredients. The diagram presented in the Dietary Guidelines is clear nonetheless. Processed foods account for the majority of saturated fat intake in the diets of Americans.

The UK classification is similar. The Family Food Survey (table 2.4, p.18) documented sources of saturated fat in the UK diet (A National Statistics Publication, 2010). Bread, cakes, buns, pastries, biscuits, cereals, confectionery and other processed foods accounted for 33% of saturated fat intake. Milk, cream and cheese accounted for 24% of dietary saturated fat. Processed meat accounted for 16% of saturated fat intake, while unprocessed (carcass) meat was 5%, fish 1% and eggs 1% of saturated fat intake. Fats and oils made up the remaining 19% (99% due to rounding errors). As with the US, processed food accounted for the majority of the saturated fat intake of the UK.

There is opportunity for strong agreement among health professionals. If the public health message were revised to advise citizens to eat natural food and not processed food, saturated fat intake would fall accordingly although the health benefit would likely be the concomitant reduction in sucrose, trans fats and other processed ingredients deleterious to human health. Human beings evolved to eat foods available

from the natural environment (Gowlett, 2003). It does not seem logical to advise populations away from carcass meat, dairy produce, eggs, nuts and seeds, in the name of saturated fat, when the modern processed foods, biscuits, cakes, pizza, desserts and ready meals, are more sensibly related to modern illness (Harcombe, Baker and Davies, 2013).

Close

An exchange between Dr. Robert Olson of St Louis University and Senator George McGovern, chair of the Dietary Committee, was recorded in July 1977 (CBS News, July 26 1977). Olson said "I pleaded in my report and will plead again orally here for more research on the problem before we make announcements to the American public." McGovern replied "Senators don't have the luxury that the research scientist does of waiting until every last shred of evidence is in."

The evidence is now in. Indeed the evidence was available at the time. The original problem was defined in middle aged men. Middle aged men were the primary focus of RCTs and epidemiological evidence at the time: secondary men for the intervention trials and largely healthy men for the cohort studies. Despite only one study finding associations (Keys, 1970a); and many others advising caution (Research Committee, 1965; Rose, Thomson and Williams, 1965; Woodhill et al., 1978) and despite a total lack of generalisability, guidelines were introduced for whole populations and have prevailed since.

An additional consequence of the guidelines is that, while it has been assumed that total and saturated dietary fat and dietary and serum cholesterol have been primary causes of CHD, factors of genuine concern have not been investigated as fully as they warrant.

The future will undoubtedly consist of the tailoring of diets and lifestyle to individual genomic makeup (Stegemann et al., 2014). This will require the understanding of the genomic structure of circulating lipid profiles and replicable data on gene and diet interaction. Caution will be required in translating contemporary research on genes, diet and lifestyle into public health advice.

It is important that we learn from the study limitations and lack of evidence upon which current guidelines are based and not make the same mistake with future guidelines or suggestions.

Table 7.1 Summary of meta-analyses of RCTs and prospective cohort studies.

	Studies examined	Studies	People	Measure	Fat	Risk Ratio	Conclusion
(Skeaff and Miller, 2009)	Prospective cohort studies & RCTs	28	280,000	CHD mortality	Total fat	0.94 [0.74, 1.18]	No sig difference
				CHD events	Total fat	0.93 [0.84, 1.03]	No sig difference
(Siri-Tarino et al., 2010)	Prospective cohort studies	21	347,747	CHD fatal & non	Sat fat (Extreme quintiles)	1.07 [0.96, 1.19]	No sig difference
				CVD fatal & non	Sat fat (Extreme quintiles)	1.00 [0.89, 1.11]	No sig difference
(Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010)	RCTs	8	13,614	CHD events	Replacing SFA with PUFA	0.81 [0.70-0.95]	Sig difference
(Hooper et al., 2011)	RCTs	21	71,790	Total mortality	All RCTs	0.98 [0.93, 1.04]	No sig difference
					Modified fat	1.02 [0.88, 1.18]	No sig difference
					Reduced fat	0.97 [0.90, 1.04]	No sig difference
					Reduced & modified fat	0.97 [0.76, 1.23]	No sig difference
				CVD mortality	All RCTs	0.94 [0.85, 1.04]	No sig difference
					Modified fat	0.92 [0.73, 1.15]	No sig difference
					Reduced fat	0.96 [0.82, 1.13]	No sig difference
					Reduced & modified fat	0.98 [0.76, 1.27]	No sig difference

(Hooper et al., 2011) (Cont'd)				CVD events	All RCTs	0.86 [0.77, 0.96]	Sig difference
					Modified fat	0.82 [0.66, 1.02]	No sig difference
					Reduced fat	0.97 [0.87, 1.08]	No sig difference
					Reduced & modified fat	0.77 [0.57, 1.03]	No sig difference
(Chowdhury et al., 2014)	Prospective cohort studies & RCTs	32	530,525	Coronary disease (All top vs. bottom third)	Sat fat	1.02 [0.97, 1.07]	No sig difference
					Monounsaturated fat	0.99 [0.89, 1.09]	No sig difference
					Polyunsaturated fat	0.93 [0.84, 1.02]	No sig difference
					Trans fat	1.16 [1.06, 1.27]	Sig difference
(Schwingshackl and Hoffmann, 2014)	RCTs	12	7,150	All cause mortality	Modified fat intake	0.92 [0.68, 1.25]	No sig difference
				CVD mortality	Modified fat intake	0.96 [0.65, 1.42]	No sig difference
				CVD events	Modified fat intake	0.85 [0.63, 1.15]	No sig difference
				MIIs	Modified fat intake	0.76 [0.54, 1.09]	No sig difference
				All cause mortality	Reduced fat intake	0.79 [0.42, 1.48]	No sig difference
				CVD mortality	Reduced fat intake	0.93 [0.66, 1.31]	No sig difference
				CVD events	Reduced fat intake	0.93 [0.65, 1.34]	No sig difference
				MIIs	Reduced fat intake	1.18 [0.88, 1.59]	No sig difference

(Harcombe et al., 2015)	RCTs to 1977/1983	6	2,467	All cause mortality	Reduced or modified fat	0.99 [0.87, 1.15]	No sig difference
				CHD mortality	Reduced or modified fat	0.99 [0.78, 1.25]	No sig difference
(Hooper et al., 2015)	RCTs	12	55,858	Total mortality	Reduced saturated fat	0.97 [0.90, 1.05]	No sig difference
				CVD mortality	Reduced saturated fat	0.95 [0.80, 1.12]	No sig difference
				CVD events	Reduced saturated fat	0.83 [0.72, 0.96]	Sig difference
				MIs	Reduced saturated fat	0.90 [0.80, 1.01]	No sig difference
				Non-fatal MIs	Reduced saturated fat	0.95 [0.80, 1.13]	No sig difference
				Stroke	Reduced saturated fat	1.00 [0.89, 1.12]	No sig difference
				CHD mortality	Reduced saturated fat	0.98 [0.84, 1.15]	No sig difference
				CHD events	Reduced saturated fat	0.87 [0.74, 1.03]	No sig difference

Table notes:

All studies examined data available at the time of the meta-analysis apart from Harcombe *et al*, which examined data available to the dietary committees.

Table 7.2 Study objectives and inclusion criteria.

	Objectives	Inclusion criteria
(Skeaff and Miller, 2009)	To summarise the evidence from cohort studies and RCTs of the relation between dietary fat and risk of CHD.	Endpoints available for CHD deaths, events & total CHD. Dietary interventions: 1) change in poly/sat ratio 2) reduction in total fat 3) increase in fish intake 4) increase in n-3. No minimum length specified. Shortest study was 2 yrs follow-up. Adults.
(Siri-Tarino et al., 2010)	Summarise the evidence for the association of sat fat with risk of CHD, stroke & CVD in prospective cohort studies.	1) sat fat intake available 2) endpoints for CVD deaths/events 3) association of sat fat with CVD evaluated 4) prospective cohort study 5) healthy adults at baseline. No min length specified. Shortest study was 5 yrs follow-up. Adults.
(Mozaffarian, Micha and Wallace, 2010)	Assess the effect of PUFA for SFA swap on CHD endpoints.	Increased total or n-6 PUFA; minimum 1 yr; reported sufficient data to calculate risk estimates for 'hard' CHD data – deaths/MIs. Adults.
(Hooper et al., 2011)	Assess the effect of reduced &/or modified dietary fat on mortality, CVD mortality/ events & other outcomes (MI, stroke, cancer) in RCTs min 6 mths duration.	1) RCT 2) reduced or modified fat or cholesterol intake 3) not multi factorial, 4) adults with or without CVD 5) Min duration 6 months 6) mortality or CV morbidity data available.
(Chowdhury et al., 2014)	To summarise evidence about associations between fatty acids and coronary disease.	Prospective cohorts & RCTs that reported on associations of dietary fat intake, circulating fatty acids or fatty acid intervention with risk of CHD (fatal or nonfatal). Min 1 yr duration. Adults. Coronary outcomes as endpoints recorded.
(Schwingshackl and	To investigate the effects of reduced and/or modified fat diets and dietary fatty acids on all-cause mortality,	RCTs comparing a modified or reduced fat diet vs control; min 1 yr duration; data on all-cause mortality, CVD mortality, CVD events and MIs available; secondary

Hoffmann, 2014)	CVD mortality and CVD events in participants with established CHD.	subjects only.
(Harcombe et al., 2015)	Review dietary fat RCTs, with all/CHD mortality, at time of setting dietary fat guidelines.	RCTs that examined the relationship between dietary fat, serum cholesterol & mortality; available in 1983; min 1 yr duration; data on all-cause mortality, CHD mortality & cholesterol available.
(Hooper et al., 2015)	Assess the effect of reducing sat fat intake & replacing it with carb, PUFA, MUFA &/or protein on mortality and cardiovascular morbidity, in RCTs min 2 yrs.	1) RCT 2) reduced or modified sat fat intake 3) not multi-factorial 4) adult humans with or without CVD 5) Minimum duration 24 months 6) mortality or cardiovascular morbidity data available.

Table notes:

All studies excluded multi-factorial studies. The most common duration considered was a minimum of one year. Hooper 2011 included studies with a minimum of 6 months duration; Hooper 2015 included studies with a minimum of 24 months duration.

Appendix 1 (Chapter Two)

Associations between GDP per capita, fat intake and deaths from heart disease

Yerushalmy and Hilleboe suggested that there were a number of dietary components, which appeared to be positively related to heart disease, but that these were also a reflection of related attributes of various countries. They proposed that the amount of fat and protein available for consumption was an index of a country's development: industrially; nutritionally; medically and in other aspects (p.2350) (Yerushalmy and Hilleboe, 1957).

Data for Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita are available for 20 of the 22 countries reviewed by Yerushalmy and Hilleboe for 1950 (Angus Maddison, 1950). The two countries for which data were unavailable were Ceylon and Israel.

GDP per capita and fat intake

The data show that there was a correlation between fat calories as a percentage of total calorie intake and GDP per capita in 1950. The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.7533 with a p value of 0.000126 ($p < 0.05$).

GDP per capita and deaths from heart disease

The data show that there was a correlation between deaths from heart disease per 100,000 men aged 55-59 and GDP per capita in 1950. The Pearson correlation coefficient was 0.4586 with a p value of 0.041978, ($p < 0.05$).

Appendix 2 (Chapter Three)

PRISMA check list

PRISMA (Moher et al., 2009) Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses			Reported in:
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review, meta-analysis, or both.	Both in title
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary including, as applicable: background; objectives; data sources; study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions; study appraisal and synthesis methods; results; limitations; conclusions and implications of key findings; systematic review registration number.	Introduction & methods
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known.	Introduction
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of questions being addressed with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, and study design (PICOS).	Introduction & methods
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate if a review protocol exists, if and where it can be accessed (e.g., Web address), and, if available, provide registration information including registration number.	N/A
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify study characteristics (e.g., PICOS, length of follow-up) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) used as criteria for eligibility, giving rationale.	Methods: data extraction
Information sources	7	Describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and date last searched.	Methods: search strategy &

			Fig. 3.1
Search	8	Present full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	Fig. 3.1
Study selection	9	State the process for selecting studies (i.e., screening, eligibility, included in systematic review, and, if applicable, included in the meta-analysis).	Methods: selection of Studies
Data collection process	10	Describe method of data extraction from reports (e.g., piloted forms, independently, in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	Original journal articles available in all cases
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought (e.g., PICOS, funding sources) and any assumptions and simplifications made.	Systematic review
Risk of bias in individual studies	12	Describe methods used for assessing risk of bias of individual studies (including specification of whether this was done at the study or outcome level), and how this information is to be used in any data synthesis.	Methods: statistical analysis & Fig. 3.2
Summary measures	13	State the principal summary measures (e.g., risk ratio, difference in means).	Methods: statistical analysis
Synthesis of results	14	Describe the methods of handling data and combining results of studies, if done, including measures of consistency (e.g., I ²) for each meta-analysis.	Methods: statistical analysis
Risk of bias across studies	15	Specify any assessment of risk of bias that may affect the cumulative evidence (e.g., publication bias, selective reporting within studies).	Methods: statistical analysis
Additional analyses	16	Describe methods of additional analyses (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression), if done, indicating which were pre-specified.	N/A
RESULTS			
Study selection	17	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for	Systematic review &

		exclusions at each stage, ideally with a flow diagram.	Fig. 3.1
Study characteristics	18	For each study, present characteristics for which data were extracted (e.g., study size, PICOS, follow-up period) and provide the citations.	Systematic review
Risk of bias within studies	19	Present data on risk of bias of each study and, if available, any outcome level assessment (see item 12).	Systematic review & Results & Fig. 3.2
Results of individual studies	20	For all outcomes considered (benefits or harms), present, for each study: (a) simple summary data for each intervention group (b) effect estimates and confidence intervals, ideally with a forest plot.	Fig. 3.3 & 3.4
Synthesis of results	21	Present results of each meta-analysis done, including confidence intervals and measures of consistency.	Results & Fig. 3.3 & 3.4
Risk of bias across studies	22	Present results of any assessment of risk of bias across studies (see Item 15).	Results & Funnel plots
Additional analysis	23	Give results of additional analyses, if done (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression [see Item 16]).	N/A
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	24	Summarize the main findings including the strength of evidence for each main outcome; consider their relevance to key groups (e.g., healthcare providers, users, and policy makers).	Discussion
Limitations	25	Discuss limitations at study and outcome level (e.g., risk of bias), and at review-level (e.g., incomplete retrieval of identified research, reporting bias).	Discussion
Conclusions	26	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	Discussion
Funding	27	Describe sources of funding for the systematic review and other support (e.g., supply of data); role of funders for the systematic review.	N/A

Appendix 3 (Chapter Three)

Funnel plots

Funnel plot for All deaths

Funnel plot for CHD deaths

Appendix 4 (Chapter Four)

PRISMA check list

PRISMA (Moher et al., 2009) Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses			Reported in:
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review, meta-analysis, or both.	Both in title
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary including, as applicable: background; objectives; data sources; study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions; study appraisal and synthesis methods; results; limitations; conclusions and implications of key findings; systematic review registration number.	Introduction & methods
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known.	Introduction
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of questions being addressed with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, and study design (PICOS).	Introduction & methods
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate if a review protocol exists, if and where it can be accessed (e.g., Web address), and, if available, provide registration information including registration number.	N/A
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify study characteristics (e.g., PICOS, length of follow-up) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) used as criteria for eligibility, giving rationale.	Methods: data extraction
Information sources	7	Describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and date last	Methods: search strategy &

		searched.	Fig. 4.1
Search	8	Present full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	Fig. 4.1
Study selection	9	State the process for selecting studies (i.e., screening, eligibility, included in systematic review, and, if applicable, included in the meta-analysis).	Methods: selection of Studies
Data collection process	10	Describe method of data extraction from reports (e.g., piloted forms, independently, in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	Original journal articles available in all cases
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought (e.g., PICOS, funding sources) and any assumptions and simplifications made.	Systematic review
Risk of bias in individual studies	12	Describe methods used for assessing risk of bias of individual studies (including specification of whether this was done at the study or outcome level), and how this information is to be used in any data synthesis.	Methods: statistical analysis & Fig. 4.2
Summary measures	13	State the principal summary measures (e.g., risk ratio, difference in means).	Methods: statistical analysis
Synthesis of results	14	Describe the methods of handling data and combining results of studies, if done, including measures of consistency (e.g., I ²) for each meta-analysis.	Methods: statistical analysis
Risk of bias across studies	15	Specify any assessment of risk of bias that may affect the cumulative evidence (e.g., publication bias, selective reporting within studies).	Methods: statistical analysis
Additional analyses	16	Describe methods of additional analyses (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression), if done, indicating which were pre-specified.	N/A
RESULTS			
Study selection	17	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for	Systematic review &

		exclusions at each stage, ideally with a flow diagram.	Fig. 4.1
Study characteristics	18	For each study, present characteristics for which data were extracted (e.g., study size, PICOS, follow-up period) and provide the citations.	Systematic review
Risk of bias within studies	19	Present data on risk of bias of each study and, if available, any outcome level assessment (see item 12).	Systematic review & Results & Fig. 4.2
Results of individual studies	20	For all outcomes considered (benefits or harms), present, for each study: (a) simple summary data for each intervention group (b) effect estimates and confidence intervals, ideally with a forest plot.	Fig. 4.3 & 4.4
Synthesis of results	21	Present results of each meta-analysis done, including confidence intervals and measures of consistency.	Results & Fig. 4.3 & 4.4
Risk of bias across studies	22	Present results of any assessment of risk of bias across studies (see Item 15).	Results & Funnel plots
Additional analysis	23	Give results of additional analyses, if done (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression [see Item 16]).	N/A
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	24	Summarize the main findings including the strength of evidence for each main outcome; consider their relevance to key groups (e.g., healthcare providers, users, and policy makers).	Discussion
Limitations	25	Discuss limitations at study and outcome level (e.g., risk of bias), and at review-level (e.g., incomplete retrieval of identified research, reporting bias).	Discussion
Conclusions	26	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	Discussion
Funding	27	Describe sources of funding for the systematic review and other support (e.g., supply of data); role of funders for the systematic review.	N/A

Appendix 5 (Chapter Four)

Funnel plots

Funnel plot for All deaths

Funnel plot for CHD deaths

Appendix 6 (Chapter Five)

MOOSE check list

MOOSE (Stroup et al., 2000) Meta-Analysis of Observational Studies in Epidemiology	Reported in:
Reporting of background should include Problem definition Hypothesis statement Description of study outcome(s) Type of exposure or intervention used Type of study designs used Study population	Background Introduction Introduction Introduction Introduction/Methods Methods Methods
Reporting of search strategy should include Qualifications of searchers (e.g., librarians and investigators) Search strategy, including time period included in the synthesis and keywords Effort to include all available studies, including contact with authors Databases and registries searched Search software used, name and version, including special features used Use of hand searching (e.g., reference lists of obtained articles) List of citations located and those excluded, including justification Method of addressing articles published in languages other than English Method of handling abstracts and unpublished studies Description of any contact with authors	Search strategy PhD student Methods/Search strategy (Fig. 5.1) Methods/Search strategy Methods/Search strategy Methods/Search strategy Methods/Select. studies Methods/Select. studies Only English language searched Methods/Select. studies N/A – pre 1983 papers
Reporting of methods should include Description of relevance or appropriateness of studies assembled for assessing the hypothesis to be tested Rationale for the selection and coding of data (e.g., sound clinical principles or convenience) Documentation of how data were classified and coded (e.g., multiple raters, blinding, and interrater reliability) Assessment of confounding (e.g., comparability of cases and controls in studies where appropriate)	Reporting methods Method/Selection of studies Method/Selection of studies Method/Selection of studies N/A

<p>Assessment of study quality, including blinding of quality assessors; stratification or regression on possible predictors of study results</p> <p>Assessment of heterogeneity</p> <p>Description of statistical methods (e.g., complete description of fixed or random effects models, justification of whether the chosen models account for predictors of study results, dose-response models, or cumulative meta-analysis)</p> <p>Provision of appropriate tables and graphics</p>	<p>Bias table (Fig. 5.2)</p> <p>Results</p> <p>Not possible with data available</p> <p>Table 5.2</p>
<p>Reporting of results should include</p> <p>Graphic summarizing individual study estimates and overall estimate</p> <p>Table giving descriptive information for each study included</p> <p>Results of sensitivity testing (e.g., subgroup analysis)</p> <p>Indication of statistical uncertainty of findings</p>	<p>Reporting results</p> <p>Summary table (Table 5.2)</p> <p>Table 5.2</p> <p>Not possible with data available</p> <p>Table 5.2</p>
<p>Reporting of discussion should include</p> <p>Quantitative assessment of bias (e.g., publication bias)</p> <p>Justification for exclusion</p> <p>Assessment of quality of included studies</p>	<p>Reporting discussion</p> <p>Fig. 5.2</p> <p>N/A</p> <p>Results: systematic review</p>
<p>Reporting of conclusions should include</p> <p>Consideration of alternative explanations for observed results</p> <p>Generalization of the conclusions (i.e., appropriate for the data presented and within the domain of the literature review)</p> <p>Guidelines for future research</p>	<p>Reporting discussion</p> <p>Discussion</p> <p>Discussion</p> <p>In final chapter of thesis</p>
<p>Disclosure of funding source</p>	<p>N/A</p>

Appendix 7 (Chapter Five)

Number of men sampled in The Seven Countries Study

The following table documents the number of men in each cohort (table I.2, p.I-7) (Keys, 1970a) and the number of men who participated in a 7-day diary food sample process, as documented in the main dietary document for The Seven Countries Study (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). There were no data for the Japanese or Rome cohorts and these were excluded from figures in Volume XVII (Keys, 1970i) indicating that dietary information was not available.

Dalmatia and Slavonia were calculated as the average of four samples (table 1, p.113) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). For USA railroad men, dietary sampling was reported as “recall interview of all men” (p.I-6) (Keys, 1970a). Finland, east and west, were reported (table 6, p.35) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). Crevalcore and Montegiorgio were reported (table 3, p.72) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). Zutphen sampling was calculated (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968) as an average of 3 samples (table 1, p.89). Crete was calculated as an average of 3 samples and Corfu as an average of 2 samples (table 3, p.60) (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968). The three Yugoslavian cohorts of Velika Krsna, Zrenjanin and Belgrade were calculated from: (table 1, p.149), an average of two samples; (table 2, p.150), an average of two samples; and (table 3, p.151) from one sample (den Hartog, Buzina and Fidanza, 1968).

	Start	Men	Sampled	% sampled	High/Low
Japan – Tanushimaru	1958	509			
Yugoslavia – Dalmatia	1958	672	36	5.4%	
Yugoslavia – Slavonia	1958	699	37	5.3%	
USA – Railroad workers	1958-60	2,571			
Finland – east (north Karelia)	1959	817	30	3.7%	
Finland – west	1959	860	30	3.5%	
Italy – Crevalcore	1960	993	28	2.8%	Lowest
Italy – Montegiorgio	1960	719	34	4.7%	
The Netherlands – Zutphen	1960	878	52	5.9%	

Japan – Ushibuka	1960	504			
Greece – Crete	1960	686	32	4.7%	
Greece – Corfu	1961	529	37	7.0%	
Italy – Rome Railroad workers	1962	768			
Yugoslavia – Velika Krsna	1962	511	40	7.8%	
Yugoslavia – Zrenjanin	1963	516	42	8.1%	Highest
Yugoslavia – Belgrade	1964	538	41	7.6%	
TOTAL		12,770	439	3.4%	Average

Appendix 8 (Chapter Five)

Correlations with CHD deaths using Keys' data

Keys reported correlation coefficients with 13 or 14 cohorts as follows (p.I-168) (Keys, 1970i):

1) Median serum cholesterol and saturated fat as a percentage of calories: $r = 0.89$ (p.I-170). This was based on 14 cohorts, with Ushibuka and Rome Railroad missing.

2) Median serum cholesterol and CHD deaths and infarctions per 100 people: $r = 0.76$ (p.I-172). This was based on 13 cohorts, with both Japanese cohorts and Rome Railroad missing.

3) CHD deaths and infarctions and total fat as a percentage of calories: $r = 0.40$ (p.I-173). This was based on 13 cohorts, with both Japanese cohorts and Rome Railroad missing.

4) CHD deaths and infarctions and saturated fat as a percentage of calories: $r = 0.84$ (p.I-174). This was based on 13 cohorts, with both Japanese cohorts and Rome Railroad missing.

Using the data in Table 2, the Pearson correlation coefficient has been calculated for the component parts of the diet-heart hypothesis, for CHD deaths alone, at the cohort level, as follows:

Correlation between:	R	R ²	p value
Median cholesterol (mg/dl) & % calories from saturated fat	0.876	0.767	0.00019
Median cholesterol (mg/dl) & CHD deaths per 100,000	0.784	0.614	0.00033
CHD deaths per 100,000 & % calories from total fat	0.433	0.187	0.16025 (*)
CHD deaths per 100,000 & % calories from saturated fat	0.786	0.618	0.00244

(*) All p values are significant at $p < 0.05$ except this one for total fat and CHD deaths per 100,000 people.

The correlations for CHD deaths alone are based on 12 cohorts. The data in Table 2 was extracted from Volume I of the *Circulation* report (table I.2, p.I-7) (Keys, 1970a). The dietary fat intake data was available for 12 cohorts, excluding Ushibuka, Rome railroad, Zrenjanin and Belgrade.

Using Pearson correlation coefficients, strong relationships were established between the component parts of the diet-heart hypothesis, using saturated, not total, dietary fat and using CHD deaths alone, excluding infarctions.

Appendix 9 (Chapter Five)

Correlation with latitude and CHD deaths

Cohort:	Men	CHD death rate per 1000	Mean baseline cholesterol mg/dl	Latitude (° N)
USA – Railroad workers	2,571	202	240.3	48
Finland – East Finland	817	288	265.0	64
Finland – West Finland	860	192	256.2	60
The Netherlands – Zutphen	878	197	235.6	52
Italy – Crevalcore	993	134	201.6	45
Italy – Montegiorgio	719	115	201.3	43
Italy – Rome Railroad workers	768	132	207.3	41
Yugoslavia – Dalmatia	671	81	189.1	40
Yugoslavia – Slavonia	696	142	199.5	45
Yugoslavia – Velika Krsna	511	122	160.3	44
Yugoslavia – Zrenjanin	516	177	168.6	45
Yugoslavia – Belgrade	536	118	211.7	44
Greece – Crete	686	46	207.1	35
Greece – Corfu	529	95	203.8	39
Japan – Tanushimaru	508	45	167.9	33
Japan – Ushibuka	502	63	162.2	32

Cohort latitude calculation: $r = A/\text{sq rt } (B)(C)$

A = 126,210

B = 18,140

C = 1,014,167

B*C = 1.8397E+10

Sqrt = 135,636

r = 0.93

Country latitude calculation: $r = A/\sqrt{B(C)}$

$$A = 27,592$$

$$B = 4,003$$

$$C = 205,944$$

$$B * C = 824,362,998$$

$$\text{Sqrt} = 28,712$$

$$\mathbf{r = 0.96}$$

Appendix 10 (Chapter Six)

MOOSE check list

MOOSE (Stroup et al., 2000) Meta-Analysis of Observational Studies in Epidemiology	Reported in:
Reporting of background should include Problem definition Hypothesis statement Description of study outcome(s) Type of exposure or intervention used Type of study designs used Study population	Background Introduction Introduction Introduction Introduction/Methods Methods Methods
Reporting of search strategy should include Qualifications of searchers (e.g., librarians and investigators) Search strategy, including time period included in the synthesis and keywords Effort to include all available studies, including contact with authors Databases and registries searched Search software used, name and version, including special features used Use of hand searching (e.g., reference lists of obtained articles) List of citations located and those excluded, including justification Method of addressing articles published in languages other than English Method of handling abstracts and unpublished studies Description of any contact with authors	Search strategy PhD student Methods/Search strategy (Fig. 6.1) Methods/Search strategy Methods/Search strategy Methods/Search strategy Methods/Select. studies Methods/Select. studies Only English language searched Methods/Select. studies Discussion
Reporting of methods should include Description of relevance or appropriateness of studies assembled for assessing the hypothesis to be tested Rationale for the selection and coding of data (e.g., sound clinical principles or convenience) Documentation of how data were classified and coded (e.g., multiple raters, blinding, and interrater reliability) Assessment of confounding (e.g., comparability of cases and controls in studies where appropriate)	Reporting methods Method/Selection of studies Method/Selection of studies Method/Selection of studies N/A

<p>Assessment of study quality, including blinding of quality assessors; stratification or regression on possible predictors of study results</p> <p>Assessment of heterogeneity</p> <p>Description of statistical methods (e.g., complete description of fixed or random effects models, justification of whether the chosen models account for predictors of study results, dose-response models, or cumulative meta-analysis)</p> <p>Provision of appropriate tables and graphics</p>	<p>Bias table (Fig. 6.2)</p> <p>Results</p> <p>Results/Fig. 6.3 & 6.4</p> <p>Tables 6.1 & 6.2/Fig. 6.3 & 6.4</p>
<p>Reporting of results should include</p> <p>Graphic summarizing individual study estimates and overall estimate</p> <p>Table giving descriptive information for each study included</p> <p>Results of sensitivity testing (e.g., subgroup analysis)</p> <p>Indication of statistical uncertainty of findings</p>	<p>Reporting results</p> <p>Summary tables (Table 6.1 & 6.2)</p> <p>Tables 6.1 & 6.2</p> <p>Not possible with data available</p> <p>Tables 6.1 & 6.2</p>
<p>Reporting of discussion should include</p> <p>Quantitative assessment of bias (e.g., publication bias)</p> <p>Justification for exclusion</p> <p>Assessment of quality of included studies</p>	<p>Reporting discussion</p> <p>Fig. 6.2</p> <p>N/A</p> <p>Results: systematic review</p>
<p>Reporting of conclusions should include</p> <p>Consideration of alternative explanations for observed results</p> <p>Generalization of the conclusions (i.e., appropriate for the data presented and within the domain of the literature review)</p> <p>Guidelines for future research</p>	<p>Reporting discussion</p> <p>Discussion</p> <p>Discussion</p> <p>In final chapter of thesis</p>
<p>Disclosure of funding source</p>	<p>N/A</p>

Appendix 11 (Chapter Six)

Funnel plots

Funnel plot for total fat & CHD deaths

Funnel plot for saturated fat & CHD deaths

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